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Antibacterial Activity of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom against Some Selected Bacteria

AKIN-OSANAIYE B. C.¹; DAHUNSI A. A.*²

¹Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

²Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding author: ayodeji.dahunsi2022@uniabuja.edu.ng; 08066761700

Abstract: Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are essential components of the innate immune system that display potent antimicrobial activity against a wide range of microorganisms. Scorpion venoms, known for their diverse molecular compositions, have been identified as rich sources of AMPs. This study focused on the antimicrobial potential of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom against selected bacteria isolated from drinking water sources. The physicochemical characteristics of the venom were analyzed, revealing a colorless, odorless, transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries easily at room temperature. The study involved the collection of 50 Emperor Scorpions, with venom extracted through electrical stimulation. The venom was purified and tested against bacterial isolates, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Analytical Profile Index (API) kits confirmed bacterial identification. The results revealed concentration-dependent antibacterial activity, with the highest zone of inhibition at 11.5mm (100% concentration) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values ranged from 25% to 50%, while minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined at 75%. The venom's effectiveness was comparable to commercial antibiotics. Physicochemical analysis, bacterial identification, and antimicrobial assays collectively support the potential of Emperor Scorpion venom as a non-toxic antibacterial agent. This research contributes valuable insights for further exploration of scorpion venom in therapeutic applications and suggests avenues for scorpion farming, extraction expertise, and public awareness to maximize the benefits of this natural resource.

Key Words: Emperor Scorpion, *Pandinus imperator*, Scorpion Venom, Antimicrobial Peptides, Antibacterial Activity.

1 Introduction

Antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, protozoan, and viruses (Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019; Ovuru, et al., 2023). The discovery of antimicrobials like penicillin and tetracycline paved the way for better health for millions around the world. Before 1941, the year where penicillin was discovered, there were no true cure for some diseases such as gonorrhoea (a venereal disease involving inflammatory discharge from the urethra or vagina), strep throat (a painful infection in the throat caused by group A streptococcus), or pneumonia (a lung infection in which the air sacs are filled with fluid) (Cosgrove et al., 2003). The resistance to antibiotics is a rising concern among health care professionals, driving the search for peptides with antimicrobial activities in plants, bacteria, and animals (Adesina et al., 2013; Shaini et al., 2010; Enerijiofi and

Isola, 2019). Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are key effector of the innate immune response of animals and show antimicrobial therapy potency (Yibao et al., 2009; Ramamoorthy, 2009). Most AMPs that display hydrophobic and cationic properties have a molecular mass below 25 to 30 kDa (Marsh et al., 2009). So far, more than 2,000 natural AMPs have been isolated, sequenced and submitted (Jupeng et al., 2021). Some natural antimicrobial peptides are being developed for use either as antibiotics for topical use in healthcare or as preservatives in the food industry. Apart from the extreme diversity in their primary and secondary structures, AMPs have in vitro effects on a wide spectrum of bacteria (Gram-negative and Gram-positive) and cells, including parasites, tumor cells, fungi and viruses (Bulet et al., 2004). AMPs have non-specific processes involved in the antimicrobial action. The unique property of an antimicrobial peptide is its ability to interact selectively with bacterial lipid membrane and cause disruption.

This property could decrease the likelihood of microbes acquiring resistance to AMPs. This could give AMPs a major advantage over conventional antibiotics, and in response, these peptides have been extensively investigated as potential antimicrobial agents (Harris et al., 2009; Thennarasu et al., 2010a, b; Ramamoorthy et al., 2010). Scorpions are particularly resistant to bacterial aggressions, and it is of interest to analyze the molecules responsible for this resistance (Sabatier et al., 1996). The scorpion venoms have three different groups of ingredients and peptides, based on their molecular mass with enzyme activity such as hyaluronidases, phospholipases, and sphingomyelinase (Chao et al., 2008). The second group contains mainly a peptide fraction with molecular mass around and lower than 10 kDa such as toxins and cytolytic compounds. The third group is composed of components such as ions, free amino acids, biogenic amines, neurotransmitters, acylpolyamines, heterocyclic compounds and alkaloids (Ma et al., 2010; Kuhn-Nentwig, 2003). Different antimicrobial peptides such as micropores have been identified from plants and animals (He et al., 2008; Zhao et al., 2009), BmKb1 and BmKn2 (Zeng et al., 2004), Hadrurin (Torres-Larios et al., 2000) and Mucroporin (Chao et al., 2008). Caerin is an antimicrobial peptide that was first found in amphibian, Australian green tree frog (Wong et al., 1997). Later different variants were isolated from a number of Australian frogs of the *Litoria* genus (Brian et al., 2000; Steinborner et al., 1998) and African frog (Gottler and Ramamoorthy, 2009). In recent years, caerin and caerin-like antimicrobial peptides were been found in scorpions such as *Mesobuthus lupus* and *Mesobuthus martensii* (Luo et al., 2005). Antibacterial activity of caerin on Gram-positive and negative bacteria has been shown with only small variation in their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values (Boland and Separovic, 2006; Chia et al., 2011).

The venom or antimicrobial peptides found in scorpion has shown a broad-spectrum activity against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms. Viral, bacterial, fungal and parasitic infections ranging from malaria, hepatitis C, meningitis, tetanus, and many nosocomial infections, etc have been treated successfully with scorpion venom. Scorpion venom is also used for treatment of non-communicable and neurological disease such as stroke, rheumatism,

diabetes, cancer, brain tumor, human neuroblastoma cells etc (Attarde and Pandit, 2016; El-Bitar et al., 2015; Petricerich et al., 2013). The emperor scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) and several additional venom peptides had been characterized as antibacterial peptides with a broad-spectrum of bacterial targets against even the antibiotic-resistant strains (Baradaran et al., 20112).

The purpose of this study was to determine the possibility of using The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom as an alternative to conventional antibacterial agent against some bacterial isolates.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Gwagwalada is one of the six area councils of the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. Gwagwalada is also the name of the main town in the Local Government Area, which has an area of 1,043 km² and a population of 157,770 as of the 2006 census. It is located at an elevation of 210 meters above sea level. Its coordinates are 8°56'29" N and 7°05'31" E in DMS (Degree Minutes Seconds) or 8.94139 and 7.09194 in decimal degrees. Its Universal Transverse Mercator position is KQ98 and its Joint Operation Graphics reference is NC32-13 (Wikipedia, 2016).

2.2 Media and Preparation

All media used were prepared according to the manufacturer's standard preparation procedures.

2.3 Sample Collection

In the Zoology Department of the Faculty of Science at the University of Abuja, fifty Emperor Scorpions (*Pandinus imperator*) were selected for venom collection. The venoms were harvested using the electrical stimulation technique outlined by Ozkan and Filazi in 2004. A series of regular currents were applied to shock the scorpions until the venom was ejected. For this purpose, the scorpions were immersed in a saline solution for better electrical conduction and shocked with electrodes using a simple 12-volt battery. The venom droplets were collected in sterile test tubes, with part of the venom stored in ice and used within 30 minutes, while the rest was frozen until further use. The venom was recovered using distilled water and centrifuged at 10,000 g. The supernatant was freeze-dried and stored at -20°C until use. All venom collected was

passed through a membrane filter.

2.4 Collection of Test Organisms

Drinking water samples, each totaling 20 ml, were collected from various sources of drinking water supply across the University of Abuja, including the main site, mini campus, and staff quarters. These samples were transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at the University of Abuja for culturing, isolation, and identification of specific test bacteria.

2.5 Preparation of Samples

2.5.1 Preparation of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom

The venom of *Pandinus imperator* was collected and measured in percentage since the venom is in liquid state. Raw venom represents 100%, while 50%, 25%, and 12.5% were diluted with 50%, 75%, and 87.5% of appropriate neutral diluents (sterile water) respectively, and also at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml.

2.5.2 Preparation of Test Organisms

The samples collected were taken to the laboratory in a sterile plastic container. Using the serial dilution method, bacteria from the drinking water samples were cultured on an enrichment medium, incubated, and plated on MacConkey agar at 37°C for 24 hours. Suspected colonies were further sub-cultured on selective media (CHROM agar, Eosin methylene blue (EMB), and Cetrimide agar). Colonies were identified based on their color: red, metallic green sheen, and blue-green/yellow-green. A single colony was picked, screened, and identified based on the Analytical Profile Index (API). The organism was sub-cultured on selective media and confirmed using standard biochemical techniques (Cheesbrough, 1998).

2.6 Antibacterial Activity of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom (Peptides)

Antimicrobial sensitivity tests of the isolates were performed using the standard agar well diffusion method described by Bauer et al. (1996). The venom was tested at different concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml) to determine antibacterial activity by measuring the zones of inhibition.

2.7 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by preparing various concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml) of the venom using the dilution method. Test tubes were set up with 2 ml of nutrient broth, with control tubes including venom control, organism control, and negative control. A 0.2 ml suspension of the test organisms was added to the test tubes. The preparation was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, after which turbidity or clearness was observed. The least concentration with no turbidity was noted as the MIC value.

2.8 Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined from the broth dilution resulting from MIC tubes by sub-culturing to the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates using a sterile inoculating loop as described by Vollekova et al. (2001) and Usman et al. (2007). Test tubes showing no microbial growth after 24 hours of incubation were sub-cultured on nutrient agar plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and observed for growth. The plates with the lowest concentration of the venom showing no bacterial growth were noted as the MBC.

2.9 Comparing the Effects of Emperor Scorpion Venom with Commercial Antibiotics

The results were compared with standard antibiotics. Inhibition effects were measured in terms of the zone of inhibition.

2.10 Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, including simple percentages and standard deviation of the mean. Microsoft Excel was used for statistical significance, and ANOVA was performed to determine if there were any statistically significant differences between the venoms and isolates. Differences in survival were considered significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

3 Results

3.1 Physical Characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The result of the physico-chemical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* venom is shown in Table 1. The venom was observed to be colorless, odorless, and a transparent liquid which dries easily at room temperature.

Table 1: Physical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

Colour	Odour	Form	pH	Room Temperature (28°C)
Colourless	Odourless	Transparent Liquid	4.5	Dried up easily

3.2 Analytical Profile Index (API-20E)

The result of the Analytical Profile Index of the bacterial identification of isolates shows the different bacteria isolated from the three water sources studied were *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *A. baumannii* (Table ??).

The result for the mean \pm SD inhibition zone of diameter of *Pandinus Imperator* venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja drinking water at different concentrations of 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% respectively is shown in Table 2. To interpret the results of the zones of inhibition, the antibacterial and inhibitory effect of the venom was considered at the concentration of 30 mg/ml as compared to that of chloramphenicol (30 μ g), a standard antibiotic. When interpreted using the CLSI, 2004 guide, a zone of chloramphenicol (30 μ g) 18 is sensitive, 12 is resistant, while 13-17 is intermediate.

The mean \pm SD of inhibition zone of ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms at different concentrations

Table 2: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja Drinking Water

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.1 \pm 0.0	7.2 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	10.0 \pm 0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5.7 \pm 0.0	7.0 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	11.5 \pm 0.0
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	3.0 \pm 0.0	4.7 \pm 0.0	6.0 \pm 0.0	8.2 \pm 0.0

of 62.5 mg/ml, 125 mg/ml, 250 mg/ml, and 500 mg/ml is shown in Table 3.

3.3 Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 4. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to inhibit the growth of the organisms.

3.4 Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 5. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to kill the organisms.

The MBC obtained in the study was 75%, indicating that the venom was effective against the isolated test organisms.

4 Discussion

This research was carried out to determine the antibacterial activities of *Pandinus imperator* venom against some selected bacteria.

Table 1 shows the physiochemical characteristics of the venom. According to this table, the venom is odorless, colorless, and a transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries up easily at room temperature.

Table ?? presents the Analytical Profile Index (API) results for selected bacteria obtained from water samples at the University of Abuja.

Table 2 displays the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of *Pandinus imperator* venom against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 3 mm at 25% against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 11.5 mm at 100% against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 3: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of Ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	62.5	125	250	500
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26	31	36	38
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	23	25	28	31

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MIC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Clear (No growth), - = Turbid (Growth)

Table 5: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MBC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Bacterial growth, - = No bacterial growth

Table 3 shows the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of commercial antibiotics against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 23 mm at 62.5 mg/ml against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 38 mm at 500 mg/ml against *Escherichia coli*.

Table 4 provides the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MIC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 25%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 50%.

Table 5 shows the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MBC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 50%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 75%.

All the antibacterial activities, MIC, and MBC support the findings of Ahmed et al. (2012), Baradaran et al. (2012), Cao et al. (2012), Nie et al. (2012), Zhao et al. (2009), Carballar-Lejarazú et al. (2008), Gawade (2007), Lee et al. (2004), Reddy et al. (2004), and Reddy et al. (2003), among others.

The action of antimicrobial peptides toward bacterial membranes is initiated by electrostatic interactions with negatively charged components of membranes, such as strong interactions with lipopolysaccharides in the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria and acidic phospholipids in the outer cell wall of gram-positive bacteria. After the initial attachment, antimicrobial peptides aggregate within membranes, leading to membrane destruction achieved through channel (pore) formation (Guo et al., 2013).

5 Conclusion

From this research work, it can be concluded or deduced that Venom of Pandinus imperator called Emperor Scorpion found in West Africa is an antibacterial agent that is non-toxic to animals, the scorpion venom has the same potency and can both be safely used as a therapeutic agent. **Conflict of interest**

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

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Antibacterial Activities of Blowfly (*Lucilla sericata*) and Housefly (*Musca domestica*) Maggots Extract on Some Selected Isolates

UGOH S. C.¹; DAHUNSI A. A.*¹

¹Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding author: ayodeji.dahunsi2022@uniabuja.edu.ng; 08066761700

Abstract: Antimicrobial substances have played a pivotal role in global health since the discovery of penicillin in 1941. However, the rise of antimicrobial resistance poses a significant threat to public health. This study focuses on the potential antibacterial properties of maggot extracts from *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* on selected bacterial isolates. The study was conducted in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria, with maggot collection, extraction, and antibacterial assays carried out through agar-well diffusion methods. The results indicate dose-dependent antibacterial activity, with the aqueous extract showing the highest efficacy. The minimum inhibitory concentrations were determined, highlighting varying sensitivities among tested bacteria. The findings suggest the potential of maggot extracts as alternative antimicrobial agents, emphasizing their efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This research provides a scientific basis for considering maggot extracts in the development of new therapies, particularly for infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria.

Key Words: Antimicrobial resistance, Maggot extracts, Antibacterial activity, Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), *Staphylococcus aureus*

1 Introduction

Antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, or protozoan, as well as killing viruses. The discovery of antimicrobials like penicillin and tetracycline paved the way for better health for millions around the world. Before 1941, the year where penicillin was discovered, there were no true cure existed for some diseases such as gonorrhoea (a venereal disease involving inflammatory discharge from the urethra or vagina), strep throat, or pneumonia (a lung infection in which the air sacs fill with pus). Often, the infected wound patients have a wounded limb removed, or face death from the infection. Research into antibacterial activity is crucial for safeguarding the health of millions worldwide. The quest for new cures against diseases caused by microorganisms underscores the significance of this endeavor, as it directly impacts human health and well-being.

Some of the microorganisms, especially bacteria are becoming resistant to more and more antibacterial agents. By making a new research, antibacterial agents that can kill or inhibit the growth of other bacteria can be found (Cosgrove *et al.*, 2003). Now, most of these infections can be cured easily with a short course of antibacterial.

Microorganisms, especially bacteria are becoming resistant to more and more antimicrobial agent. They are becoming resistant more quickly than new drugs that are being made available. Therefore, future research in antimicrobial therapy may focus on finding the new antimicrobial that can overcome this problem, or treat infections with alternative means.

The increase of life-threatening infections that are resistant to commonly used antibiotics has become a worldwide problem (Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019). It is becoming an important cause of morbidity in immune-compromised patients particularly in developing countries (Al-Bari *et al.*, 2006). The increasing prevalence of multi-drug resistant strain of bacteria and the recent appearance of strains with reduced susceptibility to antibiotics has raised the spectre of untreatable bacterial infection and adds urgency to search for new infection - fighting strategies (Akortha *et al.*, 2010; Zy *et al.*, 2005, Rojas *et al.*, 2006).

Presently, there are global problems of emergence of multiple antibiotics resistance as well as emergence of new and resurrection of previously eradicated disease. There is need to search for new and more potent antimicrobial compounds of natural origin to complement the existing synthetic antimicrobial

drugs that are gradually becoming less potent against pathogenic microorganisms (Adesina *et al.*, 2013).

The continuous spread of multi-drugs resistant pathogen has become a serious threat to public health and major concern for infection control practitioners' worldwide (Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). In addition to the increasing cost of drug regimens, this scenario has paved way for the re-emergence of previously controlled disease and has contributed substantially to the high frequency of opportunistic and chronic infection cases in developing countries (Fernandez *et al.*, 2003 and Ako-Nai *et al.*, 2003.)

The extract of fly maggot has been shown to completely lyse the cell wall of many bacteria including those that infect chronic wounds. As the population ages, the number of patients suffering from bacteria infected chronic wounds attributable to diseases such as diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disease is on the rise. This poses a significant impact on the health care system, because of the chronicity of care required and the associated costs.

i. The aim of this study was to determine the antibacterial effects of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* maggot extracts against some selected bacterial isolates.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area for this research is Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. The territory is located just north of the confluence of the River Niger and River Benue. It is bordered by the states of Niger to the West and North, Kaduna to the Northeast and South, and Kogi to the Southwest. The Federal Capital Territory lies between latitude 8.25 and 9.20 North of the equator and longitude 6.45 and 7.23 East of the Greenwich Meridian. Abuja is geographically located in the centre of the country.

2.2 Collection and Preparation of Live Maggot

The maggots of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica* were jointly collected by allowing flies to feed on cattle liver in different transparent plastic containers covered with a rubber net to enable the flies to feed and lay their eggs effectively. The flies were allowed to escape by opening the rubber net after 2 hours. After an incubation period of 24 hours, the eggs hatched and developed into larvae known as maggots.

The first generation of larvae was allowed to turn into pupae to get a new breed of flies, which were reintroduced into another fresh transparent plastic container containing fresh cattle liver for feeding and laying of eggs. This process was repeated thrice to aseptically obtain clean flies' maggots since they were not allowed to roam outside the study environment and feed on dirt. It took around 7 days for a fly life cycle to be completed depending on the temperature, and maggots grow well in the dark.

2.3 Harvesting of Maggots

The third instar maggots were harvested from the transparent plastic containers containing cattle liver by removing them with a sterile teaspoon and transferring them into a sterile universal bottle and taken to the laboratory.

2.4 Decontamination of Maggots

Whole live maggots were decontaminated by soaking in 70% alcohol for 5 minutes. Thereafter, they were transferred into another sterile container covered with a rubber net to prevent maggots from escaping while allowing alcohol to evaporate from the body of the maggots. Maggots were kept in this decontaminated container for 30 minutes to allow the recovery of normal metabolism by maggots to produce efficient extracts which are located in the guts.

2.5 Maggot Extraction Procedures

2.5.1 Aqueous Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi *et al.* (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of sterile water and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at room temperature. The mixture of pulverized maggot and sterile water was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifugation at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.5.2 Saline Water Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi *et al.* (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of saline water

and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at 28°C. The mixture of pulverized maggot and saline water was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifuging at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.5.3 Phosphate Buffer Saline Extraction

This was carried out according to the method of Suchi et al. (2010). Maggots numbering 200, 400, 600, and 800 were respectively pulverized to paste in a plastic laboratory mortar with a plastic laboratory pestle. The paste was collected and soaked in 2 ml of PBS and allowed to incubate for 1 hour at room temperature. The mixture of pulverized maggot and PBS was transferred into a centrifuge test tube to remove the particulate by centrifuging it at 5,000g for 15 minutes at room temperature (25±2°C). The supernatant was collected for antibacterial screening.

2.6 Preparation of Extract Concentrations

Ahmed and Nancy (2012) state that the total protein measured from native excretory/secretory product of 100 larvae per 1 ml distilled water was 0.9 mg. Therefore, 200 maggots per 2 ml of distilled water will be 0.9 mg.

2.7 Identification of Bacterial Isolates Used

The bacterial isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*. They were clinical isolates obtained from University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja, Nigeria. The cultures were gram-stained for proper confirmation using standard gram staining procedures. The cultures were maintained on nutrient agar slants at 36°C after which they were stored in the refrigerator and later re-identified and sub-cultured by biochemical test (Cheesbrough, 2005; Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

2.8 Preparation of Inoculum

Inoculums for each organism were prepared in a test tube of 5 ml of saline water by touching the fresh colonies with a sterile wire loop to obtain a very small portion of the organism and adding it to the 5 ml of saline water. This was stirred for proper mixing and to obtain a low bacterial load.

2.9 Preparation of the Control Antibiotic (Ampiclox) for the Antibacterial Activity

For the control, a known standard antibiotic ampiclox was used just like that of the stock solution.

The standard antibiotic was weighed into different concentrations (50, 100, 200, 250, and 500 mg/ml) using a weighing balance. It was then dissolved in 1 ml of sterile water for injection in sterile universal containers that have been properly labelled to obtain stock cultures of it.

2.10 Antibacterial Assay

The antibacterial assay was performed using the agar-well diffusion method as described by Okoli and Iroegbu (2004) to determine the growth inhibition of the test organisms by the maggot extracts. 25 ml each of the prepared Muller Hinton Agar was poured into sterile Petri dishes that were already properly labelled for easy identification and left to solidify. Using sterile pipettes, the agar was aseptically inoculated uniformly by flooding with 1 ml suspension of the three test organisms which had been prepared using a loop full of the inoculum in saline water. The plates were then rocked carefully for the inoculum to spread around the agar and allowed to dry.

Different agar wells were then made on the plates with the aid of a sterile cork borer (6 mm in diameter). Four wells were made on the agar, sufficiently spaced away from the edge of the plate and 25 mm from well to well to prevent overlapping of zones and labelled properly according to the three different crude extract concentrations at the bottom of the Petri dish. The same was done for the standard control plates for easy identification. The stock solutions of the crude extracts of the aqueous, saline water, and phosphate buffer saline were introduced (2-3 drops) into each agar well using a sterile Pasteur pipette, according to the labels including that of the standard antibiotics' plates.

The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which the sensitivity of the test organisms to aqueous, saline water, and PBS extracts of maggots were determined by measuring the zone of inhibition. The measurement of the zone of inhibition was carried out using a transparent meter rule and read to the nearest millimetres. The diameter of the clear zone was taken as an index of the degree of sensitivity.

2.11 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The MIC values of the extracts were determined using the dilution method of the extracts. Various concentrations (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) of the maggot extracts were prepared. 36 test tubes were

set up; 2 ml of nutrient broth was pipetted into each sterile test tube that was already labelled properly. Control tubes were also set up: Tube A (test tubes containing extracts and broth), Tube B (test tube containing broth and each inoculum), and Tube C (test tube containing broth only). Using sterile Pasteur pipettes, 0.2 ml suspension of the test organisms was introduced into the test tubes according to their labels. Also, 2-3 drops of the different stock solutions were introduced using sterile Pasteur pipettes into the test tubes containing both broth and inoculum. The preparation was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which the test tubes were observed for turbidity or clearness. The least concentration where no turbidity was observed was noted as the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) value.

2.12 Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The least concentration of maggot extracts that has an antibacterial effect on the organism is considered as the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). This was determined from the broth dilution resulting from MIC tubes by subculturing to the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates by using a sterile inoculating loop to streak the plate as described by Vollekova et al. [12pt]article graphicx array amsmath

RESULTS

Figure 1: Bar chart representing the efficacy of different concentrations in mg/ml (aqueous) against tested organisms compared to each other.

3 Discussion

A total yield of 30% soluble excretion/secretion was obtained for the aqueous, saline water, and phosphate buffer saline (PBS) extracts, with an original weight of 0.4 g/g of the whole maggot of *Lucilia sericata* and *Musca domestica*. The physical characteristics are indicated in Table 1. Tables ?? to ?? show the results

Figure 2: Stark line with markers chart representing the rate of efficacy of extract (aqueous) against the tested organisms.

of the antibacterial pattern of the extracts against the test organisms.

The results obtained from this study demonstrated a dose-dependent activity of *L. sericata* and *M. domestica* maggot or larva extracts (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) at tested doses (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) on the test organisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*). Maggot excretion/secretions located in their mid-gut contained protein or antibacterial peptide, as noted by Ai et al. (2008, 2012), Hon et al. (2007), and Cao et al. (2011), who extracted chitosan, HF-1 (a novel antibacterial peptide), and Lectin, respectively.

The bar chart, stacked line with markers chart, and pie chart illustrate the efficacy of the different concentrations in mg/ml (0.9, 1.8, 2.7, and 3.6 mg/ml) compared to each other, the efficacy of extracts (aqueous, saline water, and PBS) against the tested organisms, and the growth level of tested organisms (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*) compared to each other, respectively.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* was 1.8 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the saline water maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* was 3.6 mg/ml, while for *S. aureus* it was 1.8 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MIC of the PBS maggot extract against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* was 3.6 mg/ml, with no MIC against *E. coli*, as shown in Table ??.

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the aqueous maggot extract against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* was 3.6 mg/ml, while for *S. aureus* it was 2.7 mg/ml, as shown in Table ???. The MBC of the saline water maggot extract against *S. aureus* was 3.6

Table 1: Physical characteristics of the Maggot Extract

Maggot parts	Solvent	Weight of maggot (g/g)	% Yield	Colour	Odour
Texture					
Whole maggot	Aqueous	0.4	30	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily	Saline water	0.4	30	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily	PBS	0.4	10	Yellow	Unpleasant
Oily					

Table 2: Zone Diameter of inhibition (mm) of the aqueous extract on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15 ± 0.0	19 ± 0.0	22 ± 0.0	10 ± 0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	14 ± 0.0	15 ± 0.0	17 ± 0.0	11 ± 0.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20 ± 0.0	22 ± 0.0	24 ± 0.0	26 ± 0.0

The table shows the zone diameter of inhibition for test organisms at different concentrations of the aqueous extract.

mg/ml, with no MBC for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, as shown in Table ???. There was no MBC for the PBS maggot extract against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*, as shown in Table ???.

The largest zone of inhibition was obtained with the aqueous extract against *S. aureus*, and the lowest was obtained with the PBS extract against *E. coli*. The highest MIC was observed with the aqueous extract on *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* (1.8 mg/ml), while the lowest MIC was found with the PBS extract on *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*, with no MIC on *E. coli* using PBS. The highest MBC was observed with the aqueous extract on *S. aureus* (2.7 mg/ml), and the lowest MBC was obtained with the saline water extract on *S. aureus* (3.6 mg/ml), but no MBC was obtained from PBS. It is evident from the results of this study that *S. aureus* was more susceptible to the maggot extract compared to *E. coli*, which showed the highest resistance, followed by *P. aeruginosa*. These findings agree with several literature reports (Meylaers et al., 2004; Liang et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2006; Jin et al., 2006; Cancado et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2007; Hou et al., 2007; Ai et al., 2008, 2012; Ren et al., 2009; Cao et al., 2011; Yoon et al., 2008; Jang et al., 2007; Suchi et al., 2010), where maggot extract was found to possess significant antimicrobial activities against

several pathogens, especially *S. aureus*. In general, the low activity of the PBS extract on tested organisms might be due to the actions of different components that might have denatured the protein constituents of the maggot extract. This can be observed in the aqueous extract, which has the highest activity on tested organisms since it contains only two molecules of hydrogen and one molecule of oxygen.

4 Recommendation

It is recommended that while extracting excretions/secretions from maggots, a neutral solvent or sterile water should be used to obtain the extract in its natural form. The use of maggot extract is not yet prevalent in Nigeria; this can be improved or encouraged by health workers or the Ministry of Health as it serves as a good and cost-effective alternative to antibiotics.

5 Conclusion

From the study, it can be concluded that the aqueous extract is more efficient than extracts obtained from other solvents and should be preferred for obtaining maggot extract. These studies provide a scientific basis for the clinical or traditional use of maggot extract or whole maggot for therapy, especially for

Table 3: Zone diameter of inhibition (mm) of the control Antibiotic on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)				
	50	100	200	250	500
<i>E. coli</i>	26	31	32	36	38
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35	36
<i>S. aureus</i>	29	30	31	33	34

Table 4: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of aqueous extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	+MIC	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	+MIC	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	+MIC	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: + = clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

infections caused by *S. aureus*, which is sensitive to maggot extract.

6 Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

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Table 5: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of saline water extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	+MIC
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+MIC
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	+MIC	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: + = clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

Table 6: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of PBS extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	-	+MIC
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	-	-	+MIC

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to inhibit the growth of the organism.

Key: + = clear (no growth), - = turbid (growth)

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Table 7: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of aqueous extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	-MBC
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	-MBC
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

Table 8: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of saline water extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	+	-MBC

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

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Table 9: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of PBS extracts on test organisms

Microorganisms	Concentration (mg/ml)			
	0.9	1.8	2.7	3.6
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	+	+

This is the lowest concentration of the extract required to kill the organism completely.

Key: + = bacterial growth, - = no bacterial growth

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Sodium Selenite Ameliorates the Effects of Sodium Arsenite on Some Biomolecules and Enzymes of Energy Metabolism in the Testes of Albino Rats

Babayemi, D. O.¹, Akinhanmi, T. F.², Onunkwor, B. O.¹, Ozeomena, H. O.³, Adeleke, M. A.¹, Akanni, O. I.¹, Keyede, O. O.¹, Michael, M. O.¹, Idhove, F. E.¹, Mukaila, S. A.¹, & Ademuyiwa, O.¹

¹Department of Biochemistry, College of Biosciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, College of Physical Sciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemical Sciences, College of Natural Sciences, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: babayemido@funaab.edu.ng; +2348036869692

Abstract: Heavy metal exposure is becoming more common in our contemporary society as a result of its widespread availability and use. Arsenic is a well-known example of heavy metal that can harm live creatures' reproductive system and biochemical pathways. Twenty-four male Albino rats were randomly divided into four groups (n = 6) and exposed to sodium arsenite (SA) and sodium selenite (SS) for 5 weeks to investigate the ameliorative role of sodium selenite on sodium arsenite-induced testicular toxicity on some biomolecules and enzymes of energy metabolism. Group I (control) received just distilled water, whereas groups II and III were given 40 ppm SA in drinking water *ad libitum*; additionally, group III received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally, while group IV received 0.25 mg/kg bwt SS orally only. Significant increases (p < 0.05) in xanthine oxidase, aldolase, lactate dehydrogenase and aspartate aminotransferase activities, and nitric oxide and hydrogen sulphide levels were observed in the SA-exposed group (group II), while hexokinase and -ketoglutarate dehydrogenase activities decreased significantly. Sodium selenite treatment ameliorated the apparent effects of SA exposure, as seen in groups III and IV. This study supports the use of SS as a safe therapy for SA-induced testicular toxicity.

Key Words: heavy metal exposure, selenium, reproductive organs, biomolecules, energy metabolism

1 INTRODUCTION

Heavy metal exposure is becoming more common in our contemporary society as a result of its widespread availability and use. Arsenic is a well-known example of heavy metal that can harm live creatures' reproductive system and biochemical pathways. Arsenic exists in both inorganic and organic forms (Matschullat, 2000) and with varying oxidation numbers in nature (Afolabi *et al.*, 2015). The inorganic forms are predominantly present in water, food, soil and air. There are reports of arsenic contamination of water bodies in both urban and rural settings around the world (Ahoule *et al.*, 2015). Acute and chronic exposures to inorganic arsenic compounds result in multi-organ damages and perturbations in biological pathways (Gwaltney-

Brant, 2013).

Selenium is an essential micro-element that affects numerous physiological activities in both animals and plants. In trace amount, it is a good antioxidant with anticancer and anti-mutagenic properties; and improves reproductive system and developmental activities (Hariharan & Dharmaraj, 2020; Mojapelo & Lehloenya, 2019). Selenium exists in two forms: organic and inorganic. One of the most common inorganic forms is sodium selenite (SS), used for its dietary potential as a food supplement (Arshad *et al.*, 2021). Selenium has been reported to alter the toxic potential of heavy metals by interacting with them at their primary sites of action, and it can alter the way the body responds to noxious substances by altering their metabolism and transport (Rahman *et al.*, 2019).

In order to find a safer treatment for arsenic-

induced testicular toxicity, SS was employed due to its antioxidant and chemo-protective properties. This current study aims to investigate the ameliorative roles of SS on sodium arsenite-induced testicular damage in male Albino rats.

2 Biochemical Assays

2.1 Estimation of Testicular Hydrogen Sulphide and Nitric Oxide Levels

Hydrogen sulphide was assayed according to the protocol of Zhu et al. (2007), while nitric oxide levels were assayed according to the protocol of Tsikas (2005).

2.2 Determination of Testicular Xanthine Oxidase Activity

The assay for xanthine oxidase activity followed the protocol of Bergmeyer et al. (1974).

2.3 Determination of Testicular Aldolase Activity

The assay for aldolase activity followed the protocol of Jagannathan et al. (1956).

2.4 Determination of Testicular Lactate Dehydrogenase Activity

The assay for lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity followed the protocol of Borgmann et al. (1974).

2.5 Determination of Testicular Aspartate Amino Transferase Activity

Aspartate amino transferase activity was assayed according to the protocol of Reitman and Frankel (1957).

2.6 Determination of Testicular Glutamate Dehydrogenase Activity

Testicular glutamate dehydrogenase (GLDH) activity was assayed according to the protocol of Srasketa et al. (2014).

2.7 Protein Determination in the Testes

The protein concentration was determined using the Biuret method. This was used to determine the specific enzyme activity.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

The results are shown as the mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM). To assess group homogeneity, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. If there

was heterogeneity, the Duncan test was used to divide the groups. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 indicated statistical significance. All analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 24.

3 Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the total amount of arsenic intake by each rat in the SA-exposed groups. The weekly average of arsenic intake ranged from 7.37 to 7.94 mg, culminating in 36.85 and 39.74 mg of arsenic ingested by groups III and IV, respectively (Babayemi et al., 2022). One of the major sources of arsenic exposure is through the consumption of contaminated water due to its ubiquitous nature (Matschullat, 2000). The ingested arsenite is absorbed into the circulatory system via the gastrointestinal tract and distributed across organs (including testes), causing imbalances in biomolecule levels and enzyme activities, resulting in metabolic disorders and organ pathologies (Babayemi et al., 2022).

Table 1: Weekly, total, and average arsenic ingested by each rat

Week	Group II (mg)	Group III (mg)
1	9.24	7.38
2	9.67	9.51
3	7.06	5.82
4	6.74	6.78
5	7.00	7.36
Total	39.74	36.85
Arsenic per week per rat	7.94	7.37

Figure 1 shows the relative organ weights of the rats. There were no significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in the relative organ weights of the groups when compared to the control. Groups II, III, and IV were 15%, 4%, and 13% lower than the control group, respectively. The highest decrease was seen in Group II, where arsenic exposure resulted in organ injury due to oxidative damage from the overwhelming presence of free radical species (Babayemi et al., 2022; Souza et al., 2019). This reduction becomes more prominent over time if SA exposure is not checked.

Table 2 depicts the levels of signalling biomolecules (NO and H₂S) and xanthine oxidase (XO) activities in the testes. Compared to the control group, there was a 30% and 32% increase in testicular levels of mitochondrial NO and H₂S in group II, respectively, but these signalling biomolecules were restored to normal levels in groups III and IV. Elevated levels of

Figure 1: Relative organ weights of the rats. Values are means \pm SEM.

these gasotransmitters may result in imbalances and perturbations in the performance of the sperm cells (Dutta et al., 2024). There was a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in XO activity due to arsenic exposure, with a 111% increase in group II, which was reversed to 39% in group III with selenium treatment. XO is a major contributor to reactive oxygen species, causing oxidative damage to cell membranes and enzymes, disrupting their functions (Darbandi et al., 2018). Sodium selenite was able to reduce the oxidative damage by inhibiting XO activity and reducing the oxidative power of reactive oxygen species due to its antioxidant capacity (Pisoschi and Pop, 2015).

The activities of some glycolytic enzymes in the testes are shown in Table 3. Exposure to sodium arsenite resulted in a 48% inhibition of hexokinase activity in group II compared to the control group, but this was reduced to 18% in group III with selenium treatment. The aldolase activity in group II was fifteen times that of group I, while in group III, it was significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced with selenium treatment to the control level. The pattern of LDH activity in the testes was the reverse of that of hexokinase activity. When compared to the control group, LDH activity increased in the arsenic-exposed group (II) by 466%, but this was reduced to 150% and 26% with selenium administration in groups III and IV, respectively. The significant roles of testes in spermatogenesis and hormone synthesis in reproduction require the availability of energy. The

energy metabolic process is a target of arsenic toxicity (Chen et al., 2020). Glycolysis serves the purpose of providing quick ATP and high-energy compounds from glucose breakdown; hexokinase is one of the regulatory enzymes of this pathway. Arsenic species form complexes with hexokinase and glucose due to their structural resemblance to phosphate, inhibiting the phosphorylation of glucose and slowing down glycolysis (Machado-Neves Souza, 2023). During this deprived energy condition, the cells source their energy needs using alternate pathways and enzymes. The activities of aldolase and LDH increase as alternate sources of energy production. Aldolase also participates in the pathways of glucose synthesis and fructose metabolism, and LDH provides less energy through lactate production, a toxic metabolite (Fukushi et al., 2022). These effects were reversed with SS supplementation due to its competitive capacity for active sites of enzymes with arsenic (Zwolak, 2020).

Table 4 shows the activities of some enzymes involved in the Krebs cycle and protein metabolism in the testes. Testicular -KGDH activity (one of the regulatory enzymes of the Krebs cycle) was inhibited by arsenic exposure in group II by 84% compared to the control group, but this was reduced to 30% by SS supplementation in groups III and IV. This agrees with the findings of Machado-Neves (2023), where arsenic-induced toxicity inhibits -KGDH activity, decreasing the amount of reducing equivalents produced for the electron transport chain for ATP production, potentially resulting in energy starvation. Due to its antioxidant capacity, SS was able to reverse oxidative damage to the enzyme (Saikiran et al., 2020). Compared to group I (control), there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in testicular AST activity in group II by 29% and 135% in group III, but a 51% decrease was observed in group IV with SS supplementation. The activity of GLDH in group IV (with SS supplementation only) was reduced by 37% but increased by 41% and 22% in groups II and III, respectively, compared to group I. AST and GLDH enzymes play roles in ammonia and energy homeostasis. Elevated enzyme activity may indicate tissue damage or disease (Giffen et al., 2002). Due to decreased energy metabolism, the tissue activates protein breakdown mechanisms to produce glucose from non-carbohydrate sources. This is the body's attempt to compensate for the energy loss, as

Table 2: Effects of sodium selenite on signalling biomolecule levels and xanthine oxidase activities in the testes of arsenic-exposed rats

Groups	NO levels ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein)	H2S levels ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein)	XO activity (U/mg protein)
I	349.47 \pm 6.73 ^a	1096.55 \pm 59.51 ^a	0.46 \pm 0.18 ^a
II	454.78 \pm 19.14 ^b	1455.74 \pm 33.07 ^b	0.97 \pm 0.09 ^b
III	318.88 \pm 40.85 ^a	1125.94 \pm 130.20 ^a	0.64 \pm 0.10 ^{ab}
IV	285.92 \pm 18.48 ^a	920.00 \pm 65.68 ^a	0.40 \pm 0.11 ^a

All values are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Values with different superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) down the column.

Table 3: Effects of sodium selenite on glycolytic enzyme activities in the testes of arsenic-exposed rats

Groups	Hexokinase (U/mg protein)	Aldolase (U/mg protein)	Lactate dehydrogenase (U/mg protein)
I	51.70 \pm 0.64 ^c	0.98 \pm 0.25 ^a	0.41 \pm 0.02 ^a
II	21.20 \pm 2.00 ^a	14.12 \pm 0.96 ^b	2.32 \pm 0.02 ^d
III	42.60 \pm 1.98 ^b	1.45 \pm 0.22 ^a	1.02 \pm 0.03 ^c
IV	44.44 \pm 2.68 ^b	1.64 \pm 0.23 ^a	0.52 \pm 0.02 ^b

All values are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Values with different superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) down the column.

indicated by an increase in AST and GLDH activity in arsenic-exposed groups. The ameliorative actions of SS on the effects of arsenic-induced testicular toxicity could be based on the formation of inactive complexes of As-Se, Se antioxidant bolstering ability, and fast excretion of methylated As species (Zwolak, 2020).

4 Conclusion

In summary, this research corroborates the use of SS against SA-induced testicular toxicity by ameliorating the effects of SA on activities of XO, hexokinase, aldolase, LDH, -KGDH, AST, and GLDH, and testicular levels of NO and H2S. This research supports the use of SS as a safe remedy for the treatment of SA-induced testicular toxicity.

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Table 4: Effects of sodium selenite on some enzymes of the TCA cycle and protein metabolism in the testes of arsenic-exposed rats

Groups	-KGDH (U/mg protein)	AST (U/mg protein)	GLDH (U/mg protein)
I	70.95 ± 2.71 ^c	1507.44 ± 141.13 ^b	0.36 ± 0.06 ^{ab}
II	11.52 ± 2.17 ^a	1955.01 ± 79.31 ^c	0.51 ± 0.10 ^b
III	49.76 ± 6.02 ^b	3556.45 ± 44.99 ^d	0.44 ± 0.04 ^b
IV	49.00 ± 2.36 ^b	733.94 ± 115.03 ^a	0.23 ± 0.03 ^a

All values are expressed as mean ± SEM. Values with different superscripts indicate significant differences (p<0.05) down the column.

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MEDICINAL VALUE OF AFRICAN PEAR (*Dacryodes edulis*): IMPLICATION FOR AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION ACTIVITIES

Afolabi, S. O.¹

¹Farm and Environment Unit, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: sofolab@gmail.com; +2348032519376

Abstract: Plants generally possess inherent values relevant to human health but crops in various forms have direct beneficial effects as food and medicine. This review work on the medicinal value of African pear (*Dacryodes edulis*) and its extension implication seeks to explore the nutritional and medicinal value of the crop in terms of its proximate analysis from existing literatures, the perception of farmers on its food and medicinal values, and the implications for agricultural extension services. The transfer of technological innovations in agriculture remains the major focus of extension work among the farmers as a tool to transform rural farming methods to innovative agricultural practices with an increase in production level and transformation of life for the farm families as the immediate goal. The emphasis on the medicinal value of crops generally has been downplayed, hence the main objective of this review work. The African pear contains much of Vitamin C, Potassium, Protein, Oils, and other nutrients and Vitamins that have been found very beneficial to human health in terms of its potentials to manage peculiar health conditions like Sickle cell anemia, Protein deficiency, Hypertension, and also a potential antioxidant and immune booster among others. The farmers and indigenous groups in localities where African pear exist believe it possesses laxative properties and therefore helps in digestive problems and its associating ailments and some other health benefits. It is commonly consumed with boiled corn in communities where it is found and its production always coincides with early fresh Maize harvest. The emergence of human diseases in various forms globally necessitates keen interest in crops like African pear with antioxidant, antimicrobial, and immune boosting properties among other qualities of the crop. Conclusively, evidences abound that African pear is beneficial in building body immunity and management of some ailments due to its phytochemical contents. Recommendations include further extensive research and development on African pear with a view to explore its potential for human health management to transform livelihoods and boost internal and foreign trade impact on the nation's economy.

Key Words: Crops, Medicinal, Agriculture, Extension, Health

1 INTRODUCTION

Plants generally possess constituents that make them relevant for human uses in different forms both as food and medicine. "Food is medicine and medicine is food" is a common parlance to express the medicinal value of foods. Specific crops consumed directly have been found useful in the treatment of ailments or sometimes extracts from crops have been found potent in the management of ailments. Fruits and vegetables are generally known to be very important in human diets because of their constituents and their proximate profiles which have been scientifically investigated in the management of chronic or "so termed terminal ailments". Umoh (1998) noted that fruits are generally used for the treatment of ailments when taken in recommended dosage and not as a snack, such that some fruits have been found to

assist in weight loss therapy and convalescing among patients in need of quick recuperation.

However, the crucial role of agricultural extension in enlightenment campaigns and the utilization of agricultural innovation deserves specific focus to emphasize the medicinal value of crops, particularly in view of globally emerging diseases which have put lots of pressure on mankind in terms of the complexity of symptoms, scale of spread, and complexity of management. According to Oladoja (2008), agricultural development studies have proved that education is a crucial variable for achieving economic growth and human progress and agricultural extension has been designed for farmers' self-help to boost livelihood and transform lives.

Agricultural extension as an informal, out-of-school education aims at boosting the farmers' general

livelihood through education to improve farmers' productivity. The whole educational process of extension may fall short of its goal if the farmers' empowerment excludes education on the medicinal benefit of crops produced. The farm gate benefit of a farmer must be the rich diets of the fresh farm produce consumed at the farm gate before the produce gets to the markets after some days.

African pear (*Dacryodes edulis*), called *Ube* among Igbos in South Eastern Nigeria and various names in different parts of West Africa believed to be its origin, is commonly found around dwelling areas within communities in South East and South South Nigeria, where it is regarded as a choice fruit because of its perceived food and medicinal value compared to other parts of Nigeria. It is not commonly found in other parts of the country like the Southwest, Central, and Northern Nigeria. African pear, also regarded as native pear because of its green acid pulp like the Avocado pear (Umoh 1998), has a peculiar oblong shape and pink color of the fruit which turns black when ripe, making it very attractive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

African medicinal plants to a great extent have been investigated to assess the chemical constituents and some of the isolated compounds have been shown to possess interesting biological activity with few found active in controlled clinical evaluation such that edible plants, spices, and fruits are the dominant ingredients in many medicinal remedies (Iwu 2013).

The relevance of most of the African medicinal plants, particularly the crops, as evidenced by use in traditional medicines and several ongoing investigations, is gaining more attention, particularly with the involvement of governmental and non-governmental agencies in investigation and standardization of these health products. The Nigeria Natural Medicine Development Agency (NNMDA), National Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC), Pax Herbal Nigeria among others are relevant in this regard.

Proximate Composition and Medicinal Value of African Pear

Several studies have documented the high value of the African pear constituents in terms of richness in vitamins and phytochemicals which enhance their value in diets and medicinal preparations.

The richness in essential amino acids like Lysine, Phenylalanine, Leucine, and Isoleucine, and phytochemicals that have been isolated like terpenes, flavonoids, oxalates, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins (Ajibesin 2019).

African pear possesses antioxidants and antimicrobial properties with other phytochemicals that can boost body immunity. Its possession of natural folic acid makes it a beneficial fruit to pregnant women. The Vitamin C helps to boost immunity while the Phosphorus and Calcium contents promote strong bones and teeth. Its richness in Carbohydrate, thiamine, and riboflavin was also noted. The healing of wounds, management of skin infection, and dysentery have also been ascribed to African pear (Ibemere 2022).

Iwu (1986) reported that African Pear has been found useful in the treatment of parasitic skin diseases, wounds, and fever by using the stem exudates and leaves. Studies by Nlenecha (2018) documented the capacity of African pear to fight Cancer and protect women against menopausal breast cancer, decrease colon Cancer infection due to the Fiber, Vitamins, Minerals, and essential fatty acids content. Its ability to support strong bone formation, prevention of constipation, and being heart friendly was also noted.

The proximate analysis of African pear constituents as reported by Omogbai and Ojeaburu (2018) showed a Protein content of 2.89 to 4.16%, while the details of other nutrients and minerals are stated in Tables 1 and 2 below. It was also reported that the anti-nutritional content levels are low in comparison to World Health Standard Organization (WHO) standard for foods.

The effect of processing on the toxicity levels revealed that boiling and roasting have significant effects on toxic metals thus reducing the accumulation levels in the edible portion to the standards within the recommended value by World Health Organization and Food and Agriculture Organization (WHO/FAO) joint expert maximum acceptable recommendation (Dan and Udo 2013).

Table 1: Proximate Analysis Value of African Pear

Parameters	Values (%)	
Moisture	44.45 – 50.93	
Lipid	30.55 – 35.60	
Protein	2.89 – 4.16	Source: Omogbai and
Ash	2.65 – 2.76	
Crude Fiber	1.52 – 1.61	
Carbohydrate	9.75 – 12.59	
Ojeaburu (2010)		

Table 2: Proximate Analysis of African Pear (Minerals)

Minerals	Values (mg/100g)	
Phosphorus	695.55 – 698.40	
Potassium	540.81 – 553.15	
Calcium	347.50 – 354.60	
Magnesium	280.15 – 287.65	Source: Omogbai
Sodium	162.50 – 170.00	
Zinc	3.65 – 3.81	
Iron	3.43 – 3.58	
Copper	0.38 – 0.45	
and Ojeaburu (2010)		

RELEVANCE OF EXTENSION PRINCIPLES IN CROPS' MEDICINAL VALUE CHAIN

Extension education, basically, has been a potent tool in executing development projects because target beneficiaries must be sensitized to perceive development projects as self-help tasks meant to transform lives. The knowledge gap, which this review study seeks to bridge, is the value that agricultural extension personnel must place on their message to the farmer on the beneficial values of farm produce without ambiguity but in the simplest form.

Adedoyin and Aderinto (2013) opined that the role of extension education is to empower farmers directly to help themselves to raise their living standards and ultimately affect the general populace. Oakley and Garforth (1997) noted that extension is a dynamic concept because the interpretation is always changing; as a term, it cannot be defined precisely because it is a description of a continually changing process in the rural economy and is guided by principles. Some of the extension principles are relevant to properly mobilize for the utilization of

crops' medicinal value. They stated the following extension principles, a few of which are adapted for this review:

1. **Needs and Interest of Target Beneficiaries:** Felt needs as precursor drives attention, motivates action, and mobilizes for adoption. Peculiar needs of target beneficiaries must be explored to fast-track tapping the advantage of crops' medicinal value.
2. **Operation at People's Level:** Interaction at the farmers' level is key in winning the attention of a farmer for involvement in extension education. The primary level to gain attention in extension of medicinal value of crops is to open up the farmers' attention to the medicinal value of crops on his farm beyond the food or dietary value. Even though rural people, particularly adults, have indigenous knowledge on plants' medicinal value, although such knowledge may be limited, they will be ready to learn if rightly prompted.
3. **Extension Works with People, Not for the People:** The extension work basically lies with the rural people, who already have orientation and knowledge of what to do. They only need guidance, not domination or bossy attitude; their decisions need support to solve their perceived problems for extension goals to be achieved. Extension presents facts, helps people to solve problems, and encourages farmers to take decisions. Confidence is generated when farmers are part of programme decisions.
4. **Extension is Accountable to its Clients:** Extension workers relate to their superiors and the government department and at the same time respond to the needs of their clients who look forward to extension workers to mobilize them for self-help as government representatives around their locality.
5. **Extension as Two-Way Link:** The two-fold linkage of receiving from research stations to reach farmers on the field. In the crops medicinal value chain, bulk research results exist with research organizations on various crops' benefits beyond the dietary value. Extension service through the field workers are the viable links.

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EXTENSION COMMUNICATION IN CROPS' MEDICINAL VALUE CHAIN

Generally, crops are highly valued as the end product in the agricultural production process because of their potential domestic and industrial uses as food, medicine, or other applications. Iwu (2013) noted that with recent developments, management of chronic ailments and metabolic disease conditions have been found feasible through various research studies in Phytomedicine and Bioresources.

The concept of extension communication involves educating people for self-help to transform lives through innovation transmission with the ultimate goal of empowerment and improved living standards as a potent tool for development.

Innovation transmission as a deliberate action is the major theme of agricultural extension, and in this perspective, the medicinal value of crops is the brand of innovation that farmers need to be motivated into. Innovation has been defined as anything new introduced into an economy or social process (OECD 1997). The key elements of communication as emphasized by Oakley and Garforth (1997) include channel, message, source, listening, and shared meanings. These are core issues that underlie any successful communication and are highly relevant to the dissemination of crops' medicinal value information.

Since the adoption of the memorandum on the unified agricultural extension system by the National Council for Agriculture in 1989, which gave rise to the national policy and the subsequent implementation in 1990, the various states were advised to adopt the unified extension system (Adediji, 2013). The unified extension system was introduced to cater to various segments of agriculture as practiced in Nigeria such that smallholder farmers who practice various aspects of agriculture might be covered holistically by the agricultural extension system, thus enhancing the various value chain processes in the agricultural production cycle.

Thrupp (1996) identified the following factors as essential for success in the knowledge or technology dissemination process among farmers:

1. Vested leadership or shared control with the farmers in every aspect of technology dissemination.
2. Participation and empowerment of farmers and

communities.

3. Linkage between groups, institutions, and organizations, both governmental and non-governmental.
4. Innovation learning and effective communication.
5. Policy environment and political influence.

These factors, in relation to knowledge transfer of African pear medicinal value, will help to boost indigenous knowledge documentation and scientific information transfer. Consequently, the various researchers and organizations involved in Bioresources development in linkage with farmers can cross-fertilize ideas to probe into farmers' knowledge on its medicinal value and as well share the scientific information on its proximate value and its health benefits.

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THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The following theories discussed below provide a framework for this review work.

Knowledge Gap Theory

The theory of knowledge gap is based on information or knowledge acquisition generally, emphasizing that people don't acquire information at the same rate. Variables like socio-economic status and rate of learning, among others, influence the degree of knowledge acquisition. According to Asemah (2011), the theory states that the spread of news in a society can lead to an increase in the gap between people of different economic statuses, such that attempts to improve life in a social system may not always work as planned. The heterogeneous nature of economic statuses plays vital roles in individual wants, needs, and responses to knowledge acquisition. The theory views knowledge as a commodity, product, or idea not evenly distributed in society. People with higher economic status and innovative minds tend to have better access to knowledge acquisition than laggards, who are late adopters or non-adopters of innovation. Folarin (1998) noted the impact of media output in a given society: as the media grows, the knowledge gap between the privileged and underprivileged social groups increases. The relevance of the Knowledge Gap theory to crops'

medicinal value chain communication rests on the knowledge gap existing among various categories of farmers on health benefits derivable from crops beyond the food value.

Diffusion and Innovation Theory

The Innovation Diffusion theory emphasizes the information flow over time through a social system until it becomes adopted as a new product or idea observed to have beneficial value. Asemah (2017) noted that the diffusion of innovation as an idea was developed into theory in the United States of America. Agricultural technology advancement took a rapid dimension, and researchers examined the adoption of hybrid seeds, equipment, and crop propagation techniques by farmers. The relevance of Innovation Diffusion theory to crops' medicinal value adoption rests on the current emergence of diseases on a pandemic scale, such as COVID-19, Lassa fever, and HIV/AIDS. The effect of disease emergence on the disruption of the economy and human health are great challenges that mankind has come to face squarely in the twenty-first century. The necessity for alternative and supplementary therapy to manage these health challenges supports the relevance of this theory in the dissemination of crops' medicinal value as an innovation, of which African pear is one. article [utf8]inputenc

METHODOLOGY

This study, as a review work, examined existing investigative studies in literature available in libraries and on the internet concerning the medicinal value of African Pear and the relevant agricultural extension concepts and principles. The professional experience of the researcher as an Agricultural Extension specialist among rural farmers over the years also contributed to knowledge sharing in this review work. article [utf8]inputenc

CONCLUSION

The peculiarity of agricultural extension as a veritable tool to transform the lives of rural farm families and, by extension, the economic development of nations has been well documented. It has become a potent game-changer in human development projects globally. Agricultural extension is an informal, out-of-school adult education that employs various approaches and methodologies to reach rural farmers.

As reviewed in this study, the diffusion and adoption of the health benefits of crops, which can be further packaged to enhance their value, cannot be overemphasized, judging from the volumes of existing investigative work on crops' medicinal value.

Rural farmers, who are primarily smallholders, have been identified as a major source of farm produce supply in Sub-Saharan Africa. The primary benefits of crops' medicinal value to the farm family and the general populace remain largely untapped. Coincidentally, humanity is at the peak of global health challenges due to emerging diseases.

RECOMMENDATION

The promotion of further research and development on the African pear food and medicinal value chain deserves priority attention due to its immense food and health benefits to human development and the global economy. The need for a viable supplement to existing drug therapy for disease management provides a good opportunity for the exploitation of African pear's medicinal value at domestic and industrial scales. Integration of crops' medicinal value as a core subject matter in agricultural extension as a global need deserves implementation to enable the full exploration of natural reserves in African pear. article [utf8]inputenc apacite

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EVALUATION OF THE ANALGESIC EFFECT OF AQUEOUS ROOT EXTRACT OF *Combretum platypterum* (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel ON RODENT

UWAYA, OD* ¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty Of Life Sciences, University Of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Corresponding author: dickson.uwaya@uniben.edu; udickson4christ@yahoo.com; (+234) 705-965-0758

Abstract: Pain management is essential in many clinical cases, and an interdisciplinary approach eases suffering and improves the quality of life of those living with pain. The aim of this study was to test the analgesic effects of an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum*. Three animal models were used, which were the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the hot plate model, and the tail flick model. In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the test and the standard drug reduced the number of abdominal constrictions and also increased the percentage inhibition of writhing in a dose-dependent manner compared to the control. In the Hot Plate and Tail Flick models, test extracts and the standard drugs increased the pain threshold as compared to the control group (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The results of pharmacological tests performed in the present study suggest that the plant extract has significant analgesic activity and confirm its ethno-medical use to treat back pains.

Keywords: Analgesic, *Combretum platypterum*, writhing, Ethno-medical, Plant extract

1 INTRODUCTION

The management of pain is important in many clinical cases, and it is an interdisciplinary approach for easing the suffering and improving the quality of life of those living with pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Erah *et al.*, 2003). Analgesics, or painkillers, are a group of drugs used to achieve analgesia or relief from pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Zeruesenayet *al.*, 2002). These analgesic drugs are useful against pain but exhibit many adverse effects; this led to an interest in the search for safer and more available drugs for relieving pain (Erah *et al.*, 2003). Plants are used as painkillers today (Ahmadiani *et al.*, 2000; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). The populations of developing countries worldwide continue to rely on the use of traditional medicines as their primary source of healthcare (Adesina *et al.*, 2013). Ethnobotanical studies carried out throughout Africa confirm that native plants are the main constituents of traditional African medicines (Sandhu and Heinrich, 2005; Gupta *et al.*, 2005; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). Using plants as a source of relief from illness is as old as mankind, with record practices dating back at least 4000 years (Christophersen *et*

al., 1991). *Combretum platypterum* belongs to the family Combretaceae. In Nigeria, it is commonly called “mmanyanza” (palm wine of the sunbird) or “achichanza” by the Igbos; the Yorubas refer to it as “OganOgandudu” or “Oganibule” (Bredenkamp, 2000). While the Binis refer to it as ‘ove’ “oven” or “ovben-ome” (Aigbokhan, 2014), It is used in ethnomedicine to treat lower backaches, fever, eye problems, malaria, swellings, lumps, conjunctivitis, coughs, sexually transmitted diseases, helminthiasis, and diarrhea. They also use it as a tonic, febrifuge, and to stop postpartum bleeding (Bongerset *et al.*, 2005; Liben, 1983; Watt and Breyer-Brandwijk, 1962). Although this herb has been traditionally used, there have been no scientific investigations into its usage for pain therapy. Therefore, the aim of this study was to examine the pain-relieving effect of the water-based root extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Materials and Methods

Plant Collection and Extraction

Fresh leaves of *Combretum platypterum* were collected from Idumiru in Igbanke West in Orhionmwon, Edo

State. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. H. Akinnibosun of the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City. The plant was deposited in the University of Benin Herbarium with voucher number UBHc063. The fresh leaves were air-dried for 14 days in the Department of Pharmacognosy at the University of Benin, Benin City. Afterwards, they were ground to powder form with an electric mill. The powdered plant material was extracted with water over 24 hours using the maceration method and then filtered over a clean, fine white cloth. The filtrate was concentrated to dryness over a water bath, and the dried extract was stored in a glass container in a refrigerator until use.

Experimental Animals

Male and female Swiss albino mice (25–35 g) and adult albino rats of both sexes weighing 100–250 g were purchased from a commercial farm in Benin City and housed in the animal facility of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Benin City. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for 2 weeks with a 12-hour light/dark cycle at room temperature. They were fed with standard rodent pellets and water *ad libitum*. The animals were handled according to standard protocols for the use of laboratory animals (National Institute of Health USA: Public Health Service Policy on Humane Care and Use of Laboratory Animals, 2002).

Experimental Protocol

Acetic Acid-Induced Writhing in Mice

The method described by Akor et al. (2015) was used. Twenty mice were randomly divided into five groups of four animals per group. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg orally); Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance, which was an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* orally at doses of 50 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, acetic acid (0.6%) was injected intraperitoneally into each mouse. The number of writhings, which comprised constriction of the abdominal muscle together with stretching of the hind limbs, was counted for 30 minutes after the acetic acid injection. Inhibition of pain was expressed as a percentage of protection

using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of pain} = \frac{\text{mean writhing (control)} - \text{mean writhing (treated)}}{\text{mean writhing (control)}} \times 100$$

where mean writhing (control) is the mean writhing of the distilled water-treated animals, and mean writhing (treated) is the mean writhing of the animal given the plant extract, standard drug, or each dose of *C. platypterum* leaf extract.

Hot Plate Test

The method described by Badilla et al. (2003) was used. The hot plate temperature was maintained at 55 ± 1 °C. A cut-off time of 60 seconds was adopted to prevent tissue damage. Licking, biting of the hind paw, or jumping were taken as signs of pain perception. Adult Swiss mice (25–35 g) of both sexes, screened for a suitable reaction time 24 hours before the experiment, were used. The animals were randomly divided into five groups of four mice each. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance of aqueous root extract at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, each animal was placed on the hot plate, and the index of the response latency (time between placement and licking, biting the hind paws, or jumping) was recorded. Response latencies were taken at 30, 60, and 90 minutes after treatment (Debasis et al., 2011). The reaction time was recorded, and the percentage increase in the pain threshold was calculated.

$$\% \text{ Increase in pain threshold} = \frac{T_a - T_b}{T_b} \times 100$$

where T_a = mean reaction time at each time after treatment with either pentazocine or each dose of the *C. platypterum* leaf extract, and T_b = mean baseline latency.

Tail-Flick Test

The experiment was carried out by measuring tail withdrawal time from a heat source (Ezeja et al., 2011). Twenty rats were randomly divided into five groups of four rats per group and fasted for 12 hours. Rats were placed in the tail flick apparatus, and their pain threshold was determined. The rat in group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (2 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were

Table 1: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* on acetic acid induced writhing test in mice

Group	Number of Writhing	% Pain Inhibition
Control	96.40 ± 11.00	-
50 mg/kg	85.60 ± 27.14	11.44
100 mg/kg	61.84 ± 7.99	35.85
200 mg/kg	31.80 ± 3.31*	67.01
Aspirin (100 mg/kg)	19.20 ± 40**	80.08

The extract at 200 mg/kg and standard (aspirin, 100 mg/kg) reduced the number writhing in mice compared to control (** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

administered the test substance, an aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum*, at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). After 30 minutes, each rat was placed on the tail flick apparatus containing heat, and the time taken for the rat to flick the tail, known as pain reaction time (PRT), was recorded for all the rats.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as the mean ± SEM. The data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism V.6.01, where $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

An aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* (200 mg/kg) reduced abdominal constrictions in mice. The reduction was significant (* $P < 0.05$) when compared with the control. The standard drug aspirin (100 mg/kg) produced a better analgesic effect than the extract (Table 1). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain (Table 2). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain, but the standard drug produced a better analgesic effect than the extract at 60 and 90 minutes (Figure 1).

Discussion

Certain noxious stimuli are painful, and reflex movements or behaviors resulting from such stimuli show a pain threshold. The stimulus may be thermal, electrical, mechanical, or chemical, according to Ezeja et al. (2011), and this informed the three analgesic models: acetic acid-induced writhing, tail flick, and hot plate methods used in this study.

In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* dose-dependently reduced the number of abdominal constrictions. The effect was significant at 200 mg/kg when compared to the control. The percentage inhibition of writhing was also dose-dependent, increasing from 0 in the control group (distilled water) to 67% in the group that received 200 mg/kg of the extract. The standard drug, aspirin (100 mg/kg), however, produced a better analgesic effect than the extract. Acetic acid acts by inducing the release of prostaglandins and lipoxygenase products into the peritoneum (Yongna et al., 2005), which activate the pain-sensing neurons that are responsive to the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications, making the test suitable for evaluating mild pain-relieving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory substances (Ngulde, 2010).

The inhibition of writhing in mice by the aqueous extract suggested a peripheral mechanism of action via inhibition of prostaglandins, serotonin, histamine, bradykinins, and substance P endings (Eekankopf et al., 1988; Ngulde, 2010). Pain sensation in the acetic acid-induced writhing method elicits a localized inflammatory response resulting from the release of free arachidonic acid from tissue phospholipids (Ahmed et al., 2006) via cyclooxygenase (COX) and prostaglandin biosynthesis (Adiukwu et al., 2013).

Table 2: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterus* on latency time in hot plate test in mice

Group	30 mins	60 mins	90 mins
Control	5.20 ± 0.59	5.78 ± 0.41	5.78 ± 0.20
50 mg/kg	6.86 ± 0.85	11.14 ± 9.91****	7.56 ± 0.58*
100 mg/kg	8.60 ± 0.55**	9.82 ± 0.63**	7.56 ± 0.32*
200 mg/kg	7.54 ± 0.20*	9.68 ± 0.44**	7.54 ± 0.14*
Pen (3 mg/kg)	7.54 ± 0.15*	11.26 ± 0.72****	8.78 ± 0.57***

The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased latency time of pain compared to control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

Figure 1: Effect of aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterus* on tail flick induced pain in rats. The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased latency time of pain compared to control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Pen: pentozacine, values are represented as Mean ± SEM, n = 4 per group.

Acetic acid-induced writhing has been associated with an increased level of PGE2 and PGF2 in peritoneal fluids and lipoxygenase products (Dhara et al., 2000). An increase in prostaglandin levels within the peritoneal cavity then enhances inflammatory pain by increasing capillary permeability (Zakaria et al., 2008). The acetic acid-induced writhing method has been found effective for testing peripherally active

analgesics. The significant pain reduction of the plant extract might be due to analgesic principles acting within the prostaglandin pathways (Ukwuani and Hassan, 2014). The abdominal writhing induced by acetic acid has been reported to be less selective (Trongsakulet et al., 2003) and has been proposed to act indirectly by releasing endogenous mediators that stimulate neurons that are sensitive to other drugs

such as narcotics and centrally acting agents (Toma et al., 2003).

In order to confirm the anti-nociceptive effect of the extract, the tail flick and the hot plate tests were carried out. In both tests, the extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased the latency time of pain compared to the control. The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain. Thermal nociceptive tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors, and non-thermal tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors (Akor et al., 2015). The tail-flick test is considered selective for the drugs acting centrally. It measures the complex response to a non-inflammatory, acute nociceptive input and is one model used for studying central nociceptive activity (Sabina et al., 2009). The effects of the extract on the tail flick and hot plate methods confirmed its analgesic action. This further suggests a central mechanism of action for the extract. Pentazocine is known to elevate the pain threshold of albino rats or mice towards heat and pressure (Hollander et al., 2009). In the hot plate and tail flick experiments, pentazocine's effect as an analgesic had a higher effect than that of the extract. The analgesic superiority is expected since pentazocine is a narcotic analgesic used to ease deep-seated pain (Akor et al., 2015). Since there were significant activities recorded in both methods (tail flick and hot plate), the extract could be said to act both peripherally and centrally in producing analgesia. Noxious stimuli cause the release of chemicals such as prostaglandins and decarboxylated amines (histamine and serotonin), thereby inducing pain locally (Nunez et al., 1997; Yongna et al., 2005). Peripherally acting analgesics, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), act by inhibiting the release of prostaglandins (Wagner et al., 2004; Ngulde, 2010). Centrally acting analgesics such as pentazocine act through their receptors in the central nervous system (CNS) by increasing the threshold response to pain stimuli (Hollander et al., 2009). Opioid analgesics inhibit both peripheral and central mechanisms of pain, while NSAIDs inhibit only peripheral pain (Akoret al., 2015).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* was found to have analgesic effects. In accordance with the present study, it was observed that *Combretum platypterum* analgesic effects may be

centrally and peripherally pain-acting. Further studies should be initiated to study the exact mechanism of action and phytochemical investigations to find out which active constituent is responsible for its analgesic activity.

Acknowledgments

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Conflict of Interest

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EVALUATION OF THE ANALGESIC EFFECT OF AQUEOUS ROOT EXTRACT OF *Combretum platypterum* (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel ON RODENT

UWAYA, OD* ¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty Of Life Sciences, University Of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Corresponding author: dickson.uwaya@uniben.edu; udickson4christ@yahoo.com; (+234) 705-965-0758

Abstract: Pain management is essential in many clinical cases, and an interdisciplinary approach eases suffering and improves the quality of life of those living with pain. The aim of this study was to test the analgesic effects of an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum*. Three animal models were used, which were the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the hot plate model, and the tail flick model. In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the test and the standard drug reduced the number of abdominal constrictions and also increased the percentage inhibition of writhing in a dose-dependent manner compared to the control. In the Hot Plate and Tail Flick models, test extracts and the standard drugs increased the pain threshold as compared to the control group (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The results of pharmacological tests performed in the present study suggest that the plant extract has significant analgesic activity and confirm its ethno-medical use to treat back pains.

Keywords: Analgesic, *Combretum platypterum*, writhing, Ethno-medical, Plant extract

1 INTRODUCTION

The management of pain is important in many clinical cases, and it is an interdisciplinary approach for easing the suffering and improving the quality of life of those living with pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Erah *et al.*, 2003). Analgesics, or painkillers, are a group of drugs used to achieve analgesia or relief from pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Zeruesenayet *al.*, 2002). These analgesic drugs are useful against pain but exhibit many adverse effects; this led to an interest in the search for safer and more available drugs for relieving pain (Erah *et al.*, 2003). Plants are used as painkillers today (Ahmadiani *et al.*, 2000; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). The populations of developing countries worldwide continue to rely on the use of traditional medicines as their primary source of healthcare (Adesina *et al.*, 2013). Ethnobotanical studies carried out throughout Africa confirm that native plants are the main constituents of traditional African medicines (Sandhu and Heinrich, 2005; Gupta *et al.*, 2005; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). Using plants as a source of relief from illness is as old as mankind, with record practices dating back at least 4000 years (Christophersen *et*

al., 1991). *Combretum platypterum* belongs to the family Combretaceae. In Nigeria, it is commonly called “mmanyanza” (palm wine of the sunbird) or “achichanza” by the Igbos; the Yorubas refer to it as “OganOgandudu” or “Oganibule” (Bredenkamp, 2000). While the Binis refer to it as ‘ove” “oven” or “ovben-ome” (Aigbokhan, 2014), It is used in ethnomedicine to treat lower backaches, fever, eye problems, malaria, swellings, lumps, conjunctivitis, coughs, sexually transmitted diseases, helminthiasis, and diarrhea. They also use it as a tonic, febrifuge, and to stop postpartum bleeding (Bongerset *et al.*, 2005; Liben, 1983; Watt and Breyer-Brandwijk, 1962). Although this herb has been traditionally used, there have been no scientific investigations into its usage for pain therapy. Therefore, the aim of this study was to examine the pain-relieving effect of the water-based root extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Materials and Methods

Plant Collection and Extraction

Fresh leaves of *Combretum platypterum* were collected from Idumiru in Igbanke West in Orhionmwon, Edo

State. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. H. Akinnibosun of the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City. The plant was deposited in the University of Benin Herbarium with voucher number UBHc063. The fresh leaves were air-dried for 14 days in the Department of Pharmacognosy at the University of Benin, Benin City. Afterwards, they were ground to powder form with an electric mill. The powdered plant material was extracted with water over 24 hours using the maceration method and then filtered over a clean, fine white cloth. The filtrate was concentrated to dryness over a water bath, and the dried extract was stored in a glass container in a refrigerator until use.

Experimental Animals

Male and female Swiss albino mice (25–35 g) and adult albino rats of both sexes weighing 100–250 g were purchased from a commercial farm in Benin City and housed in the animal facility of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Benin City. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for 2 weeks with a 12-hour light/dark cycle at room temperature. They were fed with standard rodent pellets and water *ad libitum*. The animals were handled according to standard protocols for the use of laboratory animals (National Institute of Health USA: Public Health Service Policy on Humane Care and Use of Laboratory Animals, 2002).

Experimental Protocol

Acetic Acid-Induced Writhing in Mice

The method described by Akor et al. (2015) was used. Twenty mice were randomly divided into five groups of four animals per group. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg orally); Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance, which was an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* orally at doses of 50 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, acetic acid (0.6%) was injected intraperitoneally into each mouse. The number of writhings, which comprised constriction of the abdominal muscle together with stretching of the hind limbs, was counted for 30 minutes after the acetic acid injection. Inhibition of pain was expressed as a percentage of protection

using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of pain} = \frac{\text{mean writhing (control)} - \text{mean writhing (treated)}}{\text{mean writhing (control)}} \times 100$$

where mean writhing (control) is the mean writhing of the distilled water-treated animals, and mean writhing (treated) is the mean writhing of the animal given the plant extract, standard drug, or each dose of *C. platypterum* leaf extract.

Hot Plate Test

The method described by Badilla et al. (2003) was used. The hot plate temperature was maintained at 55 ± 1 °C. A cut-off time of 60 seconds was adopted to prevent tissue damage. Licking, biting of the hind paw, or jumping were taken as signs of pain perception. Adult Swiss mice (25–35 g) of both sexes, screened for a suitable reaction time 24 hours before the experiment, were used. The animals were randomly divided into five groups of four mice each. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance of aqueous root extract at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, each animal was placed on the hot plate, and the index of the response latency (time between placement and licking, biting the hind paws, or jumping) was recorded. Response latencies were taken at 30, 60, and 90 minutes after treatment (Debasis et al., 2011). The reaction time was recorded, and the percentage increase in the pain threshold was calculated.

$$\% \text{ Increase in pain threshold} = \frac{T_a - T_b}{T_b} \times 100$$

where T_a = mean reaction time at each time after treatment with either pentazocine or each dose of the *C. platypterum* leaf extract, and T_b = mean baseline latency.

Tail-Flick Test

The experiment was carried out by measuring tail withdrawal time from a heat source (Ezeja et al., 2011). Twenty rats were randomly divided into five groups of four rats per group and fasted for 12 hours. Rats were placed in the tail flick apparatus, and their pain threshold was determined. The rat in group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (2 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were

Table 1: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* on acetic acid induced writhing test in mice

Group	Number of Writhing	% Pain Inhibition
Control	96.40 ± 11.00	-
50 mg/kg	85.60 ± 27.14	11.44
100 mg/kg	61.84 ± 7.99	35.85
200 mg/kg	31.80 ± 3.31*	67.01
Aspirin (100 mg/kg)	19.20 ± 40**	80.08

The extract at 200 mg/kg and standard (aspirin, 100 mg/kg) reduced the number writhing in mice compared to control (** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

administered the test substance, an aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum*, at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). After 30 minutes, each rat was placed on the tail flick apparatus containing heat, and the time taken for the rat to flick the tail, known as pain reaction time (PRT), was recorded for all the rats.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as the mean ± SEM. The data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism V.6.01, where $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

An aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* (200 mg/kg) reduced abdominal constrictions in mice. The reduction was significant (* $P < 0.05$) when compared with the control. The standard drug aspirin (100 mg/kg) produced a better analgesic effect than the extract (Table 1). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain (Table 2). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain, but the standard drug produced a better analgesic effect than the extract at 60 and 90 minutes (Figure 1).

Discussion

Certain noxious stimuli are painful, and reflex movements or behaviors resulting from such stimuli show a pain threshold. The stimulus may be thermal, electrical, mechanical, or chemical, according to Ezeja et al. (2011), and this informed the three analgesic models: acetic acid-induced writhing, tail flick, and hot plate methods used in this study.

In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* dose-dependently reduced the number of abdominal constrictions. The effect was significant at 200 mg/kg when compared to the control. The percentage inhibition of writhing was also dose-dependent, increasing from 0 in the control group (distilled water) to 67% in the group that received 200 mg/kg of the extract. The standard drug, aspirin (100 mg/kg), however, produced a better analgesic effect than the extract. Acetic acid acts by inducing the release of prostaglandins and lipoxygenase products into the peritoneum (Yongna et al., 2005), which activate the pain-sensing neurons that are responsive to the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications, making the test suitable for evaluating mild pain-relieving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory substances (Ngulde, 2010).

The inhibition of writhing in mice by the aqueous extract suggested a peripheral mechanism of action via inhibition of prostaglandins, serotonin, histamine, bradykinins, and substance P endings (Eekankopf et al., 1988; Ngulde, 2010). Pain sensation in the acetic acid-induced writhing method elicits a localized inflammatory response resulting from the release of free arachidonic acid from tissue phospholipids (Ahmed et al., 2006) via cyclooxygenase (COX) and prostaglandin biosynthesis (Adiukwu et al., 2013).

Table 2: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterus* on latency time in hot plate test in mice

Group	30 mins	60 mins	90 mins
Control	5.20 ± 0.59	5.78 ± 0.41	5.78 ± 0.20
50 mg/kg	6.86 ± 0.85	11.14 ± 9.91****	7.56 ± 0.58*
100 mg/kg	8.60 ± 0.55**	9.82 ± 0.63**	7.56 ± 0.32*
200 mg/kg	7.54 ± 0.20*	9.68 ± 0.44**	7.54 ± 0.14*
Pen (3 mg/kg)	7.54 ± 0.15*	11.26 ± 0.72****	8.78 ± 0.57***

The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased latency time of pain compared to control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

Figure 1: Effect of aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterus* on tail flick induced pain in rats. The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased latency time of pain compared to control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Pen: pentozacine, values are represented as Mean ± SEM, n = 4 per group.

Acetic acid-induced writhing has been associated with an increased level of PGE2 and PGF2 in peritoneal fluids and lipoxygenase products (Dhara et al., 2000). An increase in prostaglandin levels within the peritoneal cavity then enhances inflammatory pain by increasing capillary permeability (Zakaria et al., 2008). The acetic acid-induced writhing method has been found effective for testing peripherally active

analgesics. The significant pain reduction of the plant extract might be due to analgesic principles acting within the prostaglandin pathways (Ukwuani and Hassan, 2014). The abdominal writhing induced by acetic acid has been reported to be less selective (Trongsakulet et al., 2003) and has been proposed to act indirectly by releasing endogenous mediators that stimulate neurons that are sensitive to other drugs

such as narcotics and centrally acting agents (Toma et al., 2003).

In order to confirm the anti-nociceptive effect of the extract, the tail flick and the hot plate tests were carried out. In both tests, the extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased the latency time of pain compared to the control. The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain. Thermal nociceptive tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors, and non-thermal tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors (Akor et al., 2015). The tail-flick test is considered selective for the drugs acting centrally. It measures the complex response to a non-inflammatory, acute nociceptive input and is one model used for studying central nociceptive activity (Sabina et al., 2009). The effects of the extract on the tail flick and hot plate methods confirmed its analgesic action. This further suggests a central mechanism of action for the extract. Pentazocine is known to elevate the pain threshold of albino rats or mice towards heat and pressure (Hollander et al., 2009). In the hot plate and tail flick experiments, pentazocine's effect as an analgesic had a higher effect than that of the extract. The analgesic superiority is expected since pentazocine is a narcotic analgesic used to ease deep-seated pain (Akor et al., 2015). Since there were significant activities recorded in both methods (tail flick and hot plate), the extract could be said to act both peripherally and centrally in producing analgesia. Noxious stimuli cause the release of chemicals such as prostaglandins and decarboxylated amines (histamine and serotonin), thereby inducing pain locally (Nunez et al., 1997; Yongna et al., 2005). Peripherally acting analgesics, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), act by inhibiting the release of prostaglandins (Wagner et al., 2004; Ngulde, 2010). Centrally acting analgesics such as pentazocine act through their receptors in the central nervous system (CNS) by increasing the threshold response to pain stimuli (Hollander et al., 2009). Opioid analgesics inhibit both peripheral and central mechanisms of pain, while NSAIDs inhibit only peripheral pain (Akoret al., 2015).

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EVALUATION OF THE ANALGESIC EFFECT OF AQUEOUS ROOT EXTRACT OF *Combretum platypterum* (Welw) Hutch and Dalziel ON RODENT

UWAYA, OD* ¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty Of Life Sciences, University Of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

Corresponding author: dickson.uwaya@uniben.edu; udickson4christ@yahoo.com; (+234) 705-965-0758

Abstract: Pain management is essential in many clinical cases, and an interdisciplinary approach eases suffering and improves the quality of life of those living with pain. The aim of this study was to test the analgesic effects of an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum*. Three animal models were used, which were the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the hot plate model, and the tail flick model. In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the test and the standard drug reduced the number of abdominal constrictions and also increased the percentage inhibition of writhing in a dose-dependent manner compared to the control. In the Hot Plate and Tail Flick models, test extracts and the standard drugs increased the pain threshold as compared to the control group (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The results of pharmacological tests performed in the present study suggest that the plant extract has significant analgesic activity and confirm its ethno-medical use to treat back pains.

Keywords: Analgesic, *Combretum platypterum*, writhing, Ethno-medical, Plant extract

1 INTRODUCTION

The management of pain is important in many clinical cases, and it is an interdisciplinary approach for easing the suffering and improving the quality of life of those living with pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Erah *et al.*, 2003). Analgesics, or painkillers, are a group of drugs used to achieve analgesia or relief from pain (Akande and Ologe, 2007; Zeruesenayet *al.*, 2002). These analgesic drugs are useful against pain but exhibit many adverse effects; this led to an interest in the search for safer and more available drugs for relieving pain (Erah *et al.*, 2003). Plants are used as painkillers today (Ahmadiani *et al.*, 2000; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). The populations of developing countries worldwide continue to rely on the use of traditional medicines as their primary source of healthcare (Adesina *et al.*, 2013). Ethnobotanical studies carried out throughout Africa confirm that native plants are the main constituents of traditional African medicines (Sandhu and Heinrich, 2005; Gupta *et al.*, 2005; Ovuru *et al.*, 2023). Using plants as a source of relief from illness is as old as mankind, with record practices dating back at least 4000 years (Christophersen *et*

al., 1991). *Combretum platypterum* belongs to the family Combretaceae. In Nigeria, it is commonly called “mmanyanza” (palm wine of the sunbird) or “achichanza” by the Igbos; the Yorubas refer to it as “OganOgandudu” or “Oganibule” (Bredenkamp, 2000). While the Binis refer to it as ‘ove” “oven” or “ovben-ome” (Aigbokhan, 2014), It is used in ethnomedicine to treat lower backaches, fever, eye problems, malaria, swellings, lumps, conjunctivitis, coughs, sexually transmitted diseases, helminthiasis, and diarrhea. They also use it as a tonic, febrifuge, and to stop postpartum bleeding (Bongerset *et al.*, 2005; Liben, 1983; Watt and Breyer-Brandwijk, 1962). Although this herb has been traditionally used, there have been no scientific investigations into its usage for pain therapy. Therefore, the aim of this study was to examine the pain-relieving effect of the water-based root extract of *Combretum platypterum*.

Materials and Methods

Plant Collection and Extraction

Fresh leaves of *Combretum platypterum* were collected from Idumiru in Igbanke West in Orhionmwon, Edo

State. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. H. Akinnibosun of the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City. The plant was deposited in the University of Benin Herbarium with voucher number UBHc063. The fresh leaves were air-dried for 14 days in the Department of Pharmacognosy at the University of Benin, Benin City. Afterwards, they were ground to powder form with an electric mill. The powdered plant material was extracted with water over 24 hours using the maceration method and then filtered over a clean, fine white cloth. The filtrate was concentrated to dryness over a water bath, and the dried extract was stored in a glass container in a refrigerator until use.

Experimental Animals

Male and female Swiss albino mice (25–35 g) and adult albino rats of both sexes weighing 100–250 g were purchased from a commercial farm in Benin City and housed in the animal facility of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Benin City. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for 2 weeks with a 12-hour light/dark cycle at room temperature. They were fed with standard rodent pellets and water *ad libitum*. The animals were handled according to standard protocols for the use of laboratory animals (National Institute of Health USA: Public Health Service Policy on Humane Care and Use of Laboratory Animals, 2002).

Experimental Protocol

Acetic Acid-Induced Writhing in Mice

The method described by Akor et al. (2015) was used. Twenty mice were randomly divided into five groups of four animals per group. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg orally); Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance, which was an aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* orally at doses of 50 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, acetic acid (0.6%) was injected intraperitoneally into each mouse. The number of writhings, which comprised constriction of the abdominal muscle together with stretching of the hind limbs, was counted for 30 minutes after the acetic acid injection. Inhibition of pain was expressed as a percentage of protection

using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of pain} = \frac{\text{mean writhing (control)} - \text{mean writhing (treated)}}{\text{mean writhing (control)}} \times 100$$

where mean writhing (control) is the mean writhing of the distilled water-treated animals, and mean writhing (treated) is the mean writhing of the animal given the plant extract, standard drug, or each dose of *C. platypterum* leaf extract.

Hot Plate Test

The method described by Badilla et al. (2003) was used. The hot plate temperature was maintained at 55 ± 1 °C. A cut-off time of 60 seconds was adopted to prevent tissue damage. Licking, biting of the hind paw, or jumping were taken as signs of pain perception. Adult Swiss mice (25–35 g) of both sexes, screened for a suitable reaction time 24 hours before the experiment, were used. The animals were randomly divided into five groups of four mice each. Group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (10 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were administered the test substance of aqueous root extract at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). Thirty minutes later, each animal was placed on the hot plate, and the index of the response latency (time between placement and licking, biting the hind paws, or jumping) was recorded. Response latencies were taken at 30, 60, and 90 minutes after treatment (Debasis et al., 2011). The reaction time was recorded, and the percentage increase in the pain threshold was calculated.

$$\% \text{ Increase in pain threshold} = \frac{T_a - T_b}{T_b} \times 100$$

where T_a = mean reaction time at each time after treatment with either pentazocine or each dose of the *C. platypterum* leaf extract, and T_b = mean baseline latency.

Tail-Flick Test

The experiment was carried out by measuring tail withdrawal time from a heat source (Ezeja et al., 2011). Twenty rats were randomly divided into five groups of four rats per group and fasted for 12 hours. Rats were placed in the tail flick apparatus, and their pain threshold was determined. The rat in group 1 served as the control and was administered distilled water (2 ml/kg). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were

Table 1: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* on acetic acid induced writhing test in mice

Group	Number of Writhing	% Pain Inhibition
Control	96.40 ± 11.00	-
50 mg/kg	85.60 ± 27.14	11.44
100 mg/kg	61.84 ± 7.99	35.85
200 mg/kg	31.80 ± 3.31*	67.01
Aspirin (100 mg/kg)	19.20 ± 40**	80.08

The extract at 200 mg/kg and standard (aspirin, 100 mg/kg) reduced the number writhing in mice compared to control (** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

administered the test substance, an aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum*, at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg, respectively. Group 5 served as the standard and was administered pentazocine (3 mg/kg). After 30 minutes, each rat was placed on the tail flick apparatus containing heat, and the time taken for the rat to flick the tail, known as pain reaction time (PRT), was recorded for all the rats.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as the mean ± SEM. The data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism V.6.01, where $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

An aqueous root extract of *C. platypterum* (200 mg/kg) reduced abdominal constrictions in mice. The reduction was significant (* $P < 0.05$) when compared with the control. The standard drug aspirin (100 mg/kg) produced a better analgesic effect than the extract (Table 1). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain (Table 2). The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased the latency time of pain compared to the control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain, but the standard drug produced a better analgesic effect than the extract at 60 and 90 minutes (Figure 1).

Discussion

Certain noxious stimuli are painful, and reflex movements or behaviors resulting from such stimuli show a pain threshold. The stimulus may be thermal, electrical, mechanical, or chemical, according to Ezeja et al. (2011), and this informed the three analgesic models: acetic acid-induced writhing, tail flick, and hot plate methods used in this study.

In the acetic acid-induced writhing test, the aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* dose-dependently reduced the number of abdominal constrictions. The effect was significant at 200 mg/kg when compared to the control. The percentage inhibition of writhing was also dose-dependent, increasing from 0 in the control group (distilled water) to 67% in the group that received 200 mg/kg of the extract. The standard drug, aspirin (100 mg/kg), however, produced a better analgesic effect than the extract. Acetic acid acts by inducing the release of prostaglandins and lipoxygenase products into the peritoneum (Yongna et al., 2005), which activate the pain-sensing neurons that are responsive to the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications, making the test suitable for evaluating mild pain-relieving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory substances (Ngulde, 2010).

The inhibition of writhing in mice by the aqueous extract suggested a peripheral mechanism of action via inhibition of prostaglandins, serotonin, histamine, bradykinins, and substance P endings (Eekankopf et al., 1988; Ngulde, 2010). Pain sensation in the acetic acid-induced writhing method elicits a localized inflammatory response resulting from the release of free arachidonic acid from tissue phospholipids (Ahmed et al., 2006) via cyclooxygenase (COX) and prostaglandin biosynthesis (Adiukwu et al., 2013).

Table 2: Effects of aqueous root extract of *C. platypterus* on latency time in hot plate test in mice

Group	30 mins	60 mins	90 mins
Control	5.20 ± 0.59	5.78 ± 0.41	5.78 ± 0.20
50 mg/kg	6.86 ± 0.85	11.14 ± 9.91****	7.56 ± 0.58*
100 mg/kg	8.60 ± 0.55**	9.82 ± 0.63**	7.56 ± 0.32*
200 mg/kg	7.54 ± 0.20*	9.68 ± 0.44**	7.54 ± 0.14*
Pen (3 mg/kg)	7.54 ± 0.15*	11.26 ± 0.72****	8.78 ± 0.57***

The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased latency time of pain compared to control (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Values are represented as mean ± SEM, n = 5 per group.

Figure 1: Effect of aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterus* on tail flick induced pain in rats. The extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) increased latency time of pain compared to control ($p < 0.0001$, *\$ $p < 0.001$, \$ $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$). The extract at all dose increased the threshold of pain. Pen: pentozacine, values are represented as Mean ± SEM, n = 4 per group.

Acetic acid-induced writhing has been associated with an increased level of PGE2 and PGF2 in peritoneal fluids and lipoxygenase products (Dhara et al., 2000). An increase in prostaglandin levels within the peritoneal cavity then enhances inflammatory pain by increasing capillary permeability (Zakaria et al., 2008). The acetic acid-induced writhing method has been found effective for testing peripherally active

analgesics. The significant pain reduction of the plant extract might be due to analgesic principles acting within the prostaglandin pathways (Ukwuani and Hassan, 2014). The abdominal writhing induced by acetic acid has been reported to be less selective (Trongsakulet et al., 2003) and has been proposed to act indirectly by releasing endogenous mediators that stimulate neurons that are sensitive to other drugs

such as narcotics and centrally acting agents (Toma et al., 2003).

In order to confirm the anti-nociceptive effect of the extract, the tail flick and the hot plate tests were carried out. In both tests, the extract and standard (pentozacine, 3 mg/kg) significantly increased the latency time of pain compared to the control. The extract at all doses increased the threshold of pain. Thermal nociceptive tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors, and non-thermal tests are more sensitive to opioid receptors (Akor et al., 2015). The tail-flick test is considered selective for the drugs acting centrally. It measures the complex response to a non-inflammatory, acute nociceptive input and is one model used for studying central nociceptive activity (Sabina et al., 2009). The effects of the extract on the tail flick and hot plate methods confirmed its analgesic action. This further suggests a central mechanism of action for the extract. Pentazocine is known to elevate the pain threshold of albino rats or mice towards heat and pressure (Hollander et al., 2009). In the hot plate and tail flick experiments, pentazocine's effect as an analgesic had a higher effect than that of the extract. The analgesic superiority is expected since pentazocine is a narcotic analgesic used to ease deep-seated pain (Akor et al., 2015). Since there were significant activities recorded in both methods (tail flick and hot plate), the extract could be said to act both peripherally and centrally in producing analgesia. Noxious stimuli cause the release of chemicals such as prostaglandins and decarboxylated amines (histamine and serotonin), thereby inducing pain locally (Nunez et al., 1997; Yongna et al., 2005). Peripherally acting analgesics, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), act by inhibiting the release of prostaglandins (Wagner et al., 2004; Ngulde, 2010). Centrally acting analgesics such as pentazocine act through their receptors in the central nervous system (CNS) by increasing the threshold response to pain stimuli (Hollander et al., 2009). Opioid analgesics inhibit both peripheral and central mechanisms of pain, while NSAIDs inhibit only peripheral pain (Akoret al., 2015).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the aqueous root extract of *Combretum platypterum* was found to have analgesic effects. In accordance with the present study, it was observed that *Combretum platypterum* analgesic effects may be

centrally and peripherally pain-acting. Further studies should be initiated to study the exact mechanism of action and phytochemical investigations to find out which active constituent is responsible for its analgesic activity.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Phytochemical screening and antioxidant investigation of *Persea americana*

ISAH, A.* , ODIA, A.E., OBRIFOR, E.E., IKHENEMUE, O.O., AND SULEIMAN, A.

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, P.M.B 14, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Department of Science Lab. Technology, School of Applied Sciences, Auchi Polytechnic, P.M.B 13, Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: ISAH, A.

Email: abdulhakeemisah@aauekpoma.edu.ng Tel: +2347068373795

Abstract: This work investigated the phytochemical and antioxidant properties of aqueous and ethanol extract of the leaves, stem bark, seeds, and roots of *Persea americana*. The results of the qualitative phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenols, steroids, terpenoids, and flavonoids. Antioxidant activities were assayed using 1,1-Diphenyl-2-Picryl Hydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging capacity, reductive potentials, and 2,2-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) radical scavenging. Results obtained from 15 μ g/ml of all extracts had the least percentage DPPH radicals, the values of DPPH for the leaves, stem bark, seeds, and root were 14.59 ± 0.21 , 6.24 ± 0.04 , 3.53 ± 0.12 , 9.75 ± 0.17 , and 1.66 ± 0.09 respectively. The values of percentage DPPH radical scavenging increased with extract concentration. Just like DPPH radical scavenging, reducing power also increases with the concentration of extract. However, the leaves showed a higher percentage reductive power. The half maximal Inhibitory Concentration (IC₅₀) and the maximal Effective Concentration (EC₅₀) of extracts revealed that percentage values of ABTS were higher than those of DPPH in all samples. The EC₅₀ of the reducing power showed variation in values, however, *P. americana* seeds sample had the highest value for reducing power (33.12 ± 0.01).

Keywords: Alkaloids, Antioxidant, inhibitory, macerated, medicinal plant, phytochemical

Introduction

Medicinal plants have continued to attract attention in the global search for effective antimicrobial agents that can combat resistant pathogens that have been rendering many conventional drugs obsolete in the treatment of infections. Many important drugs used in medicine today are directly or indirectly derived from plants. The most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are alkaloids, tannins, steroids, terpenoids and phenolic compounds.

Phytochemicals are biologically active, naturally occurring chemical compounds found in all the parts of plants. They protect plants from various diseases and contribute to plants' aroma, flavour and colour. In recent years, secondary plant metabolites previously with unknown pharmacological activities have been extensively investigated as sources of medicinal agents. It is anticipated that phytochemicals with adequate antimicrobial efficacy will thus be used for the treatment of bacterial infections. Despite abundant literature on the antimicrobial properties

of plant extracts, most of the plant-derived chemicals have not successfully been exploited for clinical use as antibiotics. A significant part of the chemical diversity produced by plants is thought to protect plants against microbial pathogens.

Persea americana is one of the 150 varieties of avocado pear. It is widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions of West Africa. It grows into a tree with a height of about 80 feet. It has leathery, evergreen leaves, and its flowers are rarely unisexual. The seed of *Persea americana* has diverse applications in ethnomedicine, ranging from treatment of diarrhea, dysentery, toothache, and intestinal parasites to skin treatment and beautification. The leaves have been reported to possess anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities. The seeds are rich in tannins, carotenoids, and tocopherols. The fruit has been shown to inhibit the in-vitro growth of prostate cancer cell lines, and "persin" from avocado leaves has been shown to have antifungal properties and to be toxic to silkworms.

Figure 1: MAP SHOWING THE LOCATION OF IKABIGBO COMMUNITY

The effect of *P. americana* extract was evaluated on in-vitro rat lymphocyte proliferation. Antioxidant activity and phenolic content of seeds of avocado pear were found to be greater than 70

In this study, the phytochemical and antioxidant activity of extracts of *P. americana* tree was carried out with a view to provide more scientific basis on the claim by traditional healers of its uses in traditional medicine in the context of the continued search for active therapeutic agents from plants.

Materials and Methods

Location

MAP SHOWING THE LOCATION OF IKABIGBO COMMUNITY

Sample Collection/Identification

Samples of the leaves, seed, stem, and root of *Persea americana* were obtained from a farm settlement in Ikabigbo, Uzairue, Etsako West Local Government Area of Edo state, Nigeria. The samples were authenticated in the herbarium laboratory of Botany Department, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. The samples were rinsed with distilled water, air-dried in the laboratory for about a month, and then pulverized with a ceramic mortar and pestle.

Preparation of Extracts

Pulverized leaves, seed, stem, and root were extracted using 80% ethanol and distilled water as solvents as follows: each of the pulverized samples was put in glass containers and the ethanol was added to each

container; the same setup was repeated with distilled water as solvent for the aqueous extract. The setup was left for about 72 hours and agitated 6-hourly for the extraction of the bioactive components into the solvent. The solution was filtered with muslin cloth to remove the supernatant, and the leaves, seed, stem, and root shafts remaining as residues. The crude extract was obtained by evaporating the solvent using a rotary evaporator. The extracts obtained were then transferred into airtight glass containers for further analysis. Both the ethanolic and aqueous crude extracts were analyzed for phytochemical screening while only the aqueous extracts were investigated for antioxidant properties.

Phytochemical Screening

The preliminary phytochemical screening of the ethanolic and aqueous extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* were carried out in order to ascertain the presence of its phytoconstituents by utilizing standard conventional protocols. The extracts were screened for the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenolics, steroids, terpenes, flavonoids, and cardiac glycosides as reported by Irabor et al.

Antioxidant Activity

Aqueous extracts of the plant parts were utilized for the antioxidants assay.

1,1-Diphenyl-2-PicrylHydrazyl (DPPH) Assay

The antioxidant activity by DPPH assay was carried out as described by Molyneux, using the stable free radical DPPH. To 1 ml of various concentrations of the extract, 1 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH was added to the test tube. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard for comparison. After incubation for 30 mins in the dark at room temperature, absorbance was read at 517 nm. The percent DPPH radical scavenging was calculated with the equation below and the experiment was carried out in triplicate.

Reductive Potential (Ferric cyanide (Fe^{3+}) Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay)

Reducing power of the extracts was measured by the direct reduction of $\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{CN})_6$ to $\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{CN})_6$ and was determined by absorbance measurement of the formation of the Perl's Prussian Blue complex following the addition of excess Fe^{3+} , as described previously. Different concentrations of extracts in 0.5

mL of distilled water were mixed with 1.25 mL of 0.2 M, pH 6.6 sodium phosphate buffer and 1.25 mL of potassium ferricyanide $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ (1%). The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. After 20 min incubation, the reaction mixture was acidified with 1.25 mL of trichloroacetic acid (10%). Finally, 0.5 mL of $FeCl_3$ (0.1%) was added to this solution and the absorbance was measured at 700 nm in a spectrophotometer. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicates greater reducing capability.

2,2-Azino-Bis(3-Ethylbenzothiazoline-6-Sulfonic Acid) (ABTS) Radical Scavenging Assay

The scavenging activity of extracts against ABTS radical was determined by following the method described by Roberta et al. with little modification. Briefly, the mixture of stock solutions of 7 mM ABTS and 2.4 mM potassium persulphate ($K_2S_2O_8$) in equal volumes were allowed to stand in the dark for 12-16 h at room temperature. Prior to assay, ABTS solution was diluted in ethanol to give an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.02 at 734 nm. 2800 μ l of the resulting solutions was allowed to react with 200 μ l of the plant extracts with different concentrations. The reaction mixture was incubated at room temperature for 30 min and absorbance was read at 734 nm. The same was done for the ascorbic acid standard of various concentrations (15 – 150 g/ml).

Statistical Analysis

All assays were carried out in triplicates and results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. The data was subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the differences between various concentrations were determined by Tukey's multiple comparisons test using GraphPad Prism 8.0 statistical. The P values of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. The IC_{50} and EC_{50} values were estimated by nonlinear curve-fitting and presented as their respective 95% confidence limits.

1 Results and Discussion

The phytochemical screening of *P. americana* revealed the presence of some of the phytochemicals screened and are shown in Table 1. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, terpenes and steroids, phenolics and tannins. Saponins were conspicuously absent in the aqueous extract of *P. americana* seed. Terpenoids and steroids are absent in ethanol extracts of *P. americana* stem; this is in agreement with Doughari

(2012). Also, the absence of alkaloids was recorded in the aqueous extract of *P. americana* leaves.

These phytochemicals are known to support bioactive activities in medicinal plants and may therefore be responsible for the antioxidant properties of the leaves, seed, stem, and root. Alkaloids have been associated with medicinal uses for centuries and one of their common biological properties is their cytotoxicity [?]. Tannins are generally known to be useful in the treatment of inflamed and ulcerated tissues and have remarkable activity in cancer prevention [?]. Thus, the presence of these phytochemical constituents in *P. americana* may justify the plant's inclusion in folk preparation of the popular antimalarial potion, "Agbo" in the west and central African region, particularly in Nigeria.

The antioxidant properties analyzed were assessed with regard to their antioxidant activity as typified by their reducing power and free radical scavenging ability. Data obtained showed that *P. americana* possessed strong antioxidant activities, although the ranking of antioxidant activity of samples may vary with the analytical methods because of different mechanisms for each analysis. Hence the choice of DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging activity in this research work is due to the fact that they are the most widely used and reliable methods for screening the antioxidant activity of plant extracts.

The DPPH radical scavenging of the studied plant leaves, seed, stem, and root extracts showed a good scavenging activity as shown in Table 2. Figure 1 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with standard ascorbic acid. *P. americana* exhibited high radical scavenging activities at 30 to 150 μ g/ml and it was revealed that extracts were dose-dependent. Figure 2 shows DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. Figure 3 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with standard ascorbic acid. Figure 4 compares the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* leaves with ascorbic acid.

There was a statistically significant difference between extracts and ascorbic acid used as standard ($p < 0.05$). The scavenging effects of all extracts at a concentration of 150 μ g/ml were 34.84 – 39.90%. The scavenging activity was not as good for the *P. americana* ($17.43 \pm 0.56\%$ for the seed, $25.27 \pm 0.39\%$ for the leaves, $38.03 \pm 0.36\%$ for the stem,

Table 1: Table 1: Phytochemicals in aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Persea americana*

Phytochemicals	P. americana aqueous extract				P. americana ethanolic extract			
	Seed	leaves	stem	Root	Seed	leaves	stem	Root
Alkaloids	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Saponins	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Terpene/steroids	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
Phenolics	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tannins	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

KEY: + = present, - = absent

Table 2: **Table 2:** DPPH radical scavenging (%) of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* at varying concentrations

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	14.59 \pm 0.62	8.65 \pm 0.07	7.12 \pm 0.33	2.21 \pm 0.29	5.46 \pm 0.21
30	31.26 \pm 0.33	8.96 \pm 0.07	15.21 \pm 0.36	10.71 \pm 0.13	13.58 \pm 0.26
60	41.26 \pm 2.85	27.38 \pm 0.49	19.09 \pm 0.09	13.33 \pm 0.21	19.43 \pm 0.19
90	62.92 \pm 1.46	32.11 \pm 0.45	24.19 \pm 0.31	20.90 \pm 0.15	20.36 \pm 0.60
120	77.09 \pm 0.24	34.64 \pm 0.04	26.42 \pm 0.12	27.30 \pm 0.11	24.35 \pm 0.21
150	90.91 \pm 0.15	39.90 \pm 0.39	40.21 \pm 0.55	36.85 \pm 0.15	34.84 \pm 0.12

(All values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$.)

and 40.86% for the root) as compared to ascorbic acid. DPPH radical scavenging activities of the extracts were dose-dependent; the radical scavenging activities increased with concentrations of extracts. Results obtained from DPPH radicals scavenging suggest that DPPH radical was significantly bound by the extracts of leaves of *P. americana* (with IC₅₀ value of $44.25 \pm 1.59 \mu\text{g/ml}$). These values of extract scavenging abilities are comparable to that of ascorbic acid (with IC₅₀ value of $37.57 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{g/ml}$) as shown in Table 5, showing no significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

Results for the ABTS assay are presented in Table 4, and the inhibiting power was found to be dosage-dependent. Figure 5 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* leaves and ascorbic acid. Figure 6 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* seed and ascorbic acid. Figure 7 shows ABTS radical scavenging activity of extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. Figure 8 compares the ABTS radical scavenging activities of *P. americana* root with “standard” ascorbic acid.

ABTS assay is an excellent tool for determining

Figure 2: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* seed at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM (n = 3), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not statistically different $p < 0.05$).

the antioxidant activity of hydrogen-donating antioxidants and chain-breaking antioxidants. The extracts of *P. americana* effectively scavenged ABTS radicals generated by the reaction between 2,2-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazolin-6-sulphonic acid) (ABTS) ammonium persulphate. Table 4 shows the activity of extracts of the plant parts, and the ascorbic acid standard was found to

Table 3: ABTS radical scavenging (%) of extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *Persea americana*

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	17.33 \pm 0.25	2.68 \pm 0.19	6.69 \pm 0.31	6.39 \pm 0.24	2.14 \pm 0.27
30	22.60 \pm 0.54	6.09 \pm 0.47	6.68 \pm 0.10	9.23 \pm 0.53	4.32 \pm 0.36
60	48.34 \pm 0.40	7.62 \pm 0.10	7.86 \pm 0.38	10.15 \pm 0.34	7.79 \pm 0.27
90	61.13 \pm 0.17	13.82 \pm 0.56	11.28 \pm 0.28	21.31 \pm 1.37	14.04 \pm 0.08
120	77.70 \pm 0.18	21.03 \pm 0.39	11.44 \pm 0.54	26.83 \pm 0.68	29.31 \pm 0.27
150	98.58 \pm 0.24	25.27 \pm 0.39	17.43 \pm 0.56	38.03 \pm 0.36	40.86 \pm 0.51

(All values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at varying concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAST, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars along the same group are significantly different $p < 0.05$).

Figure 4: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* root at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different $p < 0.05$).

increase in a dose-dependent manner from 2.68 to 52.27% (*P. americana* leaves), 6.69 to 17.43% (*P. americana* seed), 6.39 to 38.03% (*P. americana* stem), 2.14 to 40.86% (*P. americana* root), and 17.33 to 98.58% (ascorbic acid standard) at different concentrations from 15 to 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The extracts of *P. americana* seed, *P. americana* leaves, and the standard ascorbic acid exhibited comparative IC50 values of 55.68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 78.68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 55.42 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Therefore, the recorded IC50 values for the extracts of the plant indicated their ability to scavenge free radicals, thereby preventing lipid oxidation via a chain-breaking reaction.

The results of the reducing power assay of *P. americana* extracts are summarized in Table 4. Figure 9 compares the reducing power of leaves of *P. americana* with ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Figure 10 compares the reducing power of seed of *P. americana* with ascorbic acid used

as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Extracts and the standard are dose-dependent. Figure 11 shows the reducing power of root of *P. americana* and ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power. Figure 12 shows the reducing power of stem of *P. americana* and ascorbic acid used as a standard. Increase in absorbance indicates an increase in reducing power.

High absorbance depicts high reducing power. The data obtained in this study showed that all the extracts are dose dependent; that is, absorbance increased with concentration. Among the tested extracts, *P. americana* leaves showed the highest reducing power ($\text{EC}_{50} = 19.58 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{g/ml}$). This value was even higher than that of ascorbic acid ($\text{EC}_{50} = 21.99 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g/ml}$). The reducing capacity of a compound may serve as a significant indicator of its potential antioxidant activity. The reducing properties are generally associated with the antioxidant action

Table 4: Reducing power of extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* at varying concentrations

Extracts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ascorbic acid	Leaves	Seed	Stem	Root
15	0.075 \pm 0.002	0.018 \pm 0.002	0.006 \pm 0.001	0.024 \pm 0.001	0.013 \pm 0.001
30	0.157 \pm 0.004	0.054 \pm 0.001	0.016 \pm 0.004	0.036 \pm 0.005	0.017 \pm 0.003
60	0.352 \pm 0.001	0.117 \pm 0.018	0.024 \pm 0.003	0.094 \pm 0.004	0.050 \pm 0.002
90	0.483 \pm 0.006	0.172 \pm 0.015	0.067 \pm 0.005	0.142 \pm 0.003	0.090 \pm 0.011
120	0.647 \pm 0.004	0.174 \pm 0.016	0.095 \pm 0.003	0.174 \pm 0.002	0.114 \pm 0.009
150	0.912 \pm 0.007	0.269 \pm 0.001	0.290 \pm 0.008	0.241 \pm 0.010	0.137 \pm 0.004

(All values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values in the same range along the same row are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 5: DPPH radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves of *P. americana* at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different $p < 0.05$).

Figure 7: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* seed at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 6: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of leaves of *P. americana* at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 8: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* stem at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAsT, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p < 0.05$).

of reductones. Gordon (1990) reported that the antioxidant action of reductones is based on the breaking of the free radical chain by donating a hydrogen ion. The reduction of ferrous iron (Fe^{3+})

to ferric iron (Fe^{2+}) is measured by the intensity of the resultant blue-green solution which absorbs at 700 nm. The results linked the marked ferric reducing power activity of the extract to the presence of

Figure 9: ABTS radical scavenging activity of ascorbic acid and extracts of *P. americana* root at different concentrations. ASC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm SEM (n = 3), bars with the same alphabet along the same group are not significantly different, $p > 0.05$).

polyphenols, which may act similarly to reductones by donating electrons and reacting with free radicals to convert them into more stable products and terminate free radical chain reactions (Muanya, 2007).

Figure 10: Reducing power of extracts of leaves of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAL, *P. americana* leaves. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

Conclusion

In the present study, the aqueous extracts of leaves, seed, stem, and root of *P. americana* were found to contain phytochemicals, as revealed in both aqueous and ethanolic extracts. Antioxidant and radical scavenging activities, as assessed through various models including DPPH, ABTS, and reducing power assays, demonstrated that the plant parts analyzed have significant potential in radical scavenging compared to ascorbic acid, a standard antioxidant.

Figure 11: Reducing power of extracts of seed of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAS, *P. americana* seed. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

Figure 12: Reducing power of extracts of root of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAR, *P. americana* root. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

This supports the use of these plant parts in modern traditional medicine. The plant may also enhance the nutritional value of various foods.

All extracts exhibited concentration-dependent antioxidant and radical scavenging activities. Notably, the extracts of leaves and seeds showed the highest ability to quench DPPH radicals and scavenge ABTS radicals. In general, the leaves, seed, and stem of *P. americana* exhibit promising antioxidant effects that warrant further investigation for potential therapeutic applications. Adeyemi, O. O., Okpo, S. O., Ogunti, O. O. (2002). Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect of the aqueous extract of leaves of *Persea americana* Mill (Lauraceae). *Fitoterapia*, 73*, 375-380.

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Table 5: IC50 and EC50 of leaves, seed, stem, and root extracts of *P. americana*.

Samples	DPPH (IC50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$))	ABTS (IC50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$))	Reducing Power (EC50 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$))
AAC	37.57 \pm 0.22	55.42 \pm 1.06	21.99 \pm 0.12
PAL	44.25 \pm 1.59	78.68 \pm 2.29	19.58 \pm 0.10
PAS	62.34 \pm 5.73	55.68 \pm 7.42	33.12 \pm 0.01
PAS _t	66.98 \pm 0.64	88.16 \pm 7.01	21.63 \pm 0.45
PAR	50.08 \pm 4.53	97.58 \pm 0.55	20.65 \pm 0.86

(Values are expressed as mean \pm standard error of three replicates. Values were tested by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Values with the same subset in a group are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Key: PAL (*P. americana* leaves), PAS (*P. americana* seed), PAS_t (*P. americana* stem), and PAR (*P. americana* root).)

Figure 13: Reducing power of extracts of stem of ascorbic acid and *P. americana* at different concentrations. AAC, ascorbic acid; PAS_t, *P. americana* stem. (The bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of three replicate values)

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COMPARISON OF THE CONCENTRATION OF PAHs IN RAW AND ROASTED BEEF SAMPLES FROM EKPOMA

OBRIFOR, E. B.¹, EGBON, E. E.¹, ISAH, A.¹, ERHABOR, D. O.³, OGONEGBU, A. C.²

¹Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

²Dennis Osadebay University, Anwai, Asaba

³Federal College of Education (Technical), Umunze, Anambra State

Corresponding author: essayshype@yahoo.com; Tel: +2348067502568

ABSTRACT

The determination of the concentration of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in raw and roasted beef samples from Ekpoma, Edo State was the aim of the study. Samples were obtained from different suya outlets for the roasted samples, while the fresh beef were obtained from different spots in Ekpoma main market. Sixteen (16) polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in fresh and roasted beef samples were evaluated in this study. Extraction was done using a mix solvent of cyclohexane and acetone in a ratio of 50:50. Analysis was performed by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (G.C-MS). The procedure involved extraction, and adsorption column for clean-up. The cleaned fluid from samples was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and compressed air. The resulting solution was stored in vial bottles ready for PAH determination. The part of beef used for the experiment was the tissue. The various samples were run through the G.C-MS chromatography column. Results of each sample were obtained graphically. Findings revealed that of all sixteen (16) PAHs targeted, only two (2) PAHs were detected: Pyrene and Fluoranthene. Bulk of the PAHs were below detectable limits. The raw beef samples all had no PAHs detected (below detectable limits). The analysis of the raw and roasted beef samples was done in triplicates. Only roasted meat 1 (RTMT1) had the presence of Pyrene, with a concentration of 1.714 mg/kg, while roasted meat 2 (RTMT2) and roasted meat 3 (RTMT3) had the same concentration of 0.009 mg/kg of Fluoranthene. From the findings, it was observed that fresh beef samples normally do not contain PAHs, but during processing by roasting, PAHs can be introduced in some cases. Bulk of the PAHs in the roasted beef samples were below detectable limits. From the findings, the concentration of PAHs was below the recommended level: 5.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) in smoked meat and fishery products.

Keywords: *Polycyclic Aromatic Compound, Fresh and Roasted Beef, Bos taurus*

Introduction

The increase in the case of cancerous growth is quite alarming in contemporary times. Several factors have been attributed to this effect. One of the substances which has been partly identified by scientists among the many factors is the presence of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in food consumed, especially when roasted.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are hydrocarbons—organic compounds containing only carbon and hydrogen—that are composed of multiple aromatic rings. PAHs are uncharged, non-polar molecules found in coal and tar deposits. They are also produced by the thermal decomposition of organic matter (Wikipedia, 2018).

PAHs occur in varying amounts in water, soil, air, and even in some food and food products like fish

and meat in trace amounts (Erhabor & Edjere, 2018). In Nigeria, meat preservation is either by smoking or drying, and in the process of preservation by drying, the shelf life is prolonged.

When food items are processed by subjecting them to heat treatment such as drying, smoking, roasting, baking, and frying, it has been reported that the amount of PAHs in them increases (Ishizaki et al., 2010). Humans are reported to obtain most of this PAH contamination from their diet (Farhadian et al., 2011). Olabemiwo (2013) reported an increase in the level of PAHs in grilled/roasted maize and plantain. The flames contain PAHs that adhere to the surface of the meat (Cross & Sinha, 2004). In barbecued meat, PAH levels were found to increase from average background values usually in the range of 0.01 to 1 g/kg in uncooked foods (meats, fish, vegetables) to 130 g/kg (Gómez-Guillén et al., 2009).

The presence of variable quantities of PAHs has been reported in different food categories and beverages including vegetables and fruits, cereals, oils and fats, smoked products (e.g., meat), coffee, and tea (Tuteja et al., 2011).

In a study carried out to investigate the levels of PAHs in singed and unsinged hides and skins of animals slaughtered at three district abattoirs (Obosi, Uga, and Kwata) in Anambra State, Ofomata et al. (2020) found the total PAHs of raw and singed cattle hides to be respectively 0.80 and 12.33 g/kg for Obosi district, 0.56 and 6.96 g/kg for Uga district, and 8.30 and 16.24 g/kg for Kwata district. The total PAHs levels in raw and singed goat skins were respectively 2.75 and 9.00 g/kg for Obosi district, 1.76 and 6.42 g/kg for Uga district, and 1.30 and 5.19 g/kg for Kwata district. The levels of some PAHs in singed hides and skins were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the unsinged samples.

Also, in research conducted by Akpogheli (2018) on the assessment of PAHs in smoked fish and suya meat consumed in Warri, Nigeria, the results revealed that the PAH values for grilled meat/smoked fish are far higher than those obtained from boiled water, indicating that roasting introduces and increases PAHs in food (meat).

Analysis of charcoal-roasted common food items has proven the presence of PAHs such as benzo(a)pyrene, anthracene, chrysene, benzo(a)anthracene, and indeno(1,2,3-c,d)pyrene (Linda et al., 2011). Most of these PAHs have been found to be carcinogenic, while some are not (Lijinsky, 1999). Research carried out by Akpogheli (2018) also supports this finding.

Polycyclic aromatic compounds, as chemical compounds, are known potent carcinogenic compounds. A major source of exposure is through food contaminated with PAHs (Ishizaki et al., 2010). These food substances can be contaminated either through processing (drying methods) or from the environment from which the meat is bred.

At ambient temperatures, PAHs are solids with low vapor pressure and very low water solubility, which tends to decrease with increasing molecular weights. They attach strongly to soil and other particles, break down slowly, undergo photodecomposition when exposed to ultraviolet light from solar radiation, react readily with pollutants such as ozone, nitrogen oxides, and sulfur dioxide, and can be degraded by

some microorganisms in the soil. They are soluble in many organic solvents and are highly lipophilic, meaning they mix more easily with oil than water. The larger compounds are less water-soluble and less volatile (i.e., less prone to evaporation). Because of these properties, PAHs in the environment are found primarily in soil, sediments, and oily substances. However, they are also a component of concern in particulate matter suspended in the air (Majid Kermani et al., 2023). When PAHs attach to dust or ash, they could cause lung irritation. Skin contact with PAHs may cause redness, blistering, and peeling (Hui Jin et al., 2024). The following health effects can occur after several years of exposure to PAHs:

- **Cancer:** Many PAHs are carcinogenic, producing tumors (cancer) such as benzo[a]pyrene, methyl cholanthrene, and dibenz[a,f]anthracene. Although studies in experimental animals on individual PAHs, notably benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P), have shown various toxicological effects, including hematological effects, reproductive and developmental toxicity, and immunotoxicity, the critical effects are genotoxicity and cancer (Luch, 2005). Benzo(a)pyrene has been shown to cause lung and skin cancer in laboratory animals. Other PAHs are not known to have this effect. Extracts of various types of smoke containing PAHs have caused lung tumors in laboratory animals (Luch, 2005).
- **Toxicity:** PAH toxicity is very structurally dependent, with isomers (PAHs with the same formula and number of rings) varying from being nontoxic to extremely toxic. Highly carcinogenic PAHs may be small or large. One notable PAH compound, benzo(a)pyrene, is known as the first chemical carcinogen discovered (Luch, 2005).

Materials and Methods

Location

Ekpoma is a town in Edo State, Nigeria. It is the administrative headquarters of the Esan West Local Government Area. Ekpoma lies on the geographical coordinates of latitude $6^{\circ}45'N$ and longitude $6^{\circ}08'E$. The town has an official Post Office and is home to the Ambrose Alli University. The roasted beef (suya) samples were collected from various suya outlets in Ekpoma, Esan West L.G.A. of Edo State, Nigeria. The

raw beef samples were collected from different spots in the Ekpoma main market.

Materials

Meat Samples

1. Bos taurus commonly called beef meat (RAW)
2. Bos taurus commonly called beef meat (ROASTED)

Chemicals and Reagents

All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade and included the following:

- Acetone (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)
- Dichloromethane (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)
- Cyclohexane (Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, United States)

The three solvents were redistilled before use to keep them free from impurities.

Sodium Sulphate: Granular and anhydrous. The sodium sulphate granules were purified by heating at 400°C for 4 hours in a shallow tray and cooled in a desiccator.

Mix 26: The internal standard or surrogate, Mix 26, comes in 1 ml vials. It was prepared by diluting a 1 ml solution containing 4000 ng/ μ l in 100 ml of dichloromethane. The solution, which contains 40 ng/100 ml, has a fluorescent green color.

Equipment/Apparatus

The equipment/apparatus used include:

- Water bath
- Vials and corks
- Test tubes
- Round bottom flasks
- Rotary evaporator
- Thermometer
- Silica gel packed cartridges
- Conical flasks
- Retort stands
- Weighing balance
- Spatula
- Beakers
- Volumetric pipettes: 1 ml, 5 ml, and 10 ml
- Micro syringes: 10 μ L, 100 μ L, 250 μ L, 500 μ L, 1000 μ L
- Drying oven
- Desiccator
- Blender
- Ultrasonic bath
- SPE cartridges with stand
- Gas chromatography instrument
- Oven and drier

Method

Sampling Area

Ekpoma, Esan West L.G.A. of Edo State, Nigeria, was the sampling location.

Sample Collection

The roasted meat samples, *Bos taurus* commonly called suya, were collected from three different locations in Ekpoma:

- Ujuolen junction axis (RTMT 1), a very busy junction with high traffic and vehicular activity
- Ekpoma market square axis (RTMT 2)
- New market axis (RTMT 3)

Composite sampling was applied at these locations to obtain representative samples.

The fresh cow meat samples, *Bos taurus* commonly called beef meat, were collected from three different locations in Ekpoma:

- Ekpoma market square axis (FRMT 1)
- New market axis (FRMT 2)
- Hausa market axis (FRMT 3)

Composite sampling was also used at these locations.

The samples were kept in polythene bags, properly labeled, placed in coolers with ice, and transported to Earth Quest Laboratory, Otokutu, Warri, Delta State, where they were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C prior to further processing.

Sample Preparation

The fresh meat samples from the sampling sites were washed and re-rinsed with distilled water. The fresh and roasted samples were separately ground using a Mikachi meat grinder, homogenized using a laboratory pestle and mortar, and then stored in a refrigerator at 4°C prior to extraction and analysis.

Extraction and Clean-Up of Samples

The fresh and roasted meat samples were separately ground using a blender (Mikachi meat grinder). The blender was washed, rinsed, and re-rinsed with distilled water after each use. Fifty grams of each meat sample was mixed with 25 g of sodium sulphate and 200 ml of a 50/50 cyclohexane/acetone mixture in a tightly covered bottle, with 10 ml of Mix 26 internal standard added to each bottle. The bottles containing the sample, solvents mixture, sodium sulphate, and internal standard were placed inside an ultrasonic bath (Astrabro ultrasonic cleaner, model 7E) for 2 hours, with shaking every 10 minutes.

Twenty-five milliliters of the extract was collected using a pipette and filler, concentrated using a rotary evaporator to 5 ml, and then further concentrated to 1 ml using compressed air. The clean-up was done using a solid phase extractor, and cyclohexane was employed as the eluting solvent. The cleaned-up sample was concentrated to 1 ml using compressed air, stored in 1 ml vials, and subjected to GC analysis using an FID detector.

Gas Chromatography Operating Procedure

Instrument type: Gas chromatography system 6890 series

Product: HP

Detector type: FID

The basic chromatography parameters for the analysis of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are as follows:

- Initial Temperature: 100°C
- Rate 1: 4°C/min
- Final Temperature: 330°C
- Detector Temperature: 300°C

One milliliter extracts of both the *Clarias gariepinus* (raw and roasted) and *Bos taurus* (raw and roasted) kept in vials were analyzed using GC-MS model QP2010SE, Shimadzu, Japan.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Polynuclear Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

The summary of the concentration of various Polynuclear Aromatic Compounds (PAHs) present in raw and roasted meat samples is shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows the comparison of results between raw meat and roasted meat samples. This research was conducted to determine the presence and concentration of 16 PAHs in raw and roasted meat samples from Ekpoma, Edo State. The results showed that not all 16 targeted PAHs were present in the raw and roasted meat samples. A total of only two PAHs were observed in the samples: Pyrene and Fluoranthene. The concentration of PAHs in the samples is shown in Table 2.

No PAHs were detected in any of the raw meat samples labeled FRMT 1, FRMT 2, and FRMT 3. This result is consistent with other researchers' findings

Table 1: Polynuclear Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

COMPONENT	FRMT1	FRMT2	FRMT3	RTMT1	RTMT2	RTMT3
Naphthalene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Acenaphthalene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Acenaphthene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Florene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Phenanthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Fluoranthene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.009	0.009
Pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.000	0.000
Benzo(a)anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Chrysene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(b)fluoranthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(k)fluoranthrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Total PAH (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	BDL	1.714	0.009	0.009

Note: Each of the coded samples are averages of triplicate measurements of representative samples from each sampling spot.

KEY: RTMT – ROASTED MEAT; FRMT – RAW MEAT; BDL – BELOW DETECTABLE LIMIT

that raw foods typically do not contain high levels of PAHs, which are generally formed during processing such as roasting, baking, smoking, or frying (Amos-Tauta, Inengite, Abasi, & Amirize, 2013). For example, a study by Ofomata, I. B. et al. (2020) investigating PAH levels in singed and unsinged hides and skins of animals slaughtered at three district abattoirs (Obosi, Uga, and Kwata) in Anambra State found that total PAHs in raw and singed cattle hides were 0.80 and 12.33 g/kg for Obosi district, 0.56 and 6.96 g/kg for Uga district, and 8.30 and 16.24 g/kg for Kwata district. Similarly, total PAHs in raw and singed goat skins were 2.75 and 9.00 g/kg for Obosi district, 1.76 and 6.42 g/kg for Uga district, and 1.30 and 5.19 g/kg for Kwata district. The levels of some PAHs in singed hides and skins were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in unsinged samples.

The concentration of PAHs in roasted meat (suya) samples in our study, RTMT 1, RTMT 2, and RTMT 3, ranged between 0.009 to 1.714 mg/kg. The total average PAHs level in suya was 0.576 mg/kg.

Table 2. Concentration (mg/kg) levels of PAHs in raw and roasted meat

[h!]

The results of the raw beef samples were comparable with the report of Amos-Tauta et al. (2013), where the PAH concentrations were below detectable limits. However, the roasted meat (suya) samples showed the presence of Pyrene and Fluoranthene. This could be due to the processing location of the roasted meat. RTMT 1 was sourced from Ujuoelen junction axis, a very busy spot with heavy vehicle activity. Akpoghelie (2018) noted that poor road networks and potholes can increase traffic congestion, leading to higher PAH emissions. To determine the source of PAHs in samples, whether from pyrolytic, combustive, petrogenic, or petroleum hydrocarbon origins, the ratios of Fluoranthene (Fla) to Pyrene (Pyr) and Phenanthrene (Ph) to Anthracene (An) are often used. A ratio of Fluoranthene to Pyrene greater than one ($Fla/Pyr > 1$) indicates a pyrolytic source, while $Fla/Pyr < 1$ suggests a petroleum hydrocarbon source. Similarly, a Phenanthrene to

Table 2: Concentration (mg/kg) levels of PAHs in raw and roasted meat

PAHs AVERAGE	FRMT1	FRMT2	FRMT3	AVERAGE	RTMT1	RTMT2	RTMT3
Pyrene 0.570	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.000	0.000
Fluoranthene 0.006	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.009	0.009
TOTAL 0.576	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.714	0.009	0.009

Anthracene ratio less than ten (Ph/An \leq 10) indicates a combustion source, while Ph/An $>$ 10 suggests a petrogenic source. In this study, the PAHs in the roasted meat can be attributed to a pyrolytic source, as the ratio is $>$ 1.

The PAHs concentration of RTMT 1 was higher than that of RTMT 2 and RTMT 3. Apart from the busy location where the sample (RTMT 1) was sourced, other factors that could affect the results include the part of the beef (muscle) used, as some parts may have higher fat content; the method of preparation; the length of cooking; and the amount of heat used (Akpogheli, 2018).

Figure 1: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

Figure 1: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Content (mg/kg)

KEY: ROASTED MEAT: RTMT; RAW MEAT: FRMT

The highest concentration of total PAHs was detected in RTMT 1, with a concentration of 1.71 mg/kg, and the lowest in FRMT 1, FRMT 2, and RTMT 3, all having concentrations below detectable limits.

The total PAHs concentration can be attributed to the temperature of heating and the particle size of PAHs sorbed into organic matter. High-temperature heating tends to produce high molecular weight PAHs (Choi et al., 2010). High molecular weight PAHs, which have more than four rings, are more likely to be formed. Pyrene was detected in RTMT 1. Additionally, two- to four-ringed PAHs volatilize sufficiently to appear in the atmosphere in gaseous form, with their physical state depending on temperature (Walker et al., 2013). High temperatures generate high molecular weight PAHs, while low temperatures generate low molecular weight PAHs (Wikipedia, 2018). This could explain the high concentration of Pyrene.

Conclusion

The results of the six (6) samples in this study showed a total of two (2) PAH compounds present. Total PAH concentrations for roasted meat samples were higher than those of raw meat. This is because, when food, particularly meat and meat products, are smoked, roasted, barbecued, or grilled, PAHs are formed as a result of incomplete combustion or thermal decomposition of the organic material (WHO, 2006). According to the results of this research, the concentration of PAHs is above the recommended level of 5.0 g/kg or 0.005 g/g BaP in smoked meat and the 2 g/kg fixed by European standards (Akpogheli, 2018). No PAHs were detected in the fresh beef samples. It was also observed that when raw meat is roasted, the amount of PAHs increases, and new PAHs can be formed in the process.

From the foregoing analysis, caution must therefore be taken because of the adverse effects posed by exposure to PAHs through food, such as genotoxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity. This research sought to compare the concentration of samples based on location, as this is a factor in the presence and

concentration of PAHs in food samples.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NUTRIENTS AND PHYTOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF MATURED AND YOUNG LEAVES OF *Manihot esculenta*, *Arachis hypogea*, AND *Parkia biglobosa*

OGIDI, O. I.*¹, ADDY, P. S.¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe

Corresponding author: Peresogoi@gmail.com; Tel: +2348039529426

ABSTRACT

The nutritive and phytochemical constituents of three plant leaves were investigated. The plants include: Matured *Manihot esculenta*, six weeks old *Manihot esculenta*, matured *Arachis hypogea*, two weeks old *Arachis hypogea*, matured *Parkia biglobosa* and two weeks old *Parkia biglobosa*. The nutrients and phytochemicals determined quantitatively were: soluble protein, soluble sugar, total protein, nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, saponin, alkaloid, and tannin. The results of the quantitative analysis of these plants show that all the vegetable plant leaves contained all the parameters analyzed in varying proportion. For the quantitative analysis, matured *M. esculenta* had the highest amount of total protein (36.69% FW) and saponin (0.21g/g FW), six weeks old *M. esculenta* had the highest amount of total soluble protein (0.26g/g FW), total soluble sugar (0.12g/g FW) and nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (2.25% FW), matured *P. biglobosa* had the highest amount of alkaloid (0.04g/100g FW). Two weeks old *A. hypogea*, matured *A. hypogea* and matured *P. biglobosa* had same amount of soluble protein (0.18g/g FW), matured *M. esculenta*, two weeks old *A. hypogea* and two weeks old *P. biglobosa* had same amount of alkaloid (0.02g/100g FW), matured *M. esculenta*, two weeks old *A. hypogea* and two weeks old *P. biglobosa* had same amount of tannin (0.04g/g FW) and matured *A. hypogea* and matured *P. biglobosa* had same amount of tannin (0.05g/g FW). The significance of these results showed that there are lots of phytochemicals and nutrients present in *M. esculenta*, *A. hypogea* and *P. biglobosa* leaves which can be utilized as potential vegetables in traditional Nigeria soups.

Keywords: Vegetable; Phytochemicals; Nutrients; Mature; Young; Leaves

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, especially in the Western and Southern regions of the country, many kinds of soups are made with various vegetables like pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*) leaves, waterleaf (*Talinum fruticosum*), bitterleaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*) which are quite rich nutritionally (Tonukari et al., 2013). A number of studies have proved that vegetables contain some nutrients such as sugars, amino acids and vitamins, which have long been recognized for their health benefits to humans (Donoghue et al., 2006; Ovuru et al., 2023). As technology and research techniques are improving, other substances in vegetables that were previously ignored are getting the spotlight. Vegetables are rich sources of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, carotenoids, anthocyanins, vitamins and other polyphenolics (Lee et al., 2005; Adesina et al., 2013). Such compounds play roles in disease prevention/reduce disease risk factors through antioxidant activity (Enerijiofi &

Isola, 2019). Researchers have identified hundreds of compounds in vegetable crops with functional qualities and they continue to make new discoveries surrounding the complex benefits of phytochemicals such as lycopene in tomatoes, curcumin in turmeric, gingerol in ginger, organosulphur compounds in allium species, omega-3 fatty acids in cucurbitaceous vegetable seeds and so on (Ram et al., 2000).

Cassava leaves are largely consumed in Africa and are among the top three African indigenous vegetables rich in nutrients (Umuhozariho et al., 2013). In Nigeria, especially in the Northern part of the country, cassava leaves are used in the preparation of soup. Cassava leaves soup is widely consumed in Central Africa. In Central Africa, cassava leaves soup is called Saka Saka or Ponda (Immaculate, 2021). The leaves of cassava are utilized as vegetables and the tuberous roots can be processed into over one hundred food types. Certain cassava varieties are mainly grown for industrial use (Fyhri, 2010). In the

rural areas, the roots and young leaves are utilized as a vegetable. Cassava “mash”, fufu, is widely consumed by pounding and sieving cassava to make flour which is then put into hot water and other cassava produce.

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*) belongs to the pea and beans family and is a legume. Groundnut is rich in oil and protein, and has a high energy value (Nautiyal et al., 2002). It can be eaten raw, roasted or cooked and the flour is an ingredient in many foods. Groundnut can be used in the preparation of groundnut soup with warm garri. Groundnut soup is mostly cooked by Northerners and some parts of Southern Nigeria (Nautiyal et al., 2002). Groundnut is important in vegetarian diets because of the protein it contains. It provides 13 different vitamins, especially A, the B group, C and E, along with 26 essential trace minerals, including calcium, iron, zinc and boron, and dietary fibre (Nautiyal et al., 2002). Groundnut is a rich source of fat ranging from 36 to 54% (Asibu, 2008). Groundnuts and groundnut butter are energy-rich and nutritious foods, providing a valuable supply of a wide range of vitamins, minerals and dietary fibre (Jennette, 2003).

Beans (*Parkia biglobosa*) are a tropical legume plant and have been used as a staple in the diet, and the health benefits derived from them have been well recognized. Beans are a strong, plant-based source of protein, fibre and iron that offer many health benefits (Kathy et al., 2023). Beans are nutrient-dense in that the amount of nutrients provided per calorie is particularly high. They are packed with protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, and are low in fat. They are rich in lignans, which may play a role in preventing osteoporosis, heart disease, and certain cancers (Maria, 2008). Vegetables, including legumes/beans are nutrient-dense, low in kilojoules, and are a good source of minerals and vitamins (such as magnesium, vitamin C and folate), dietary fibre and a range of phytochemicals including carotenoids (Darrell et al., 2008).

This study was aimed to determine the nutritional and phytochemical components of mature and young leaves of cassava (*M. esculenta*), groundnut (*A. hypogea*) and beans (*P. biglobosa*) so as to ascertain the possibility of utilizing them as vegetables in traditional Nigerian soups.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Materials

The leaves of plants screened in this investigation were collected from a multiple farming farmland that grows cassava, beans, groundnut, and garden egg located at Ekrejeta, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria with an agroecological zone within the coordinates 5.7894° N and 6.1023° E.

Samples Extraction

The method used for the extraction of the samples was that of Marinova (2005). Samples weighing 0.5g respectively were ground using a mortar and pestle. All samples were homogenized with 50ml distilled water and transferred to test tubes. Then, the mixtures were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 4,000 rpm. The supernatants were collected and used for the determinations.

Assay for Soluble Protein Content

The protein content of each sample was determined by means of the Biuret Method as described by Gornal et al. (2000) with some modifications. 1.5ml of the biuret reagent was added to 0.5ml of each of the three different formulations in their respective test tubes and thoroughly mixed. Thereafter, the test tubes were left to stand for 30 minutes at 37°C and then the absorbance of the samples was determined in the spectrophotometer at 540nm wavelength against reagent blank.

Estimation of Soluble Sugar (Phenol Sulphuric Acid Reagent method)

Five milliliters each of the plant leaf extract was homogenized with 10ml of 80% ethanol. Then each homogenate was centrifuged at 2000rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatants were collected separately. To 1ml of alcoholic extract, 1ml of 5% phenol solution was added and mixed. Five milliliters of 96% sulphuric acid was also added. This was done in triplicate. Each tube was gently agitated during the addition of the acid and then allowed to stand in a water bath at 25°C for 20 minutes. The optical density of the characteristic yellow-orange colour thus developed was measured at 490nm in a spectrophotometer. Simultaneously, a standard curve was prepared by using a known concentration of glucose. The amount of sugar was expressed as mg/g (Dubois et al., 2002).

Determination of Total Protein

The method used for the determination of total protein was that of Lowry et al. (2002). Five milliliters of the sample was mixed with 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 in a digestion flask. Copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate ($CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$) was added to catalyze the reaction and then heated under a fume cupboard until a clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was diluted to 100ml in a volumetric flask, filtered, and used for the analysis. Ten milliliters of the diluted solution was mixed with an equal volume of 45% NaOH solution in a Kjeldahl distillation apparatus. The mixture was added into 10ml of 4% basic acid containing three drops of mixed indicator (bromocresol green and methyl red). A total of 50ml distillate was collected and titrated against 0.02N EDTA from green to a deep red endpoint. A reagent blank was also digested, distilled, and titrated. The nitrogen content, hence the protein content, was calculated thus:

$$\% \text{Protein} = \%N_2 \times 6.25$$
$$\%N_2 = \frac{(T - B) \times N \times 1.4 \times V_t}{W \times V_a}$$

Where:

- W = weight of sample analyzed (5ml)
- N = normality of titrant (0.002N H_2SO_4)
- V_t = total digest volume (100ml)
- V_a = volume of digest analyzed (10ml)
- T = sample titre value
- B = blank titre value

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

The scavenging effect on nitric oxide (NO) radical was measured according to the method of Marcocci et al. (2000). One milliliter of the leaf extract was added in the test tube to 1ml of sodium nitroprusside solution (25ml) and the tubes incubated at $37^\circ C$ for 2 hours. An aliquot (1ml) of the incubation solution was removed and diluted with 0.6ml of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide in 5% H_3PO_4 and 0.1% naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride). The absorbance of the chromophore formed was immediately read at 570nm against distilled water as blank with catechin (500g) used as standard.

The results were expressed as percentage radical scavenging activity (RSA):

$$\%RSA = \frac{\text{Abs. of Control} - \text{Abs. of sample}}{\text{Abs. of Control}} \times 100$$

Quantitative Determination of Saponin

The method used for the determination of saponin was that of Peny et al. (2005). Five grams of the leaf samples were pulverized and placed in a conical flask and 50ml of 20% aqueous ethanol added. The samples were stirred at a constant temperature of $55^\circ C$ for 12 hours. Thereafter, the samples were filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper and the residue re-extracted with another 100ml of 2% ethanol. The extracts were combined and reduced to 40ml by heating in a water bath at $55^\circ C$. The purification process was repeated two more times. Six grams of NaCl were added to adjust the pH of the solution to 4.5 (confirmed with a pH meter). The solution was shaken with 30ml portion of n-butanol, extracted and washed twice with 10ml of aqueous NaCl. They were dried to constant weight, and the saponin extracted was shaken and expressed as a percentage:

$$\%Saponin = \frac{\text{Weight of Residue}}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Alkaloid Determination

Alkaloid content was determined gravimetrically (Sreexidya and Mehrotra 2003). One gram of leaf was dispersed in 10ml of 10% acetic acid in methanol. The suspension was shaken and allowed to stand for 4 hours before it was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to a quarter of its original volume before concentrated ammonium hydroxide (30%) was added dropwise to precipitate the alkaloids. A pre-weighed filter paper was used to filter the precipitate and it was then washed with ammonium hydroxide solution (1%). The filter paper with alkaloids precipitate was dried at $60^\circ C$ until a constant weight was obtained. The content of alkaloid was determined by the difference in the filter paper and expressed as g/100g DW.

Determination of Tannin

Tannins were determined using the method of Dawra et al. (1998). Zero point two grams of each sample was weighed into a beaker. Each was soaked with a

solvent mixture (80ml of acetone and 20ml of glacial acid) for 5 hours to extract tannin. The filtrates were removed and samples were filtered through a double filter paper to obtain the filtrate. Catechin was used as a standard solution. The absorbances of the standard solution as well as that of the filtrates were read at 750nm on a spectrophotometer.

$$\text{Conc. of Samples} = \frac{A_{\text{Sample}} \times \text{Conc. of std.}}{A_{\text{Std.}}}$$

RESULTS

The results obtained from the quantitative analyses of soluble protein, soluble sugar, total protein, nitric oxide radical scavenging assay, saponin, alkaloid, and tannin from the three investigated vegetable leaves are presented in the figures below.

Assay for Soluble Protein Content

The results of the quantitative analysis revealed that soluble protein was present in all the vegetable plant leaves investigated; six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest mean value (0.24g/g FW) compared to that of the matured cassava leaves (0.19g/g FW) (Figure 1). Two weeks old groundnut leaves and matured groundnut leaves have the same mean value (0.18g/g FW) while two weeks old beans leaves have a lower mean value compared to that of the matured beans leaves (Figure 1). This revealed that six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest soluble protein content.

Figure 1: Soluble Protein Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Estimation of Soluble Sugar

From the results, the soluble sugar of the six weeks old cassava leaves is slightly higher than the matured

cassava leaves. The mature groundnut leaves have a slight higher mean value (0.07g/g FW) than the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.06g/g FW) while the two weeks old beans leaves (0.04g/g FW) have a higher mean value than the matured beans leaves (0.02g/g FW). This showed that six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest soluble sugar content (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Soluble Sugar Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Determination of Total Protein

The total protein content of the matured cassava leaves have a higher mean value (36.69%) compared to that of the six weeks old cassava leaves (34.86%). The two weeks old groundnut leaves have a higher total protein value (17.96%) than the matured groundnut leaves (15.96%) while the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (3.82%) than the two weeks old beans leaves (2.82%). This showed cassava leaves have the highest total protein content (Figure 3).

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

As seen, nitric oxide radical scavenging activity of the six weeks old cassava leaves (2.25%) is higher than the matured cassava leaves (2.18%). Although the two weeks old groundnut leaves (2.00%) are slightly higher than the matured groundnut leaves (1.91%), the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (2.13%) than the two weeks old beans leaves (1.98%) (Figure 4). This revealed that the six weeks old cassava leaves have the highest nitric oxide radical scavenging assay.

Figure 3: Total Protein Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Figure 5: Saponin Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Figure 4: Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

have a higher mean value (0.04g/100g) than the two weeks old beans leaves (0.02g/100g) (Figure 6). This showed that the matured beans leaves have the highest alkaloid content. Alkaloids act on a diversity of metabolic systems in humans and other animals; they almost uniformly invoke a bitter taste (Rhoades et al., 2000).

Figure 6: Alkaloid Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Quantitative Determination of Saponin

The saponin content of the matured cassava leaves have a higher mean value (0.21g/g FW) compared to that of the six weeks old cassava leaves (0.15g/g FW). The matured groundnut leaves have a higher saponin value (0.14g/g FW) than the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.11g/g FW) while the matured beans leaves have a higher mean value (0.18g/g FW) than the two weeks old beans leaves (0.16g/g FW) (Figure 5). This showed that the matured cassava leaves have the highest saponin content among all the leaves investigated.

Alkaloid Determination

The alkaloid content of the six weeks old cassava leaves is higher than the matured cassava leaves. The two weeks old groundnut leaves have a higher mean value (0.02g/100g) than the matured groundnut leaves (0.01g/100g) while the matured beans leaves

Determination of Tannin

The tannin content of the matured cassava leaves (0.04g/g FW) is higher than the six weeks old cassava leaves (0.02g/g FW). Matured groundnut leaves have a higher amount of tannin (0.05g/g FW) compared to that of the two weeks old groundnut leaves (0.04g/g FW), while that of the matured beans leaves have a high tannin content (0.05g/g FW) compared to the two weeks old beans leaves (0.04g/g FW) (Figure 7). This revealed that matured beans leaves have the highest tannin content.

Figure 7: Tannin Content of Cassava, Groundnut, and Beans Leaves

Discussion

The soluble protein, soluble sugar, and nitric oxide radical scavenging concentrations are higher in the young cassava leaves followed by the matured cassava leaves. A study by Ravindran and Ravindran (2010) on cassava leaves during different stages of maturity reported a decrease in solubility in protein and carbohydrate contents from young to mature leaves respectively. Hence their high nutritive value may probably account for their use in catalyzing metabolic reactions while polysaccharides are long carbohydrate molecules of monosaccharide units joined together by glycosidic bonds and serve as a source of energy. The high soluble sugar content of the six weeks old cassava leaves could therefore be used as a source of energy. In humans, nitric oxide radical is an important cellular signaling molecule involved in many physiological and pathological processes (Moncada et al., 2004). This implies that six weeks old cassava leaves is a powerful vasodilator with a short half-life of a few seconds in the blood when used.

For the groundnut leaves, soluble protein, soluble sugar, and total protein concentrations have high nutritional value compared to that of beans leaves and serve as a great source of protein (Shalini et al., 2015). This is an indication that these vegetables have a good amount of nutrients.

The saponin and tannin content of the matured cassava leaves have higher mean values compared to that of the young cassava leaves. Alkaloid of the young cassava leaves is higher than the matured cassava leaves. According to research, cassava leaves contain a high concentration of phytochemical

components like saponin, alkaloid, and tannins (Babalola and Ahmed, 2005).

The matured groundnut and beans leaves have higher saponin, alkaloid, and tannin concentrations than the young leaves, except for young groundnut leaves which have a slightly higher mean value than the matured groundnut leaves. This work is in agreement with that of Chelangat and Mukono (2023).

This showed that the bioactive non-nutrient plant compounds in vegetable plant foods have complementary and overlapping mechanisms of action, including modulation of detoxification enzymes, scavenging of oxidative agents, stimulation of the immune system, regulation of gene expression in cell proliferation and apoptosis, hormone metabolism, and antibacterial and antiviral effects (Dragsted et al., 2000). The results of the quantitative analysis of these plants showed that all of the plant leaves contained varying proportions according to the nutritive and phytochemical properties in them.

Conclusion

This study showed the determination of the nutritional and phytochemical components of mature and immature leaves of cassava (*M. esculenta*), groundnut (*A. hypogea*), and beans (*P. biglobosa*) so as to ascertain the possibility of utilizing them as vegetables in traditional Nigerian soups and incorporating them into other dishes. Though the analysed components of the vegetables are not enough to satisfy the recommended dietary allowances (RDAs), they can be used as sources of additional organic nutrients in our daily traditional meals.

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Phytoremediation of Cd, Pb, and Ni-co-contaminated soil of the Niger Delta by using Local Maize (*Zea mays*) plant

TUBOTU, K.F.^{1*}; AGBAIRE, P.O.¹; AKPORHONOR, E.E.¹; ODAGWE, A.A.²

¹Department of Chemistry, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: +2348027538882; tubotuken@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Phytoremediation is an innovative, cost-effective technology that uses plants to extract metals from polluted soils. Experiments were conducted using *Zea mays* plants grown in soils contaminated with varying levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni. The results indicated that rising soil heavy metal concentrations decreased plant height, weight, and chlorophyll content. Plants grown in soil with the highest levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni (20, 120, and 60 mg/kg) showed the highest amounts of Cd (11.71 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt in shoots), Pb (29.60 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt in shoots), and Ni (38.70 mg/kg Dwt in roots and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt in shoots). As the soil's metal levels rose, the bioconcentration factor (BCF) and translocation factor (TF) values declined. In 80% of cases, Ni had BCF values over 1, while Cd exceeded 1 in only 20%, and Pb had none. All metals had TF values below 1. Our findings indicate that *Z. mays* primarily employs phytostabilization to remediate these elements, supported by high BCF values, particularly for Ni, and low TF values across all examined treatments, suggesting minimal metal translocation from roots to shoots.

Keywords: Bioconcentration factor, Translocation factor, phytostabilization, metals, physicochemical properties

Introduction

The rapid growth of the global population, urbanization, and industrialization have led to the contamination of millions of hectares of land with heavy metals, affecting over 50% of contaminated sites worldwide (Behnisch et al., 2022; Elehinafe et al., 2022; Gill et al., 2023). These metals can be from natural sources or anthropogenic activities like emissions from waste incinerators, residues from mining and military activities, the smelting industry, use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, burning fossil fuels, and municipal trash (Andresen & Küpper, 2013; Zulfiqar et al., 2022). Heavy metals in soils at high concentrations negatively affect crop health and productivity, disrupt cellular structures, and cause oxidative stress (Rashid et al., 2023). They may also make their way into the food chain, putting people at risk of developing cancer (Gill et al., 2023). According to national and international organisations, certain metal concentrations in soil and plants have surpassed allowable limits, endangering both human health and the environment (Alengebawy et al., 2021; Behnisch et al., 2022). Several heavy metal pollutants are frequently found in soil, including Cd,

Pb, and Ni. These metals, like others, are difficult to break down into innocuous byproducts like carbon dioxide, therefore they must usually be removed from contaminated soils (Wuana & Okieimen, 2011).

There are multiple approaches to addressing soils contaminated with heavy metals. Although there are traditional methods like excavation, burning, and chemical washing, they can be quite costly, require a lot of manual labour, and may release harmful secondary pollutants that can negatively impact biological processes and the environment (Ding et al., 2023). Due to the current circumstances, there is a growing need for a solution that is both affordable and eco-friendly. Phytoremediation is an effective and eco-friendly strategy that utilises plants to reduce metal toxicity. It involves the transportation of ions to shoots and their elimination from roots, resulting in a cost-effective solution. Phytoremediation involves the utilisation of plants to absorb, sequester, and detoxify contaminants, with a specific focus on heavy metals (Ashraf et al., 2019). Several mechanisms are involved in phytoremediation: phytoextraction, phytostimulation, phytovolatilization, rhizofiltration, and phytostabilization. Whereas phytostimulation seeks to improve plant growth for greater metal

absorption, phytoextraction uses plants to gather metals from the soil. Rhizofiltration is the process by which roots remove metals from water; phytovolatilization is the process by which plants release metals into the atmosphere. Finally, phytostabilization aims to immobilise metals in soil or plant roots, thereby limiting their mobility (Ashraf et al., 2019; Kanwar et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2024). The useful implementation of phytoremediation methods depends on the choice of plant species with suitable characteristics for certain soil contaminants. Sunflower, Indian mustard, water hyacinth, willow, and Indian pennywort are among the more than 400 plant species that have been identified as heavy metal hyperaccumulators; nevertheless, because of the way that heavy metals affect plant cellular processes, most growing plants are not hyperaccumulators for heavy metals (Shrivastava et al., 2019). Since plant capacities to collect heavy metals vary, the choice of plant species for phytoextraction of heavy metals is mostly determined by the biomass and tolerance capacity of the chosen plant (Peng et al., 2021; Zulfiqar et al., 2022).

Maize (*Zea mays*) an indigenous annual plant belonging to the Poaceae grass family, plays a vital role in Nigerian agriculture and culinary practices. Originally from the Americas, Maize thrives in the Niger Delta region, where it can grow to heights exceeding 10 feet under optimal soil conditions. This crop is known for its rapid growth and high biomass production, offering promise in soil remediation by reducing heavy metal concentrations. The plant's photosynthetic efficiency and nutrient profile significantly influence its growth rate and biomass output (Atta et al., 2023). Previous research has indicated Maize's notable resilience to heavy metal exposure (Irfan et al., 2021; Ni et al., 2022; Tariq, 2022). But, while Maize (*Zea mays*) thrives in a variety of soil types, not all soils in the Niger Delta are equally conducive to its growth (Anoliefo et al., 2006; Egobueze et al., 2019). This study is therefore carried out to: (i) evaluate an indigenous Maize variety to see if it is naturally adapted to sandy soil conditions and capable of metal uptake. (ii) determine the ability of local Maize to accumulate Cd, Pb, and Ni without external amendments like fertilizer and (iii) investigate the impact of phytoremediation on some selected soil properties and the effect of Cd, Pb, and Ni-co-contaminated soil on the total biomass of Maize.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location of Study

The research was conducted at Delta State University (DELSU), located in Abraka, Nigeria, between March and May in the year 2023. Located at latitude 6° 30' 59.99" N and longitude 3° 23' 5.99" W, the campus is roughly 29 metres above sea level. Abraka is located around 49 miles northeast of Warri and experiences a tropical wet and dry climate.

Preparation of soil and conducting experiments in pots

A soil sample was obtained from DELSU (Campus 3) at a depth of 0-20 cm beside a coal-tarred road adjacent to an agricultural region. The soil was air-dried by exposure to air and subsequently filtered through a stainless-steel screen with a 2 mm mesh size. A pot experiment was conducted in a rain-protected net-house where *Zea mays* plants were cultivated for sixty days, being subjected to natural sunlight. Cadmium acetate, lead sulphate, and nickel sulphate served as the corresponding sources of Cd, Pb, and Ni. Varying quantities of these compounds were mixed in containers along with soil (2kg) and distilled water. Five treatment levels (n = 3) of Cd, Pb, and Ni (P treatments) and control groups (CT) were part of the trial. The P-group included Cd, Pb, Ni, and plants; the control group had unspiked soil with plants. Table 1 offers specifications of the metal addition levels to the soil.

Table 1: Cd, Pb, and Ni concentration per treatment pot (mg/kg)

Metals	CT	P1	P2	P3	P4
Cd	0	5	10	15	20
Pb	0	30	60	90	120
Ni	0	15	30	45	60

The pots were put in a dark room for 14 days, with tap water added to maintain them at 75% field capacity. Three *Zea mays* seedlings were transplanted to each container after ten days of growth in fertiliser-free, unspiked soil. Two or three times a week, the pots were watered and inspected. The experiment ended with an examination of soil parameters including pH, EC, TOC, TN, Av. P., and texture.

Analysis

Physicochemical Properties and heavy metals of soil

The soil sample was tested chemically using approved procedures. Phosphorus and total nitrogen concentrations were assessed using the Bray 1 and Kjeldahl methods, respectively (Bray & Kurtz, 1945; Bremner & Bremner, 1996). The total organic carbon (TOC) concentration of the soil was assessed by the Walkley-Black method (Nelson & Sommers, 1996). The texture of the soil was measured by the hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962). A 1:1 weight-to-volume soil-to-water extract had its pH measured with a pH meter. The metal content of 0.5 g of air-dried, sieved soil sample was determined by utilising the method given by Paunović et al. (2019) using microwave-digested aqua regia (HCl, 36% and HNO₃, 65%). The resulting solution was filtered and diluted before the levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Perkin Elmer 700, Boston, MA, USA). The test soil has a sandy texture, an average total organic carbon concentration of 0.19 %, and physicochemical parameters of 6.75 pH and 1.40 EC micro/Sm. Besides, the soil contained 6.95, 35.55, and 20.80 mg/kg on average for total Cd, Pb, and Ni. Similar baseline values for metals in soils have been reported in other studies around the Niger Delta (Tubotu & Agbaire, 2022).

Harvesting, preparing, and analysing plants

The plants were methodically pulled out of the experiment, cleaned and rinsed with deionized water, and then their roots and shoots were separated. Following note of the plant heights and fresh biomass, the roots and shoots were dried in an oven at 70 °C for 24 hours to calculate the dry biomass. After that, the metal contents in the plant tissues were analysed. For the analysis of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in plant root and shoot, a solution of hydrochloric acid and hydrogen nitrate in a 3:1 volume ratio (HCl/HNO₃, 3:1 v/v) was used to digest 0.5 g of the sifted plant material after it had been powdered. The Cd, Pb, and Ni concentrations in the resulting digests were determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) (Alaboudi et al., 2018). The study examined the chlorophyll levels in *Zea mays* by extracting it with acetone and measuring it using spectrophotometry. The quantities

of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll were measured using equations provided by Kumar et al. (2018): total chlorophyll : 20.2(A645) + 8.02(A663), chlorophyll a : 12.7(A663) 2.69(A645) and chlorophyll b : 22.9(A645) 4.68(A663).

Factors of bioconcentration and translocation

By use of bioconcentration and translocation factors, as described by Takarina and Pin (2017) and Usman et al. (2019), the study examined *Zea mays*' capacity to absorb and disseminate cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), and nickel (Ni) from the soil using the following equations:

$$BCF = \frac{C_{root}}{C_{soil}} \quad (1)$$

$$TF = \frac{C_{shoot}}{C_{root}} \quad (2)$$

$$BCF_{shoot} = \frac{C_{shoot}}{C_{soil}} \quad (3)$$

where C_{soil} , C_{root} , and C_{shoot} are the metal concentrations (mg/kg) in the soil, root, and shoot, respectively.

Should the bioconcentration factor be less than one (BCF < 1), soil heavy metal concentrations exceed plant absorption. Larger absorption by plants or crops is indicated by BCF values larger than one (BCF > 1). Trace metals are detected predominantly in the biomass of the roots of plants with a translocation factor (TF) less than 1 but in the shoot biomass of plants with a TF > 1.

Statistical Analysis

This paper used Excel 2016 and IBM SPSS Statistics 27 for statistical analysis. The data provided are the mean ± standard deviation of three independent replicates (n = 3). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data, and Tukey's HSD post-hoc test found significant mean differences. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$. Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to assess the relationships between plant characteristics, metal concentrations in roots and shoots, and soil physicochemical factors.

Table 2: Selected soil physicochemical properties at the end of the experiment

	pH	EC	TN	SOC	Av. P	Cd	Pb
CT	6.25 ± 0.04a	1.41 ± 0.3e	0.71 ± 0.01a	0.91 ± 0.01a	29.74 ± 0.10a	2.69 ± 0.04e	18.11 ± 0.00e
P1	5.80 ± 0.02b	2.60 ± 0.11d	0.58 ± 0.01b	0.81 ± 0.01b	26.92 ± 0.39b	4.00 ± 0.27d	29.70 ± 1.68d
P2	5.00 ± 0.30c	3.94 ± 0.04c	0.51 ± 0.01c	0.48 ± 0.00c	26.31 ± 0.10c	7.81 ± 0.10c	43.57 ± 0.52c
P3	4.00 ± 0.09d	5.16 ± 0.18b	0.50 ± 0.02c	0.42 ± 0.01d	13.63 ± 0.20d	9.89 ± 0.22b	58.53 ± 1.02b
P4	3.01 ± 0.04e	6.40 ± 0.12a	0.46 ± 0.02d	0.42 ± 0.01d	12.11 ± 0.10e	14.88 ± 0.59b	82.91 ± 1.03a

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Results

Physicochemical Properties of the Soil Following Corn Harvest

Following the Maize harvest, Table ?? displays the soil's physicochemical parameters. Significant variability in pH was observed across all treatments (p < 0.05). The control soil exhibited the highest pH at 6.25, while the soil treated with 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and 60 mg/kg Ni (P4 soil) showed the lowest pH at 3.01. Control soil had the highest total organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus levels. Higher metal concentrations in treatment soils decreased pH, organic carbon, total nitrogen, and available phosphorus, but enhanced electrical conductivity post-harvest. Among the treatments, P4 soil had the highest electrical conductivity. The control soil had the lowest concentrations of bioavailable Cd, Pb, and Ni.

Concentration of Heavy Metals in the Soil After Maize Harvest

Table ?? displays the average concentrations of soil Cd, Pb, and Ni in both the control and P pots after 60 days of planting. Compared to the initial soil samples, the results indicate a decrease in the three metals in the control, P1, P2, P3, and P4. P4 exhibited significantly higher metal concentrations (14.88, 82.91, and 39.81 mg/kg Cd, Pb, and Ni, respectively) compared to the control group, with a p-value of less than 0.05. The soil's metal concentrations increased in proportion to the spike concentrations.

Plant Development and Biomass

As the soil's Cd, Pb, and Ni levels climbed, maize shoot length and total biomass diverged significantly

from the control (Figure 1). In P1, plant height dropped by 8.59%; in P2, by 14.30%; and in P3 and P4, by 25.71%. Regarding biomass (Figure 2), the fresh and dry weights of plants in the Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contaminated growth media (P1 to P4) were substantially lower than the control by 26.32% to 57.71% and 22.48% to 72.14% in the root, respectively, and by 17.10% to 39.74% and 40.90% to 68.27% in the shoot. Growing in the growth media tainted with the largest quantities of Cd, Pb, and Ni (P4), the weights of the plants reduced most dramatically (P<0.001). The results confirm the unfavorable association between higher levels of Cd, Pb, and Ni and plant development markers.

Figure 1: Zea mays shoot development in soil as impacted by metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni). Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Figure 2: Effects of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) on soil-grown *Zea mays* biomass. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P \leq 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Figure 3: Effects of metals (Ni, Pb, and Cd) on soil-grown *Zea mays* chlorophyll concentration. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P \leq 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Contents of Chlorophyll

The soil's contamination with Cd, Pb, and Ni lowered the quantities of Chl-a and Chl-b; control plants had higher values. Concerning the total chlorophyll (t-Chl) levels of the plants, significant decreases were also observed (Figure 3). Plants treated with 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and 60 mg/kg Ni had the lowest levels of Chl-a, Chl-b, and t-Chl. All the plants proved, on average, to have more Chl b than Chl a. As the chlorophyll a/b value was less than 1.00, Cd, Pb, and Ni stress impaired the plant's photosynthetic resilience (Table ??). As the amount of metal in the soil grew, all chlorophyll contents fell in a dose-dependent way.

Distribution of Cd,Pb, and Ni in Tissues of Plants

As the metal concentrations in the treated soils increased in relation to the control, so did the metal concentrations in *Zea mays* roots and shoots (Figure 4). Plants grown on soil treated with co-contamination of 20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb, and

60 mg/kg Ni (or P4 treatment) increased their Cd (11.71 and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt), Pb (29.60 and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt), and Ni (38.70 and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt) contents in their roots and shoots, respectively, to the highest significant ($P < 0.001$) levels. The control group of plants exhibited the lowest levels of Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), and Nickel (Ni) in both their roots and shoots. Notably, a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the concentrations of these elements between the roots and shoots of plants grown in spiked pots compared to those in the control group. The roots were identified as the primary site for the accumulation of Cd, Pb, and Ni in plants across various treatment soils, as indicated by the distribution of concentrations of these elements in plant tissues (refer to Figure 4). The sequence of Cd, Pb, and Ni concentrations in different plant compartments was determined to be roots $\hat{}$ stems.

Translocation Factor (TF) and Bioconcentration Factor (BCF) of Cd, Pb and Ni

As soil metal levels increased, the bioconcentration factor for each of Cd, Pb, and Ni decreased. *Zea mays* BCF followed the pattern Ni $\hat{}$ Cd $\hat{}$ Pb, as Table ?? makes rather clear. From 1.20 (at 5 mg/kg Cd, 30 mg/kg Pb and 15 mg/kg Ni co-contamination level) to 0.79 (20 mg/kg Cd, 120 mg/kg Pb and 60 mg/kg Ni co-contamination level), the Cd root BCF values steadily fell. The other metals followed similar patterns (Pb = 0.51 to 0.36; Ni = 2.00 to 0.97). Cd had the one larger-than-1 root-BCF value in P1 (BCF $\hat{}$ 1). Except for P4, Ni root BCF values were more than 1 (BCF $\hat{}$ 1) in every treated soil and the control. All shoot BCF values for the metals were less than 1 except for Ni in the control (1.14).

Maximum TF values were found in the control. Generally, when soil metal concentrations increased, the TF values of the metals decreased (P $\hat{}$ P2 $\hat{}$ P3 $\hat{}$ P4): Cd TF decreased from 0.33 to 0.22; Pb from 0.49 to 0.31; and Ni from 0.34 to 0.28. The recorded data makes it quite clear that roots had higher BCF than shoots and that, in all treatments, there was very little metal translocated from root to shoot (TF $\hat{}$ 1) (Table ??).

Pearson Correlation Analysis

Tables 5, along with supplementary tables 1 and 2, provide insight into the Pearson correlations among plant features, metal concentrations in plant tissues (roots and shoots), and soil physicochemical parameters. Parameters such as shoot fresh weight (SFW), root fresh weight (RFW), shoot dry weight (SDW), root dry weight (RDW), shoot length (SL), chlorophyll a (Chl-a), chlorophyll b (Chl-b), total chlorophyll content (t-Chl), and metal-related traits (e.g., Cd, Pb, Ni concentrations in plant tissues and soil) displayed significant correlations. Notably, Maize plant metal characteristics and soil properties exhibited both positive and negative associations. While all metals (Cd, Pb, Ni) demonstrated negative relationships with plant growth characteristics, strong positive connections were observed between soil physicochemical properties and plant growth traits, except for electrical conductivity and soil metal concentrations as indicated in supplementary tables 1 and 2. article pdfscape lipsum geometry a4paper, total=170mm,257mm, left=20mm, top=20mm

Figure 4: The concentrations of metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in *Zea mays* roots and shoots grown on soil supplemented with a mix of nickel, lead, and cadmium. Mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of $P < 0.05$ is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

Table 3: Cd, Pb, and Ni bioconcentration factors in Maize tissues

	BCF-Root			BCF-Shoot		
	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cd	Pb	Ni
CT	0.88 ± 0.05b	0.27 ± 0.11c	1.31 ± 0.00c	0.76 ± 0.03a	0.22 ± 0.02a	1.14 ± 0.02a
P1	1.20 ± 0.04a	0.51 ± 0.01a	2.00 ± 0.13a	0.40 ± 0.01b	0.25 ± 0.03a	0.38 ± 0.01c
P2	0.86 ± 0.01bc	0.55 ± 0.04a	1.36 ± 0.05b	0.27 ± 0.02c	0.16 ± 0.02b	0.45 ± 0.01b
P3	0.87 ± 0.02bc	0.43 ± 0.01ab	1.14 ± 0.03b	0.23 ± 0.01c	0.14 ± 0.02b	0.32 ± 0.01d
P4	0.79 ± 0.01c	0.36 ± 0.02bc	0.97 ± 0.02c	0.17 ± 0.02d	0.11 ± 0.01b	0.27 ± 0.01e

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by mean values that do not share a common letter.

Table 4: Translocation factors of Cd, Pb, and Ni in Maize tissues

	Cd	Pb	Ni
CT	0.87 ± 0.02a	0.81 ± 0.01a	0.87 ± 0.02a
P1	0.33 ± 0.01b	0.49 ± 0.01b	0.34 ± 0.01b
P2	0.31 ± 0.01b	0.32 ± 0.04c	0.33 ± 0.01b
P3	0.26 ± 0.01c	0.31 ± 0.03c	0.28 ± 0.02c
P4	0.22 ± 0.01d	0.31 ± 0.03c	0.28 ± 0.01c

Mean ± standard deviation; n = 3; statistically significant difference at a level of P < 0.05 is evidenced by the mean values that do not share a common letter.

[1]
[h!]

DISCUSSION

Soil properties can impact heavy metal availability and plant uptake. The test soil of this study is sandy, has low organic carbon and nutrient levels typical of tropical areas like the Niger Delta, and its fertility level can be described as low. The presence of heavy metals in the soil altered the physicochemical properties of the soil, leading to higher EC values and a reduction in pH. This reduction in soil pH, which in turn increases the solubility and plant uptake of metals, indicates that the test soil has a high potential for the transport of metals from the soil solution to the plant.

The results of the current study reveal that Maize growth parameters, including shoot lengths and root and shoot weights, are significantly reduced when exposed to various levels of cadmium, lead, and nickel co-contamination in the growth media (Figures 1 and 2). The deleterious impact is dose-dependent due to Increased hazardous heavy metals (HMs) absorption as metal concentration in the soil increases. The study

also found that the application of cadmium, lead, and nickel co-contamination significantly lowered harvestable biomass, indicating Maize vulnerability to toxicity. In the current study, the longest Maize shoot length was observed in control soil with an average value of 17.5 cm, while the shortest shoot length (13.0 cm) was recorded under P3 and P4 treatments (Fig. 1). Similar findings have been observed in other similar investigations. In a study conducted by Liu et al. (2018), the impact of arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) inoculation and biochar amendment on Maize growth, cadmium (Cd) uptake, and soil Cd speciation in Cd-contaminated soil was investigated. The researchers found that the introduction of 6 mg/kg Cd resulted in a 20.96% reduction in Maize shoot length compared to the control group (Liu et al., 2018). In another study by Coulibaly et al. (2021), where P. maximum was subjected to 2 ppm of Cd, 50 ppm of Ni, and 100 ppm of Pb contaminated soil and uncontaminated soil, for 120 days in a greenhouse, it was observed that the stem height of Panicum maximum was reduced by around 5.11%, 23.30%, and 52.84% in Pb, Cd and Ni contaminated soils

Table 5: Pearson correlations for different plant traits and metals in plant tissues (roots and shoots)

	R-Cd	R-Pb	R-Ni	ST-Cd	ST-Pb	ST-Ni	Chl-a	Chl-b	t-Chl	SL	RFW	SFW
SDW												
R-Cd	1.000											
R-Pb	.952*	1.000										
R-Ni	.974**	.953*	1.000									
ST-Cd	0.749	0.623	0.782	1.000								
ST-Pb	.885*	.934*	0.827	0.373	1.000							
ST-Ni	.940*	.901*	.980**	.882*	0.718	1.000						
Chl-a	-0.872	-.951*	-0.852	-0.366	-.984**	-0.744	1.000					
Chl-b	-0.796	-0.597	-0.782	-.923*	-0.441	-0.838	0.407	1.000				
t-Chl	-.989**	-.968**	-.968**	-0.655	-.930*	-.908*	.928*	0.718	1.000			
SL	-.953*	-.944*	-.984**	-0.675	-0.853	-.935*	.891*	0.716	.970**	1.000		
RFW	-.971**	-.988**	-.955*	-0.599	-.956*	-.887*	.962**	0.634	.992**	.962**	1.000	
SFW	-.943*	-.999**	-.943*	-0.605	-.938*	-.890*	.954*	0.573	.961**	.935*	.985**	1.000
RDW	-.964**	-.988**	-.986**	-0.700	-.884*	-.950*	.913*	0.677	.972**	.977**	.979**	.983**
SDB 1.000	-.921*	-.974**	-.910*	-0.472	-.973**	-0.819	.992**	0.513	.965**	.940*	.987**	.974**

Cd concentration in shoot (ST-Cd) and roots (R-Cd), Pb concentration in shoot (ST-Pb) and roots (R-Pb), Ni concentration in shoot (ST-Ni) and roots (R-Ni); shoot length (SL), chlorophyll a (Chl-a), chlorophyll b (Chl-b), total chlorophyll (t-Chl); shoot fresh weight (SFW), root fresh weight (RFW), shoot dry weight (SDW), and root dry weight (RDW).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

respectively. Heavy metals can generate oxidative stress, damage cell structures, and disrupt metabolic pathways, resulting in stunted development and lower stem height (Rashid et al., 2023; Zulfiqar et al., 2022).

In our study, low biomass production was reported in all the treatments (P1 to P4) compared with control (Figure 2). This reduction implies a deleterious influence of heavy metals on Maize growth. The reduction in biomass compared with the control might potentially be attributable to higher Cd, Pb and Ni uptake as the level of concentrations of the metals in soil increased. In the present study, the fresh and dry weights of plants significantly decreased in the root by 26.32 to 57.71% and 22.48 to 72.14% and in the shoot by 17.10 to 39.74% and 40.90 to 68.27 in the Cd, Pb and Ni co-contaminated growth conditions (P1 to P4) compared with control (Table 2). The results of our investigation are in agreement with similar studies by other researchers. For instance, the addition of 6 mg/kg Cd to soil has been observed to lower the fresh weight of Maize by 21.50% when compared with control (Liu et al., 2018). It may be deduced that exposure to excessive Cd, Pb and Ni may adversely influence plant development and biomass production and these detrimental effects might be further amplified by an increase in the metal concentrations in the growth medium.

Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contamination significantly lowered plant growth and development, potentially due to a decrease in the photosynthetic rate (Asare et al., 2023). The chl-a, chl-b and total chlorophyll content in Maize plants cultivated in the Cd, Pb, and Ni co-contaminated soil compared with the control decreased significantly, with an increase in metal concentrations in the growth medium. This destruction of chlorophyll structure may be due to the substitution of the central Mg^{2+} ion by Cd, Pb, and Ni ions, which may damage the chlorophyll molecule (Bechaieb et al., 2018). As metal concentrations increase in soil, it may accelerate metal uptake, further affecting the detrimental effect of toxicity on chlorophyll content (Chtouki et al., 2021; Ewais, 1997).

Our investigation demonstrates a negative association between plant growth indices, chlorophyll content, and increasing concentrations of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in soil. The higher rate of metal concentrations in soil decreased these metrics

compared to the control. Heavy metal stress impacts plant metabolic activity, hinders photosynthesis, and lowers the uptake of critical nutrients from the soil, leading to decreased plant biomass establishment (Ghori et al., 2019).

Based on the obtained results, *Z. mays* seems to be a tolerant and rapidly growing plant, suitable for phytoremediation due to its fast growth, large root development potential, impressive biomass establishment, and high storage capacity for heavy metals (Daryabeigi Zand & Mühling, 2022).

Metal speciation in soil is crucial in limiting metal uptake by plants. In our investigation, Cd, Pb, and Ni levels in Maize root and shoot systems increased as metal concentrations in soil increased (Figs. 1 and 2). Plants grown in P4 soil had the highest Cd (11.71 and 2.55 mg/kg Dwt), Pb (29.60 and 9.10 mg/kg Dwt), and Ni (38.70 and 10.90 mg/kg Dwt) contents in their roots and shoots, respectively. The study found that *Z. mays* roots are the preferred organ for cadmium, lead and nickel storage, which is consistent with previous research on zinc, copper, and lead (Sagbara et al., 2020). Heavy metals in soil may compete with mineral nutrients for absorption by plant roots. This occurrence may lead to a lack of vital elements such as iron, for plant viability. Furthermore, higher amounts of heavy metals can alter water balance and nutrient digestion, potentially resulting in plant death (Siyar et al., 2020).

Phytoextraction Efficiency of Metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni)

Our findings indicate that *Z. mays* accumulates more Cd, Pb, and Ni in its roots than in its shoots, with roots absorbing more Ni than Cd or Pb. At low Ni concentrations, root BCF values are < 1 , but when Ni concentrations exceed 45 mg/kg, root BCF values drop. Our findings suggest that phytostabilization is the primary mechanism by which *Z. mays* remediates these elements, as the BCF values (particularly for Ni) in most treatments were higher than 1, while the TF values of all metals (Cd, Pb, and Ni) in all examined treatments were less than 1. The results of our study also suggest that *Zea mays*' capacity to translocate heavy metals from roots to shoots diminishes with an increase in soil concentration of these metals. Heavy metals in the soil can impede a plant's capacity to absorb vital nutrients and water by blocking the root apex. This root-level interference may lessen the

plant's capacity to move heavy metals from its roots to its aerial portions, which may affect the plant's general growth and health (Thomas, 2021). There have also been reports of other plants, like *Tetraena qataranse*, being tolerant to Cd, Cr, Cu, and Ni (Usman et al., 2019). article lipsum

Conclusion

This study sought to determine the ability of native *Zea mays* in Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria, to remove Cd, Pb, and Ni from contaminated soil. The acquired data demonstrated that *Zea mays* can collect Cd, Pb, and Ni in its tissues (shoots and roots). However, Ni buildup in plant roots was preferable to Cd and Pb. Ni treatments below 60 mg/kg had a greater BCF value than 1, indicating metal ion absorption. Furthermore, the BCF of Cd showed a similar result at 5 mg/kg, whereas that of Pb for all treatments did not reach 1. Phytostabilization is the primary process by which *Zea mays* remediates soil contaminated with Cd, Pb, and Ni (TF i 1). Additional research is required to explore the phytoremediation performance of *Zea mays* for heavy metals when combined with plant growth boosters in order to maximize the plant's heavy metal removal effectiveness in sandy soils.

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Declarations

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- **Conflict of interest:** None declared
- **Ethical approval:** Not required

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Physiochemical Properties and Biodegradation Potentials of Soil Microbes Isolated from Mechanic Workshops in Benin Metropolis

Udinyiwe, C.O.^{1*} and Omoregie, A.E.¹

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, P.M.B 1154, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: collins.udinyiwe@uniben.edu, +2348062613143

ABSTRACT

The release of used engine oil into the environment is gradually becoming a challenge to our environment. This research was carried out to determine the physiochemical properties and biodegradation potentials of some soil microbes isolated from mechanic workshops in Benin metropolis. The physiochemical properties of the soil samples were investigated according to the methods of Association of Official Analytical Chemists. The microbial analysis was carried out according to standard microbiological and biochemical methods. Results revealed bacterial count ranged from 1.6×10^4 – 3.8×10^4 cfu/g, Hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial counts ranging from 0.4×10^4 – 1.0×10^4 cfu/g. Fungal counts ranging from 0.1×10^4 – 0.7×10^4 cfu/g. The bacteria isolated were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Acinetobacter* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp. and *Klebsiella* spp. The fungi isolates identified were *Trichoderma* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Mucor* spp., *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium* spp. The screening test revealed *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Trichoderma* spp. and *Aspergillus niger* to have biodegradative potentials. Shake flask experiment revealed increased in the turbidity of the mineral salt medium amended with engine oil. The consortium of bacterial and fungal showed better degradation potentials especially with the gradual increase turbidity and reduction in pH. The results suggest that the consortium of the isolates could be used in remediating contaminated soils.

Keywords: Bacteria, Fungi, Optical density, Consortium, Microbes

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution and the presence of complex mixtures of hydrocarbons and other organic compounds, including some organo-metabolic constituents used to lubricate the metallic parts of an automobile engine, have become major challenges today in the environment (Udeani et al., 2009). When spent engine oil enters the environment, it causes alterations in some soil properties, microbial activities, and influences the concentration of organic matter, nitrogen, magnesium, and heavy metals in the soil (Okonokhua et al., 2007). Prolonged exposure to high oil concentrations may cause the development of liver or kidney disease, possible damage to the bone marrow, and an increased risk of cancer (Mishra et al., 2001). Used engine oil pollutes the environment and constitutes a potential threat to humans, animals, and vegetation (Edewor et al., 2004; Adelowo et al., 2006). Used motor oil can cause great damage to sensitive environments and soil microorganisms. Substantial volumes of soil have been contaminated by used

oil in many countries, especially industrialized nations. Large amounts of used engine oil are released into the environment when the oil from motor cars, motorbikes, and generators is changed and disposed of into gutters, water drains, open vacant plots, and farmlands—a common practice by motor and generator mechanics (Odjegba and Sadiq, 2002). The presence of spent engine oil in the soil creates a chemical impurity which contributes to chronic hazards resulting in mutagenicity and environmental risk (Blodgette, 2001). Various contaminants, such as used engine oil and heavy metals, have been found to alter soil biochemistry, including changes in soil microbial properties such as pH, O₂, and nutrient availability (Odjegba and Sadiq, 2002). Spent engine oil contains metals and heavy polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), which could contribute to chronic hazards, including mutagenicity and carcinogenicity (Boonchan et al., 2000). As it is inevitable for the efficient and effective functioning of automobile engines, soil contamination with used engine oil is becoming one of the major

environmental problems (Mandri and Lin, 2006), mainly due to uncontrolled disposal, particularly in developing economies. The widespread ability of microorganisms to assimilate these hydrocarbons is of great significance, and when it occurs in the natural environment, the process is known as biodegradation. Hydrocarbons, including PAHs, have long been recognized as substrates supporting microbial growth. A wide range of hydrocarbon utilizers (HCUs) found to be useful in the soil includes species such as *Pseudomonas*, *Rhodococcus*, *Mycobacterium*, *Bacillus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Providencia*, *Flavobacter*, *Corynebacterium*, and *Streptococcus* (Bhattacharya et al., 2002). Other organisms, such as fungi, are also capable of degrading hydrocarbons in engine oil to a certain extent, but they take longer periods to grow compared to their bacterial counterparts (Prenafeta-Boldu et al., 2001). The aim of this study was to determine the physiochemical properties and biodegradation potentials of soil microbes isolated from mechanic workshops in Benin metropolis, Nigeria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Sites

The five locations in Benin City metropolis used in this study were Uwelu around the mechanic workshops, Evbareke around the mechanic workshops, Igun around the mechanic workshops, Ugbowo around the mechanic workshops opposite University of Benin, and Oluku around the mechanic workshop close to the Bypass.

Sample Collection

Composite soil samples from designated mechanic workshops in the five areas of study were collected in a sterile polyethylene bag using a sterile spatula from the edge of a motor oil-stained patch in the workshop by scooping to about 5 cm. The samples were immediately transported to the laboratory for analyses.

Physiochemical Properties of the Soil Samples

The physiochemical properties of the soil samples were investigated according to the methods of A.O.A.C. (2000).

Figure 1: Map showing GPS coordinates of soil samples collected around the study sites.

Bacterial Enumeration

One gram (1 g) of the contaminated soil was weighed using an analytical balance (Model no AX423/E, USA Ohaus Cooperation) into test tubes containing 9 ml distilled water, and 10-fold dilution was carried out to 10^{-3} dilution. One milliliter (1 ml) of each dilution was inoculated into nutrient agar and potato dextrose agar for bacteria and fungi using the pour plate method. The plates for bacteria were incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs, while the plates for fungi were incubated at 30°C for 48 hrs. Hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria counts (HUB) were enumerated by inoculating 1 ml of aliquot of 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} into mineral salt agar plates prepared according to Chessbrough (2000). The plates were incubated for 7 days, and the discrete colonies were counted.

Characterization and Identification of Bacterial and Fungal Isolates

The bacteria and fungi isolates were characterized based on preliminary cultural and biochemical characteristics. Identification of the isolates was performed according to the method of Chessbrough (2000). The pure cultures were maintained in slants in McCartney bottles containing tryptic soy broth-glycerol (TSB-glycerol). They were stored at 4°C until required for analysis.

Screening Test for Biodegradation Potential of Engine Oil Contaminated Soil

The isolates were screened for the ability to utilize spent engine oil using mineral salt medium. Nine

milliliters (9 ml) of mineral salt medium were dispensed into six test tubes for bacteria and five test tubes for fungi. In each of the test tubes, one milliliter of spent engine oil was added as the main source of carbon. Thereafter, all the test tubes were inoculated with 0.5 MacFarland (10^8 cfu/ml) of an isolate previously grown. All the test tubes were incubated at 30°C for 7 days, after which the turbidity of the solution was checked to determine the potentials of the isolates. Those with high degradation potentials were utilized, while those with poor degradation potential were eliminated from the experiment (Somari et al., 2022).

Determination of the Ability of the Bacterial and Fungal Isolates to Utilize Spent Engine Oil from Contaminated Soil Using Shake Flask Method

A known volume of 98 ml of the mineral salt medium was transferred into 250 ml conical flasks followed by 1 ml spent engine oil before sterilization. Thereafter, all the conical flasks except for the control sample were inoculated with 0.5 MacFarland (10^8 cfu/ml) of a twenty-four (24 h) culture. The utilization of the engine oil was monitored at three-day intervals for a total of twelve days. The optical density and pH readings were monitored at 3-day intervals for 12 days. The optical density was measured with a M501 UV-Vis Camspec Spectrophotometer using 600 nm, while the pH was measured with a pH meter (Onyeiwu et al., 2022; Veerapagu et al., 2019).

Statistics

The data were subjected to One-way ANOVA using SPSS for various parameters. Further tests, such as Duncan's multiple range test, were carried out to ascertain significance among the parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals the physicochemical properties of the crude oil-contaminated soil samples. The research by Mahmood et al. (2020) shows that the physicochemical properties of soil can be affected by hydrocarbon contamination. These properties have been found to aid in the proliferation of bacteria in the soil. The interaction between living organisms and petroleum contaminants is highly dependent on the type of soil (Onyeiwu et al., 2022). Mahmood et al. (2020) further show that soil pH plays a critical role in the absorption of nutrients by plants and has

a significant effect on the interaction of microbes, which can affect the potential of microbes to carry out bioremediation. In this study, the pH ranged from 6.31 ± 0.07 to 6.79 ± 0.10 , a comfortable range that could facilitate the bioremediation activities of the bacteria isolated from the soil. Similar pH ranges have been reported by Udinyiwe and Aghedo (2023), and Udinyiwe et al. (2022), which supports better comparison and understanding. Soil pH is a key factor influencing the uptake of available nutrients for plant utilization (Udinyiwe and Aghedo, 2023; Mahmood et al., 2020). Bada et al. (2018) reported a similar pH range of 4.48 ± 0.48 to 6.72 ± 0.72 , which favors microbial metabolic activities. Okoh (2006) noted that low or acidic pH can affect the rate of oil biodegradation by bacteria in oil-contaminated soil. Acidic soil releases heavy metals such as Cd, Ni, Pb, Cu, Hg, and Zn, which creates problems for crop production (Bada et al., 2014).

The significantly higher values of electrical conductivity obtained from various sampling sites in this study could have resulted from the high concentration of charged ions in the impacted sites. Oyem and Oyem (2013) revealed electrical conductivity values higher than those reported in this study. The electrical conductivity in this study ranged from 306.30 ± 05.40 to 497.50 ± 0.90 , which could be attributed to the presence of high Na^+ and Mg^+ salts in the environment. This range is consistent with the values reported by Abosede (2013), Sari et al. (2018), and Oyem and Oyem (2013). High electrical conductivity can negatively impact soil (Abdulfattah et al., 2016; Precti and Shah, 2015).

Table 2 reveals bacterial counts ranging from 1.6×10^4 to 3.8×10^4 cfu/g, while Table 3 shows hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts ranging from 0.4×10^4 to 1.0×10^4 cfu/g. This indicates that bacteria can survive and thrive in this environment. Udinyiwe et al. (2022) reported total heterotrophic bacteria counts and hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts similar to those reported in this study. Ogbonna et al. (2020) reported total heterotrophic bacterial counts (THBC) ranging from $2.58 \times 10^8 \pm 0.07$ cfu/g to $2.10 \times 10^7 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g, and total hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts (THUBC) ranging from $8.1 \times 10^3 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g to $5.0 \times 10^4 \pm 0.50$ cfu/g, which agree with the findings of this study, confirming that bacteria can thrive in hydrocarbon-polluted sites.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of hydrocarbon-contaminated soil samples

Parameters Sample E	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D
pH 6.56 ± 0.12	6.79 ± 0.10	6.47 ± 0.01	6.31 ± 0.07	6.41 ± 0.08
EC (mS/m) 497.50 ± 0.90	456.45 ± 1.55	306.30 ± 5.40 ^{ab}	396.00 ± 0.90	391.90 ± 4.60 ^a
Carbon (%) 3.05 ± 0.23 ^a	3.31 ± 0.05	3.23 ± 0.04	3.44 ± 0.05	3.19 ± 0.03
Nitrogen (%) 0.79 ± 0.06	0.09 ± 0.03 ^a	1.04 ± 0.22 ^a	0.74 ± 0.06 ^a	0.62 ± 0.05 ^{ab}
Phosphorus (%) 1.57 ± 0.02	1.61 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.04	1.68 ± 0.09	1.66 ± 0.01
Water holding capacity (%) 76.55 ± 0.30 ^a	80.70 ± 0.70	78.50 ± 0.50	80.28 ± 0.72	75.55 ± 0.55 ^a
Bulk density (g/cm ³) 2.05 ± 0.11 ^a	2.66 ± 0.02	2.40 ± 0.01 ^a	1.90 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	2.70 ± 0.04
Moisture (%) 12.07 ± 0.30	12.06 ± 0.30	13.09 ± 0.24	13.40 ± 0.20	12.33 ± 0.55

Table 2: Total heterotrophic bacterial counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples Mean counts	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Uwelu 3.8 × 10 ⁴	139	74	31
Evwaike 3.4 × 10 ⁴	110	59	24
Igun 2.3 × 10 ⁴	88	35	19
Ugbowo 1.6 × 10 ⁴	72	29	13
Oluku 3.0 × 10 ⁴	94	51	24

Table 3: Hydrocarbon-utilizing bacterial counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples Mean counts	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Uwelu 1.0 × 10 ⁴	57	22	08
Evwaike 0.7 × 10 ⁴	44	17	05
Igun 0.6 × 10 ⁴	38	14	05
Ugbowo 0.4 × 10 ⁴	31	11	03
Oluku 0.8 × 10 ⁴	40	16	07

Table 4 shows fungal counts ranging from 0.1 × 10⁴ to 0.7 × 10⁴ cfu/g. The presence of fungal growth indicates that the soil has been exposed to hydrocarbon pollution, enriching it for fungal growth. Ogbonna et al. (2020) reported total fungal counts (TFC) and hydrocarbon-utilizing fungal counts (HUFC) ranging from 2.0 × 10⁵ ± 0.05 cfu/g to 1.6 × 10⁵ ± 0.08 cfu/g and 9.0 × 10³ ± 0.05 cfu/g to 7.0 × 10⁴ ± 0.50 cfu/g, respectively. This confirms that fungi can utilize hydrocarbons as a source of energy.

The microbes identified in this study with degradation potentials include *Bacillus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Micrococcus* spp., *Acinetobacter* spp., *Fusarium* spp., and *Aspergillus* spp. (Udinyiwe et al., 2022; Ijah and Abioye, 2003; Ajayi et al., 2008; Das and Chandran, 2011; Omotayo et al., 2012; Ogbonna et al., 2020; Bento et al., 2005). The results in Tables 5 and 6 show the growth and potential of these microbes to utilize hydrocarbons as an energy source. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas*

Table 4: Total heterotrophic fungal counts (cfu/g) of soil from mechanic workshop

Samples	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³
Mean counts			
Uwelu 0.7 × 10 ⁴	29	14	06
Evwaike 0.4 × 10 ⁴	23	08	03
Igun 0.2 × 10 ⁴	19	07	02
Ugbowo 0.1 × 10 ⁴	15	04	01
Oluku 0.3 × 10 ⁴	18	05	02

Table 5: Result of screening test for biodegradation of engine oil contaminated soil

Isolates	Optical Density (OD)
Acinetobacter spp	0.293
Micrococcus luteus	0.507
Bacillus subtilis	0.883
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.916
Corynebacterium spp.	0.128
Aspergillus niger	0.739
Penicillium	0.427
Mucor spp.	0.396
Trichoderma spp.	0.661
Fusarium spp.	0.131
Control	0.000

Keys: + = Little Growth, ++ = Moderate Growth, +++ = Heavy Growth, - = No Growth

aeruginosa, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Trichoderma* spp., selected after the screening test, demonstrated hydrocarbon degradation abilities in the 12-day shake flask experiment. The gradual increase in optical density indicates hydrocarbon utilization by these microbes. Dilmi et al. (2017) reported a similar gradual increase in optical density over fifteen days, indicating bacterial adaptation, survival, and proliferation. This study's results showed a gradual increase in turbidity of the mineral salt medium, indicating bacterial adaptation and proliferation, leading to the degradation of hydrocarbons. Udinyiwe et al. (2022) also reported increased turbidity and

pH over 12 days, consistent with this study. The microbial proliferation observed using poor plate techniques in Table 6 indicates bacterial utilization and adaptation in the medium, in agreement with Udinyiwe et al. (2022) and Ogbonna et al. (2020). For instance, the microbial population of *Bacillus subtilis* increased from 5.9×10^6 at day 0 to 1.25×10^7 at day 15.

Conclusion

The study revealed that soil samples collected from the five mechanic workshops were contaminated with spent engine oil. Results from this study are relevant in explaining the changes in the state of the soil environment, which leads to a corresponding change in the microbial composition. Oil degraders with inherent hydrocarbon assimilatory potentials are enriched by the contaminants, while the less adapted microbial species among the total heterotrophic populations are gradually being eliminated due to changes in species composition. The results of this study showed that the microbes isolated from engine oil-contaminated soil had biodegradation potentials.

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Table 6: Optical density (600 nm) during shake flask biodegradation for 12 days

Isolates	Day 0 to Day 3	Day 3 to Day 6	Day 6 to Day 9	Day 9 to Day 12
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	0.077	0.394	0.771	0.737
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	0.086	0.525	1.103	0.919
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	0.091	0.478	0.933	0.896
<i>Trichoderma spp.</i>	0.052	0.303	0.596	0.538
Bacterial consortium	0.103	0.768	1.394	1.361
Fungal consortium	0.119	0.694	1.286	1.209
Control	0.028	0.032	0.038	0.036

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A Preliminary Investigation of Microplastic Levels in a Commercially Important Clariid Fish Species from Ikpoba River, Benin City, Nigeria

Wangboje, O. M.*¹ (ORCID: 0000-0001-7587-3883) and Omzogie, C.¹ (ORCID: 0009-0008-8357-3475)

¹Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Benin, P.M.B. 1154, Benin City, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: oiseoje.wangboje@uniben.edu

ABSTRACT

Microplastics (MPs) in natural water resources and their inclusion in food webs has become a critical issue globally. The paucity of risk assessment data on the levels of MPs in Ikpoba River, Benin City, Nigeria, warranted this research which was done via Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy. The mean levels of MPs in *Clarias gariepinus* (mean total length 32.74 ± 1.58 cm, mean weight 885 ± 1.76 g) according to stations ranged from 0.37 in June at station 1 to 5.23 in August at station 3 with a total ranging from 2.97 at station 2 to 6.18 at station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean levels of MPs between the months across stations 1 and 3. The mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at station 1 to 6.34 in August at station 3 with a total ranging from 3.22 at station 2 to 7.41 at station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean plastic load between the months across stations 1 and 3. The dominant types of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* were fragments and filaments of Polyethylene. The estimated daily intake (EDI) for MPs (No./person/day) ranged from 0.00154 at station 2 to 0.00321 at station 3. *C. gariepinus* must therefore be consumed with caution in order to avert health problems associated with polymer pollution in the long run.

Keywords: *Clarias gariepinus*, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, Microplastics, Polyethylene

1 INTRODUCTION

Plastic production has increased substantially since large scale industrial manufacture started many decades ago such that all aspects of daily human life involve plastics hence their persistence in aquatic ecosystems globally (Lusher *et al.*, 2017). The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), has defined microplastics (MPs) as small fragments of plastic measuring less than 5 mm in length that are hazardous to aquatic bodies and their resources (NOAA, 2023). These polymers could have either primary or secondary sources. Primary microplastics are plastics directly released into the environment in the form of small particulates e.g. cosmetics, shower gels, abrasion of large plastic objects, wear of tyres and abrasion of synthetic textiles. Secondary microplastics on the flipside are microplastics originating from the degradation (e.g. photodegradation and weathering processes) of larger plastic items into smaller plastic fragments (International Union for Conservation of Nature, 2017). The occurrence of MPs in natural water

resources and their inclusion in food webs made possible by their minute size, has become a critical issue around the world especially in recent times (Kamau *et al.*, 2023; Pellicer and Domingo, 2023). It has been observed that a host of hydrobionts including fish, readily ingest MPs while grazing for food and these particles end up making their way into other parts of the body including edible tissue which is cherished by man (My *et al.*, 2023). The marine environment has been the focus of MP research in recent times (Wagner *et al.*, 2017; Selvakumar *et al.*, 2023). However, the searchlight has shifted to freshwater bodies which are now known to contain a cocktail of MPs including Polyethylene (PE), Polyamide (PA), Polyester (PES), Polypropylene (PP) and Polystyrene (PS) especially in their sediments thereby making benthic fish veritable targets of risk (Boskovic *et al.*, 2023). Mangrove ecosystems have also been scrutinized for MPs around the world in order to examine the contamination of flora, fauna and abiotic compartments (Mendes *et al.*, 2023). It has been observed that an increase in anthropogenic

2.3 Ex-situ Procedures and Laboratory Assay

2.3.1 Isolation of MPs from Organic Matter and Microscopy

The modified isolation procedure by Abidin et al. (2021) was applied. Briefly, fifty grams (50 g) of the excised intestine of fish was treated with 10% KOH solution (at three times the volume of tissue) followed by incubation for 24 hours. Excision was carried out using a stainless steel lancet via the ventral aspect of whole fish. The Wet Peroxide Oxidation process was applied by adding 30 mL of 0.05 M Fe (II) oxide (FeO) and 30 mL of 20% Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), followed by heating on a Binatone® Hotplate (Model ECP-207, rated at 2,500W) at 75°C for 45 minutes to eradicate organic matter from the fish. All reagents used were of analytical grade (SIGMA, Germany). The remaining filtrates were treated via heating, followed by filtration with stainless steel sieves of 45 m mesh size. The dried filtrate was placed on a slide under a UNIC® compound binocular electric microscope, in order to visually account for the numerical strength of fibres, filaments, fragments, and pellets.

2.3.2 Additional Verification Procedures for MPs

Additional verification of MPs was achieved by applying the tagging method as described by Maes et al. (2017) and the hot needle test or hot point test as described by De Witte et al. (2014).

2.3.3 Application of Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy for Polymer Differentiation

Polymer differentiation was achieved using FTIR Spectroscopy. The specific device used was a Shimadzu® FTIR 8400S Spectroscope which was correctly programmed and conditioned according to the manufacturer's standard prior to use.

2.3.4 Determination of Plastic Load (PL)

The mean amount of MP per fish is known as the plastic load (PL). $PL = \frac{\text{Total number of MP particles}}{\text{Total number of fish species examined}}$ (Zhang et al., 2021).

2.3.5 Determination of Frequency of Occurrence (FO) for MP

Frequency of occurrence (FO) denotes the percentage of fish with at least one piece of MP. $FO = \frac{\text{Number of fish with at least one MP particle}}{\text{Number of fish sampled}}$ (Riaz et al., 2023).

2.3.6 Contamination Circumvention

In order to avert contamination of samples, non-plastic clothes were worn (Cotton laboratory coat) while sampling and laboratory instruments made from non-plastic components, such as glass, were used as recommended by Cutroneo et al. (2020). All work benches and surrounding areas were thoroughly wiped with absolute alcohol (99.9%) and disposable Cotton sheets before, in between, and after analysis.

2.3.7 Determination of Estimated Annual Intake (EAI) and Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) of MPs

- $EAI (\text{No./person/year}) = \frac{\text{Number of MP items in fish} \times \text{Per capita figure}}{\text{Adult body weight (Assumed to be 70 kg)}}$
Where: Per capita figure is 13.3 kg/person/year for Nigeria (World Fish Center, 2023)
- $EDI (\text{No./person/day}) = \frac{EAI}{365 \text{ days}}$

2.4 Statistical Analysis

GENSTAT software (version 12.1) was used for statistical analysis. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine significant differences between mean values of MPs at a 5% level of probability, while significant means ($P < 0.05$) were separated using New Duncan Multiple Range Test.

3 Results

As presented in Table ??, the mean levels of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.37 in June at Station 1 to 5.23 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 2.97 at Station 2 to 6.18 at Station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean levels of MPs between the months across Stations 1 and 3. The mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at Station 1 to 6.34 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 3.22 at Station 2 to 7.41 at Station 3. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean plastic load between the months across Stations 1 and 3 as shown in Table ??. The mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to stations ranged from 0.31 in June at Station 1 to 0.85 in August at Station 3, with a total figure ranging from 1.54 at Station 3

Table 1: Table 1: Mean level of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.37 ± 0.55a	1.35 ± 1.32a	0.38 ± 0.26a
July	0.66 ± 0.48a	1.25 ± 0.77a	5.23 ± 1.65b
August	0.66 ± 0.48a	1.25 ± 0.77a	5.23 ± 1.65b
Mean	3.38	2.97	6.18

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

Table 2: Table 1: Mean level of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.31 ± 0.55a	1.37 ± 1.41a	0.35 ± 0.46 a
July	2.65 ± 1.25b	0.52 ± 0.56a	0.72 ± 1.25a
August	0.71 ± 0.43a	1.33 ± 0.58a	6.34. ± 1.62b
Mean	3.38	3.22	7.41

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

to 1.94 at Station 2. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed in the mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* between the months across all stations as presented in Table ???. The type of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* according to morphological classification is presented in Table ??, where fragments and filaments were found in *C. gariepinus* in June, fragments, filaments, pellets, and fibres in July, and foam, fragments, filaments, and pellets in August. A typical FTIR spectrum for MP particles obtained from *C. gariepinus*, showing absorbance bands at different wave numbers, is presented in Figure 2. Peaks at 2910 cm^{-1} , 2820 cm^{-1} , 1445 cm^{-1} , and 710 cm^{-1} are characteristic of polyethylene (PE) compounds. The estimated annual intake (EAI) values (No./person/year) for MPs ranged from 0.564 at Station 2 to 1.174 at Station 3 (Fig. 3) while the estimated daily intake (EDI) values (No./person/day) ranged from 0.00154 at Station 2 to 0.00321 at Station 3 (Fig. 4). As presented in Figure 5, the percentage quota of abundance for MPs in *C. gariepinus* by stations ranged from 23.70% at Station 2 to 49.32% at Station 3. Figure 6 shows the proportion of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*, with the highest proportions being for filaments and fragments (33.33%) and the least proportion for fibre (3.70%). As shown in Figure 7, the temporal percentage quota of types of microplastics peaked for filaments in August (55.55%) while there was a peak for fragments in June, July, and August (33.33%).

4 Discussion

Microplastic particles were found in *C. gariepinus*, clearly implying that the fish species consumed such particles while grazing for prey. The mean level of MPs in *C. gariepinus* according to Stations reached

Table 3: Table 1: Mean frequency of occurrence of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
June	0.31 ± 0.04a	0.75 ± 0.03c	0.32 ± 0.04a
July	0.78 ± 0.13c	0.62 ± 0.03a	0.37 ± 0.03a
August	0.49 ± 0.02b	0.57 ± 0.05b	0.85 ± 0.02b
Mean	1.58	1.94	1.54

Mean values with the same superscripts are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Vertical comparison only.

a zenith at Station 3 and was the lowest at Station 1. Similarly, the mean plastic load in *C. gariepinus* peaked at Station 3 and was the lowest at Station 1. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed between months for Stations 1 and 3 in the mean level of MPs, and similar significant differences were observed in the mean plastic load between months for Stations 1 and 3. These significant differences indicate variations in the MP profile in the investigated fish species across the research period. Mendes et al. (2023) observed that both temporal and spatial variations in MPs are to be expected when sampling for MPs in environmental matrices. Additionally, particle density, water surface area, water surface depth, wind action, and water flow patterns could further influence the distribution and consequent levels of MPs in aquatic bodies (Sau et al., 2023).

The mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* by stations was at a peak at Station 3, while it was lowest at Station 1. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean frequency of occurrence of MPs in *C. gariepinus* were observed between months across all stations. This variability

Table 4: Mean frequency of occurrence of microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* according to stations

Month	June			July			August		
Station Code	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
R1	N	T	N	Z, T	N	N	N	Z, P	Z, T, P
R2	T, Z	T	N	Z, P	P	N	N	Z	Z, P
R3	N	N	Z	T	N	B, T	T	N	Z, T, P

R1, R2, R3= Replicates Key: N = No plastic, Z = Filament, T = Fragment, P = Pellet, B = Fibre

Figure 2: A typical FTIR spectrum for microplastic particles obtained from *Clarias gariepinus* showing absorbance bands at different wave numbers.

Figure 4: Estimated daily intake (EDI) values for microplastics from *Clarias gariepinus*.

Figure 3: Estimated annual intake (EAI) values for microplastics from *Clarias gariepinus*.

Figure 5: Percent (%) quota of abundance for microplastics in *Clarias gariepinus* by station.

indicates a significant fluctuation in the frequency of occurrence of MPs in the target fish species. The types of MP particles found in *C. gariepinus* included fragments, filaments, fibers, and pellets, with filaments and fragments being the dominant types. However, the temporal distribution revealed that filaments and pellets were prominent in August. The varying types of MP particles observed could reflect different degradation mechanisms, such as photo-oxidation, ultraviolet radiation, hydrolysis, and biodegradation, leading to various shapes and forms (Gewert et al., 2015). The temporal distribution

indicates the occurrence of these MP types within the sampling period, considering the respective months. MP levels in aquatic resources can vary by water body, location, and season (Boskovic et al., 2023).

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy confirmed the presence of Polyethylene in *C. gariepinus*. According to Unnimaya et al. (2023), specific band widths from spectrometric readings define the type of plastic in examined samples. Boskovic et al. (2023) observed that Polyethylene is the most common plastic in rivers worldwide, along with Polypropylene, resulting from anthropogenic impact. These plastics are widely used in the packaging industry, which may account for their

Figure 6: Proportion of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*.

Figure 7: Temporal distribution quota of the type of microplastics in *C. gariepinus*.

prevalence in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. In Nigeria, plastic and nylon waste pollution remains a problem (Bolaji et al., 2021). Mancuso et al. (2023) noted the dominant presence (52%) of Polyester in the Antarctic fish *Trematomus bernacchii* from the Terranova Bay Area.

The EAI and EDI values were highest at Station 3 and lowest at Station 2. This was supported by the percentage quota of abundance for MPs in *C. gariepinus* by station, where Station 3 accounted for 49.32 % of the total. This indicates that *C. gariepinus* at Station 3 (Bridge) were more impacted by MPs, while the least impact was at Station 2 (Reservoir). This implies that *C. gariepinus* from Station 3 for human consumption may have a greater impact compared to fish from other stations due to the heavier MP load. It could be inferred that Station 3 (Bridge) is the most polluted regarding MPs. The prevalent anthropogenic activities at the Bridge station, including car washes, rug washes, and slaughterhouses, contribute to the MP burden of the river. Ng et al. (2022) observed that abattoir wastewater contains proteins, fats, microbes, organic matter, and emerging pollutants including MPs. Rugs, carpets, and car parts, including tyres, contain plastics

as components (Aydin et al., 2023). Moreover, the Bridge station, situated downstream of the other two stations, receives additional MPs from upstream due to the river's lotic nature and high anthropogenic impact in the busy city.

5 Conclusion

This research was a pilot investigation into the levels of microplastics (MPs) in *C. gariepinus*, particularly sourced from the Ikpoba River in Benin City, Nigeria. The presence of MPs in the aforementioned fish species is a concerning development due to the potential primary risk to the fish species and the potential secondary risk to end-of-the-line consumers, including humans. To address the ongoing influx of MPs into the Ikpoba River ecosystem, it is recommended that stringent legislation on the disposal of plastic products into aquatic environments be enforced. Additionally, a robust monitoring and enforcement system should be established to ensure that the plastic load in the river and its natural resources does not reach critical levels. Furthermore, *C. gariepinus* should be consumed with caution to avoid health problems associated with polymer contamination in the long run.

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PHYTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND TOXICITY ASSESSMENT OF ACUTE AND SUB-ACUTE ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *JATROPHA TANJORENSIS* LEAF

Ebhohon, S. O.¹, Emelike, A. P.¹, Onyenze, C. C.¹, Ikenna, J. C.¹, Ngwuta, C. R.¹,
Ejue, P. O.¹, and Ogbu, C. A.¹

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author E-mail: so.ebhohon@mouau.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The phytochemical evaluation of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids. Toxicity studies indicated no mortality up to 6000 mg/kg in mice, with 33.33% mortality at 7000 mg/kg and 100% mortality at 10,000 mg/kg, yielding an LD₅₀ of 7745.97 mg/kg. Biochemical analyses in Wistar rats showed no significant ($p < 0.05$) changes in serum ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase) and AST (Aspartate Aminotransferase) activities but a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in ALP (Alkaline Phosphatase) activity, particularly at 400 mg/kg. Serum total protein and albumin concentrations increased significantly ($p < 0.05$), while bilirubin and globulin levels remained unchanged ($p < 0.05$). Urea levels decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) at 200 mg/kg, with no significant ($p < 0.05$) changes in creatinine, sodium, chloride, and potassium levels. Bicarbonate levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced at 200 mg/kg. Antioxidant biomarkers—SOD (Superoxide Dismutase), CAT (Catalase), GSH (Reduced glutathione), and GPx (Glutathione peroxidase)—increased ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependently, while MDA (Malondialdehyde) levels decreased ($p < 0.05$). Histological analyses of liver and kidney sections revealed normal ultrastructures, indicating no histopathological damage. These findings suggest that *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract has a favorable safety profile at lower doses, with potential antioxidant benefits and no adverse effects on liver and kidney structures.

Keywords: Antioxidant enzymes, *Jatropha tanjorensis*, Liver enzymes, Phytochemicals, Toxicity

INTRODUCTION

Traditional herbal medicines have long been cherished for their natural origins and perceived minimal side effects, serving as integral components of local and regional healing practices worldwide (WHO, 2019; Rizvi et al., 2022). The World Health Organization defines these medicines as plant-derived substances with minimal industrial processing, used for the prevention and treatment of illnesses. Over millennia, they have found extensive application in both developed and developing countries, evolving from crude formulations like tinctures and teas to contributing directly to the synthesis of modern pharmaceuticals such as aspirin (from willow bark), morphine (from opium poppy), and quinine (from cinchona bark) (Chaachouay & Zidane, 2024). While the historical efficacy of herbal remedies is undeniable, concerns about their safety persist, prompting rigorous toxicity

evaluations. Despite sparse reports of adverse reactions leading to injury or death, the presence of potentially harmful compounds like alkaloids and anthraquinone glycosides necessitates comprehensive safety assessments (Zhang et al., 2015). This underscores the critical importance of evaluating the toxicity of medicinal plants to ensure their therapeutic benefits outweigh any potential risks (Neergheen-Bhujun, 2013).

The assessment of acute, sub-acute, and sub-chronic toxicity in medicinal plants plays a crucial role in ensuring their safety and efficacy for human consumption. Acute toxicity assessments provide valuable insights into the immediate adverse effects of a medicinal plant or its extracts. This helps in determining safe dosage levels and potential risks associated with high doses. Sub-acute toxicity studies, conducted over a longer duration, further elucidate the cumulative effects and potential toxicity of repeated doses, mimicking more closely the

conditions of chronic use. Sub-chronic toxicity studies, on the other hand, evaluate the effects of repeated exposure over a longer duration, mimicking more closely the typical usage patterns of medicinal products. Both assessments contribute significantly to ensuring the safety of herbal medicines (Li et al., 2020; Njinga et al., 2020).

Jatropha tanjorensis (J. L. Ellis & Saroja), a member of the Euphorbiaceae family, stands as a versatile botanical wonder with a plethora of medicinal virtues (Ellis & Saroja, 1961). This gregarious shrub, reaching heights of about 1.8 meters, thrives as a common weed among field crops, primarily flourishing in the rainforest zones of West Africa (Idu et al., 2014). The multifaceted applications of *Jatropha tanjorensis* in traditional medicine and beyond underscore its significance. Abundant scientific evidence supports the medicinal properties of this plant. Every part of the *Jatropha tanjorensis* plant, from its seeds to its leaves and bark, is rich in therapeutic potential. Exploring the medicinal properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* uncovers a wealth of benefits, including anti-diabetic, cardiovascular, antioxidant, and haematological improvements (Adebajo et al., 2001; Oyewole & Akingbala, 2011; Omoregie & Osagie, 2011; Idu et al., 2014).

The antioxidant and hypoglycaemic properties of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extracts have made them a popular treatment for conditions such as diabetes, malaria, and hypertension in Southern Nigerian regions like Edo State. Here, the leaves are consumed not only as a nutritious vegetable but also as part of daily meals, due to their reputed effectiveness in managing diabetes mellitus, thanks to their anti-hyperglycaemic effects (Olayiwola et al., 2004). These antioxidants enhance the body's defence mechanisms and are crucial in fighting oxidative stress-related conditions like diabetes, malaria, and hypertension, which are especially common in areas where this plant is cultivated. Studies administering *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf powder to animal models have demonstrated improvements in haematological indices, indicating a potential enhancement in bone marrow function (Orhue et al., 2008). Additionally, the plant's antibacterial attributes have been delineated, affirming its role in infectious disease management (Viswanathan & Jeyaananthi, 2009). The nutritional profile of

Jatropha tanjorensis is equally noteworthy, boasting a rich concentration of antioxidant nutrients such as phosphorus, selenium, zinc, vitamin C, and E (Omobuwajo et al., 2011).

Phytochemical investigations revealed the existence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and anthraquinones in the aqueous leaf extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (Ebenyi et al., 2021). Similarly, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, and anthraquinones were detected in the methanol leaf extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* (Igbinaduwa et al., 2011). Studies have reported that *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract contains phytochemical constituents capable of reducing blood cholesterol levels, which can be beneficial in treating cardiovascular diseases resulting from hyperlipidaemia (Oyewole & Akingbala, 2011). *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract also has antimicrobial properties, inhibiting the growth of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Ewa-Udu et al., 2022). As scientific exploration continues, this botanical gem promises to unveil even more of its healing secrets, potentially revolutionising the landscape of natural medicine. An earlier study examining the toxicity characteristics of *Jatropha tanjorensis* demonstrated the absence of toxicity when administering (2000 and 5000 mg/kg) of aqueous leaf extract to mice and rats within 24 hours after oral ingestion (Ebenyi et al., 2021). Similarly, no observed toxicity was reported at 8000 mg/kg of methanol extracts in the same animal models within the same timeframe (Igbinaduwa et al., 2011).

Insufficient exploration into the toxicity evaluation of the aqueous extract derived from *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf, especially regarding acute and sub-acute oral administration, limits a thorough understanding of the safety attributes linked to this extract. Assessing toxicity is crucial for identifying potential adverse reactions, setting safe dosage thresholds, and balancing the risks and benefits associated with utilising the extract in therapeutic or medicinal scenarios. The absence of comprehensive toxicity analyses may lead to uncertainties regarding the extract's safety, potentially prompting cautious or restricted usage within clinical settings. The study seeks to identify and quantify the key phytochemical constituents present in the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf. This entails gauging the levels of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins,

terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinones, and other bioactive compounds that contribute to the plant's medicinal attributes. Although *Jatropha tanjorensis* offers potential medicinal benefits, the presence of alkaloids and anthraquinones requires caution due to their potential toxic effects such as hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, cardiotoxicity, gastrointestinal distress, and neurotoxicity. Proper dosing, a thorough understanding of the plant's pharmacology, are essential to mitigate these risks. Furthermore, it aims to evaluate the toxicity of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf through both acute and sub-acute oral administration, with the goal of elucidating its safety profile and potential therapeutic applications. In conclusion, acute and sub-acute toxicity assessment of medicinal plants is indispensable for safety evaluation, risk identification, quality control, optimizing treatment regimens, public health protection, scientific validation, and building consumer confidence. These assessments are essential steps in ensuring the safe and effective use of herbal medicines in healthcare practice.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plant Materials and Preparation of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaves

Fresh leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* were collected from the National Crop Research Institute (NCRI) in Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria, and identified by Mr. Pipi Okey from the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The specimen was assigned voucher number MOUAU/PSB/18/103592 and deposited in the Department's Herbarium. The leaves were rinsed with distilled water to remove dirt and air-dried at room temperature until completely dry. The dried leaves were ground into a fine powder using an electric blender. A known quantity (188.54 g) of the powdered sample was macerated in 2.5 L of distilled water for 24 hours in a sterile extraction jar. The filtrate was first filtered using muslin cloth and then filtered again using Whatman filter paper No. 1 into a clean, calibrated flask. The filtrate was lyophilized, using a freeze dryer set to a temperature of -40°C . A dark-brown paste with a yield of 50.85% was obtained, transferred into a sterile clean bottle, and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until needed for biochemical assays.

Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

Preliminary analysis of the aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf was carried out to identify the presence of various phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponin, cardiac glycoside, and steroids.

Test for Alkaloid

For qualitative alkaloid determination, a few drops of Meyer's reagent were added to 1 mL of extract. The formation of a creamy white precipitate was considered positive for the alkaloid (Archana et al., 2012).

Test for Tannin

For qualitative tannin analysis, a few drops of lead acetate were added to 1 mL of extract. A large white-brown precipitate formation was considered a positive test for tannin (Archana et al., 2012).

Test for Flavonoids

For the confirmation of flavonoid, 0.5 g of each extract were added in a test tube and 10 mL of distilled water, 5 ml of dilute ammonia solution were added to a portion of the aqueous filtrate of each plant extract followed by addition of 1 mL concentrated H_2SO_4 . Indication of yellow colour shows the presence of flavonoid in each extract (Sofowora, 1993).

Test for Phenols

To detect phenols, 1 mL of extract solution was added to 2 mL distilled water and a few drops of 10% ferric chloride (FeCl_3). The appearance of a green or blue colour is the indication of phenols presence. Next, 0.50 g of plant extract was added and allowed to dissolve in distilled water and then 3 mL of 10% lead acetate was added. The presence of phenolic compounds was confirmed by the appearance of white precipitation (Trease et al., 2003).

Test for Saponin

To detect the presence of saponin, 5 mL of distilled water was added to 1 mL of extract and vortexed for 10 minutes. The formation of a foam column that did not disappear with the addition of HCl was evaluated as positive for saponin (Sati and Kumar, 2015; Savithramma et al., 2011).

Test for Cardiac Glycoside

Qualitative analysis of cardiac glycosides in the extracts was performed with the Keller Killiani test.

1 mL of acetic acid and 2 drops of ferric chloride were added to 2 mL of extract, then 2 mL of sulfuric acid (concentrated) was added and the colour change was observed. Reddish-brown colour formation was deemed to be a positive test for cardiac glycosides (Archana et al., 2012; Sati & Kumar, 2015).

Test for Terpenoids and Steroids

The presence of terpenoids and steroids was determined by a previously described method (Kantamreddi & Lakshmi, 2010; Siddiqui & Ali, 1997) with slight modifications. Briefly, 0.5 g of solvent-free extract was added in 2 mL chloroform and then filtered. The filtrate was placed on ice; addition of 2 mL of acetic acid and then a few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) was carefully applied to the inner sides of the test tubes. The emergence of a pink or pinkish brown colour/ring indicates the terpenoids existence, while a blue or bluish green colour for steroids presence and the combination of pink and blue/bluish green colours confirmed the presence of both terpenoids and steroids.

Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis

Quantitative analysis of the phytochemical components, whose presence were tested by qualitative analysis, were also carried out. All the analysis were performed in triplicate.

Estimation of Total Alkaloids

Alkaloid determination was made according to the method reported by Selvakumar et al. (2019). To 1 mL of the test extract 5 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) and 5 mL of bromocresol green (BCG) solution was added to the solution. The mixture was shaken and the complex extracted with 1-, 2-, 3- and 4-mL of chloroform by vigorous shaking. The extracts were then collected in a 10 mL volumetric flask and then diluted to adjust volume with chloroform. The absorbance of the chloroform complex was measured at 470 nm using a UV spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly, but without extract. To quantify the total alkaloid content in the sample, a standard curve was prepared using atropine. Standard solution of atropine was prepared at concentrations of (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 mg/mL). To generate the standard curve, the average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding atropine concentrations. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the

equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total alkaloid content in the extract. The alkaloid content was expressed as mg atropine equivalent (AE)/g of sample. All tests were repeated in triplicate.

Estimation of Total Tannins

Tannin content was determined according to the method of Van-Burden & Robinson, 1981. A known weight of sample (500 mg) was weighed into a 100 mL plastic bottle. 50 mL of distilled water was added and shaken for 1 h in a mechanical shaker. This was filtered into a 50 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark. Then 5 mL of the filtered was pipette out into a test tube and mixed with 2 mL of 0.1 M $FeCl_3$ in 0.1 N HCl and 0.008 M potassium ferrocyanide. The absorbance of each reaction mixture was thereafter measured at 120 nm against a blank using a spectrophotometer. To quantify the total tannin content in the sample, a standard curve was prepared using gallic acid. Standard solution of gallic acid were prepared at concentrations of (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 mg/L). The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of gallic acid to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total tannin content in the extract. Results were quantified in the form of GAE (mg of Gallic Acid Equivalents) per gram of dry plant extract/fraction. Samples were analysed in triplicates.

Estimation of Total Flavonoids

The total flavonoid content of the extract was determined using a slightly modified method reported by Meda et al. (2005). 0.5 mL of the extract samples were mixed with 0.5 mL methanol, 50 L of 10% $AlCl_3$, 50 L of 1 mol L^{-1} potassium acetate and 1.4 mL water, and allowed to incubate at room temperature for 30 min. Thereafter, the absorbance of each reaction mixture was subsequently measured at 415 nm against blank. To quantify the total flavonoids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using quercetin. Standard solutions of quercetin were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, and 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of quercetin to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the

equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total flavonoid content in the extract. The flavonoid content was expressed as mg quercetin equivalents (QE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Total Phenols

Total phenolic content was determined using the method of Makkar et al. (1993) with some modifications. The reaction mixture contained 100 L of the extract, 2.8 mL distilled water, 2 mL of 2% sodium carbonate and 100 L of 50% Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, and it was incubated at room temperature for 30 min. Thereafter, the absorbance of the mixture was measured at 750 nm using a spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly, but without extract. To quantify the total phenolic content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using tannic acid. Standard solution of tannic acid were prepared at concentrations of 0, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of tannic acid to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total phenolic content in the extract. The total phenol was expressed as mg tannic acid equivalents (TAE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Total Saponins

Saponin content was determined by the gravimetric method of AOAC, (1990). 20 g of sample was weighed into a 250 mL beaker and 100 mL of 20% aqueous ethanol was added. The suspension was heated over a hot water bath for 4 h with continuous stirring at about 55°C. The mixture was filtered and the residue re-extracted with another 200 mL 20% ethanol. The combined extracts were reduced to 40 mL over water bath at about 90°C. The concentrate was transferred into a 250 mL separatory funnel and 20 mL of diethyl ether was added and shaken vigorously. The aqueous layer was recovered while the ether layer was discarded. The purification process was repeated. 60 mL of n-butanol was added and the combined n-butanol extracts were washed twice with 10 mL of 5% aqueous sodium chloride. The remaining solution was heated in a water bath. After evaporation the sample was dried in the oven to a constant weight. The saponin content was calculated

using the formula:

$$\text{Saponin content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}{\text{Weight of original sample (g)}} \times 100$$

Estimation of Cardiac Glycosides

The determination of the total cardiac glycosides was performed using the Baljet method as described by (El-Olemy et al., 1994) with slight modifications. Briefly, 1 g of pulverized leaf powder was macerated in 10 mL of 70% alcohol for 30 min. The solution was filtered and the residue re-macerated twice to ensure extraction of the metabolites. The extract was dried at 40°C for 6 h and reconstituted in distilled water. To 1 mL of the reconstituted sample was added 1 mL of freshly prepared Baljet's reagent (95 mL of 1% aqueous picric acid + 5 mL of 10% aqueous NaOH) and the intensity of the colour complex formed was read at 495 nm after 1 h against a blank treated in the same way except that the sample was substituted with distilled water. A blank experiment was also performed using distilled water. To quantify the total cardiac glycosides content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using digitoxin. Standard solutions of digitoxin were prepared at concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 mg/L. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of digitoxin to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total cardiac glycosides content in the extract. The total cardiac glycosides were expressed as mg digitoxin equivalents (DE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Terpenoids

The determination of the total terpenoid content was performed using the method of Indumathi and Mohandass, (2014) with slight modifications. 1 mL of the extract was mixed with 3 mL of chloroform and allowed to stand for 1.5 h. Then, 1.5 mL of the mixture was taken and mixed with 3.5 mL concentrated H_2SO_4 . The absorbance of the mixture was read at 538 nm. To quantify the total terpenoids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using linalool. Standard solutions of linalool were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of

linalool to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total terpenoids content in the extract. The total terpenoids content was expressed as mg linalool equivalents (LE)/g of sample.

Estimation of Steroids

The determination of the total steroid content was performed using the method of Indumathi and Mohandass, (2014) with slight modifications. 0.5 g of each extract was dissolved in 3 mL chloroform. Then, 2 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 was carefully added to form a lower layer. A reddish brown colour at the interface indicated the presence of steroids. The absorbance of the resulting reddish brown colour was measured at 550 nm against a reagent blank. To quantify the total steroids content of the extract, a standard curve was prepared using linalool. Standard solutions of linalool were prepared at concentrations of 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240 g/mL. The average absorbance values were plotted against the corresponding concentrations of linalool to generate the standard curve. A linear regression analysis was performed to obtain the equation of the line: $y = mx + b$. This linear equation was then used to determine the total steroid content in the extract. The total steroids content was expressed as mg linalool equivalents (LE)/g of sample.

Animals

Thirty (30) male albino rats (100-150 g) were procured from the Department of Veterinary Medicine, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria. The animals were housed in clean, well-ventilated polypropylene cages, maintained under standard conditions (12 h light and 12 h dark cycle) at an ambient temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ C$ and were fed with standard rodent pellets and water *ad libitum*. The rats were acclimatized for 14 days before the commencement of the experiment.

Experimental Design

The acclimatized animals were randomly divided into five (5) groups (A, B, C, D, E) of six (6) rats each. They were treated as follows:

1. Group A (normal control): received distilled water throughout the experimental period.
2. Group B (positive control): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite only throughout the experimental period.
3. Group C (test group 1): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 100 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.
4. Group D (test group 2): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 200 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.
5. Group E (test group 3): received 500 mg/kg b.w. of sodium arsenite and 400 mg/kg b.w. of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaves extract throughout the experimental period.

The treatments were administered orally for 14 days and the animals were weighed every 3 days to monitor weight changes.

Preparation of Tissue Homogenate

After the last administration, the animals were fasted overnight and sacrificed by cervical dislocation. The testes were rapidly excised, rinsed in ice-cold 1.15% KCl solution, blotted dry, and weighed. Each tissue sample was then homogenized in four (4) volumes of ice-cold 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) using a Potter-Elvehjem homogenizer. The homogenate was centrifuged at 10,000 g for 20 minutes at $4^\circ C$ to obtain the post-mitochondrial supernatant, which was used for the biochemical assays.

Biochemical Assays

The following biochemical assays were carried out on the post-mitochondrial supernatant.

Malondialdehyde (MDA) Assay

Lipid peroxidation was estimated by measuring the level of malondialdehyde (MDA), a product of lipid peroxidation, using the method of Buege and Aust (1978). Briefly, 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant was mixed with 1.5 mL of 20% acetic acid (pH 3.5), 0.2 mL of 8.1% SDS, and 1.5 mL of 0.8% TBA. The mixture was made up to 4 mL with distilled water and incubated at $95^\circ C$ for 60 minutes. After cooling, 1 mL of distilled water and 5 mL of n-butanol:pyridine mixture (15:1 v/v) were added. The mixture was shaken vigorously and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes. The absorbance of the

organic layer was measured at 532 nm. The MDA concentration was calculated using the extinction coefficient of $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and expressed as nmol/mg protein.

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Assay

SOD activity was determined using the method of Misra and Fridovich (1972). The reaction mixture consisted of 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1.2 mL of sodium carbonate buffer (50 mM, pH 10.2), and 0.2 mL of epinephrine (30 mM). The reaction was initiated by the addition of epinephrine, and the increase in absorbance was measured at 480 nm for 4 minutes. One unit of SOD activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to cause 50% inhibition of the oxidation of epinephrine to adrenochrome. The specific activity was expressed as units/mg protein.

Catalase (CAT) Assay

CAT activity was determined according to the method of Sinha (1972). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant and 1.9 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0). The reaction was initiated by the addition of 1 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 mM), and the decrease in absorbance was measured at 240 nm for 2 minutes. The enzyme activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of $43.6 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and expressed as units/mg protein.

Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) Assay

GPx activity was measured according to the method of Rotruck et al. (1973). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), 0.1 mL of GSH (1 mM), 0.1 mL of NADPH (0.12 mM), 0.1 mL of sodium azide (1 mM), and 0.1 mL of hydrogen peroxide (0.15 mM). The decrease in absorbance at 340 nm was recorded for 3 minutes. The enzyme activity was expressed as nmol NADPH oxidized/min/mg protein using the extinction coefficient of $6.22 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$.

Glutathione-S-Transferase (GST) Assay

GST activity was determined according to the method of Habig et al. (1974). The reaction mixture contained 0.1 mL of the post-mitochondrial supernatant, 1.7 mL of phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 7.0), 0.2 mL of GSH (1 mM), and 0.1 mL of CDNB (1 mM). The increase in absorbance at 340 nm was

recorded for 5 minutes. One unit of GST activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to conjugate 1 mol of CDNB with GSH per minute. The specific activity was expressed as units/mg protein.

Protein Estimation

The protein content in the post-mitochondrial supernatant was estimated by the method of Lowry et al. (1951) using bovine serum albumin as the standard. The absorbance was read at 750 nm and the protein concentration was expressed as mg/mL of the supernatant.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

1 Results

1.1 Phytochemical Analysis of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

The result of the phytochemical evaluation of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf is shown in Table 1. It revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids.

1.2 Results of Acute Toxicity Study of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf in Wistar Rats

Graded doses up to 6000 mg/kg of the extract produced no mortality in rats as the treated rats remained active and physically stable throughout the 24-hour period of observation. However, 33.33 percent mortality was observed in the third phase and group administered 7000 mg/kg body weight while all the rats in the 10,000 mg/kg treated group died, representing 100 percent mortality. The application of Lorke's formula yielded an LD_{50} value of 7745.97 mg/kg body weight for the aqueous extract. The results are presented in Tables 2, 3, and 4 below.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{D_0 \times D_{100}}$$

Where:

D_0 : Highest dose that gave no mortality.

D_{100} : Lowest dose that produced mortality.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{6000 \times 10000}$$

$$LD_{50} = 7745.97 \text{ mg/kg body weight}$$

Table 1: Phytochemical Constituents of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

Phytochemical Parameter	Qualitative	Quantitative (mg/100g)
Alkaloids	++	27.15±0.59
Tannins	+	7.63±0.18
Flavonoids	+++	39.18±1.07
Phenols	+++	46.07±1.14
Terpenoids	+	5.41±0.15
Saponins	+++	33.10±1.25
Cardiac glycosides	+	4.83±0.19
Steroids	+	3.80±0.10

+++ = high amount, ++ = moderate amount, + = low amount

Table 2: Stage 1 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Evaluation of the Extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	10	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
2	100	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
3	1000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{D_0 \times D_{100}}$$

Where:

D_0 : Highest dose that gave no mortality.

D_{100} : Lowest dose that produced mortality

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{6000 \times 10000}$$

$$LD_{50} = 7745.97 \text{ mg/kg body weight}$$

1.3 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on the Activities of Liver Enzymes and Total Protein Levels in Sera of Male Wistar Rats

The experimental results showed no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum levels of ALT and AST between Wistar rats administered the extract at various doses and the control group (Figures 1 and 2). However, serum ALP levels were significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$) in all experimental groups given

the extract compared to the control group, with the lowest ALP level observed in the group administered 400 mg/kg (Figure 3). Additionally, serum total protein and albumin concentrations were significantly increased ($P < 0.05$) in rats given the extract compared to their respective controls (Figures 4 and 5). There were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum total bilirubin levels between the experimental groups and the control group after 30 days (Figure 6). Similarly, serum globulin concentrations did not show a significant increase ($P > 0.05$) in the experimental groups compared to the control (Figure 7).

Table 3: Stage 2: Acute toxicity (LD50) evaluation of the extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	1600	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
2	2900	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed, instead animals remained active and physically stable.
3	5000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed. Animals were initially calm but regained physical activity within one hour of administration.

Figure 1: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of ALT in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 2: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of AST in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

2 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Kidney Function Indices in Sera of Male Wistar Rats

The serum urea levels in rats given 400 and 800 mg/kg of the extract did not show significant differences ($P > 0.05$) compared to the control group. However, administering 200 mg/kg of the extract resulted in a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in urea concentration compared to the control (Figure 8). Similarly, serum creatinine levels in rats given 400 and 800 mg/kg of the extract were not significantly

different ($P > 0.05$) from the control (Figure 9). There were no significant reductions ($P > 0.05$) in serum Na^+ concentration in rats administered 200, 400, and 800 mg/kg of the extract (Figure 10). The serum chloride and potassium ion concentrations in rats given the extract were also not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) from the control (Figures 11 and 12). However, rats administered 200 mg/kg of the extract showed a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in serum bicarbonate ion concentration compared to the control and those given 400 mg/kg of the extract. In contrast, rats given 800 mg/kg of the extract did not show significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in serum bicarbonate levels

Table 4: Stage 3 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) Evaluation of the Extract

Group	Dose (mg/kg)	No. of Deaths	Percentage of mortality	Observations
1	6000	0/3	0.00	No mortality observed. Animals were initially calm but regained physical activity within 24 hours of administration.
2	7000	1/3	33.33	33.33% mortality was observed. Surviving animals were weak, depressed and calm. They also did not completely regain physical activity within 24 hours of administration.
3	10000	3/3	100.00	Rats were initially calm and depressed and 100% mortality was observed by the end of 24 hours of administration.

Figure 3: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum levels of ALP in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 4: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum total protein levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

3 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Sera Antioxidant Status in Male Wistar Rats

In this study, the rats administered varying doses of the extract exhibited significant ($P < 0.05$) increases in

compared to the control (Figure 13).

Figure 5: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum albumin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 6: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum total bilirubin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

serum levels of SOD, CAT, GSH, and GPx, in a dose dependent manner when compared to the control groups. However, at the 800 mg/kg dose, serum levels of SOD and GSH were decreased but not statistically ($P > 0.05$) significant when compared to the 400 mg/kg group (Figures 14, 15, 16, 17). Additionally, serum levels of MDA were significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced in a dose dependent manner in all treatment groups when compared to the control (Figure 18).

Figure 7: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum globulin levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 8: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum urea concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

4 Effect of Varying Doses of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf on Kidney Homogenate Supernatant and Antioxidant Status in Male Wistar Rats

In this study, rats administered varying doses of the extract showed significant increases ($P < 0.05$) in the antioxidant status of kidney homogenates, as evidenced by elevated levels of SOD, CAT, GSH, and GPx, in a dose-dependent manner compared to the control groups (Figures 19, 20, 21, 22). Additionally, the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the kidney homogenates were significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$) in a dose-dependent manner across all treatment groups

Figure 9: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum creatinine concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 11: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on chloride ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 10: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on sodium ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 12: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on potassium ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

compared to the control (Figure 23).

5 Histopathological Assessment of Liver and Kidney Ultrastructures Following Administration of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* Leaf

5.1 Liver

Histological analysis of liver sections from rats administered 200, 400, and 800 mg/kg of the extract revealed essentially normal histology, similar to the control group. Sections of the liver in all the groups showed normal hepatic histomorphology, lacking any

signs of acute or chronic damage, and portal tracts without significant inflammation (Plates 1a, b, c, and d). Normal hepatic lobules consisting of hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins were observed. Likewise, the structures of the portal triads were normal.

Group 1 (Control)

Plate 1a: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the control group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic

Figure 13: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum bicarbonate ion concentrations in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 14: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum SOD levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 15: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum CAT levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 16: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum GSH levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 2 (200 mg/kg)

Plate 1b: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 200 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 3 (400 mg/kg)

Plate 1c: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 400 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic

lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Group 4 (800 mg/kg)

Plate 1d: The photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 800 mg/kg treated group revealed normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules appeared normal, with hepatocytes arranged in interconnecting cords around the central veins. Additionally, the structures of the portal triads were normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery

Figure 17: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum GPx levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 19: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on SOD of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 18: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on serum MDA levels in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 20: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on CAT of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

(HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

5.2 Kidney

Histological analysis of the kidney sections from rats administered the varying doses of the extract revealed essentially normal histology, similar to the control group. Sections of the kidney in the various groups showed normal renal histomorphology, with no indications of glomerular damage or acute or chronic tubular damage (Plates 2a, b, c, and d). Normal glomeruli in their respective Bowman's capsules were observed, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules (proximal convoluted tubules, pars recta, distal convoluted tubules, and collecting ducts) in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix.

Group 1 (Control)

Plate 2a: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the control group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Group 2 (200 mg/kg)

Plate 2b: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 200 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli

Figure 21: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on GSH of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 23: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on MDA of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 22: Effect of different doses of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf on GPx of kidney homogenate supernatant in male Wistar rats. Data sharing the same lower-case letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), whereas data with different lower-case letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

Group 4 (800 mg/kg)

Plate 2d: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 800 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Group 3 (400 mg/kg)

Plate 2c: The photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 400 mg/kg treated group displayed normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules were seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

6 Discussion

The phytochemical evaluation of *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract reveals a rich presence of bioactive compounds with diverse pharmacological properties. The extract contains a diverse array of phytochemicals, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids. This finding aligns with those reported by Ebenyi et al. (2021) regarding the phytochemical analysis of aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf, as well as by Igbinauwa et al. (2011) and Oyewole et al. (2011) concerning the phytochemical analysis of the methanol extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf.

In this study, alkaloids are present in moderate amounts. Medicinal plants generally contain alkaloids in the range of 10 to 50 mg per 100 grams. This extract, with an alkaloid content of 27.15 mg per 100 grams, falls within the typical range, suggesting a moderate level that could effectively provide therapeutic benefits like pain relief and anticancer activity without being excessively toxic. Alkaloids

Figure 24: Plate 1a: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the control group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Figure 25: Plate 1b: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 200 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

are recognized for their analgesic, antimalarial, antimicrobial, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory properties (Heinrich et al., 2021).

Plants known for their astringent and antimicrobial qualities typically contain tannin levels ranging from 5 to 20 mg/100g. The 7.63 mg/100g tannin content in this extract falls towards the lower limit of this range, indicating its potential to deliver advantageous antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits while reducing the risk of excessive astringency. Tannins exhibit astringent, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial characteristics (Kováč et al., 2022).

Flavonoids are powerful antioxidants known for their anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and anticancer properties (Hasnat et al., 2024). In medicinal plants, flavonoid content generally ranges from 20 to 50 mg/100g. With a flavonoid content of 39.18 mg/100g, this extract is on the higher end of the spectrum, suggesting it has significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential. This makes the extract beneficial for preventing diseases related to oxidative stress and for managing inflammation.

Plants recognized for their potent antioxidant properties usually have phenol content ranging from 30 to 70 mg/100g. This extract, with a phenol content of 46.07 mg/100g, falls within this typical range, indicating substantial antioxidant properties that can aid in the prevention and management

of diseases linked to oxidative stress, such as cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Phenols are powerful antioxidants that protect against oxidative damage and help reduce the risk of chronic diseases (Kostić et al., 2023).

Typically, medicinal plants have terpenoid levels ranging from 1 to 10 mg/100g. The terpenoid content of 5.41 mg/100g in this extract falls within this anticipated range, suggesting potential benefits in reducing inflammation, fighting infections, and possibly inhibiting cancer cell growth. Terpenoids exhibit anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antimicrobial properties (Masyita et al., 2022).

Plants known for their health benefits typically contain saponin levels ranging from 20 to 60 mg/100g. With a saponin content of 33.10 mg/100g falling within this usual range, the extract shows promise in managing cholesterol levels, boosting immune function, and potentially preventing cancer. Saponins are recognized for their ability to lower cholesterol, enhance immune response, and exhibit anticancer properties (Juang & Liang, 2020).

Cardiotonic plants typically have cardiac glycoside levels between 1 and 5 mg/100g. This extract contains 4.83 mg/100g of cardiac glycosides, which falls towards the higher end of the usual range. This suggests a robust potential for cardiotonic effects that can be beneficial in the management of heart failure and arrhythmias (Škubník et al., 2021). Cardiac

Figure 26: Plate 1c: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 400 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m.* Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

Figure 27: Plate 1d: Photomicrograph of the sectioned liver from the 800 mg/kg treated group, revealing normal hepatic histomorphology. The hepatic lobules and portal triads appear normal. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m.* Central veins (V); Portal area (P) consisting of hepatic artery (HA), hepatic vein (HV), and bile duct (BD).

glycosides are employed in treating heart conditions by fortifying cardiac contractions and regulating heart rhythm.

Plants with anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects typically have steroid levels ranging from 1 to 10 mg/100g. Steroids are known for their anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties (Dembitsky, 2023). The extract's steroid content of 3.80 mg/100g falls within this anticipated range, indicating potential advantages in reducing inflammation and modulating immune responses. This could be valuable in treating inflammatory and autoimmune conditions like rheumatoid arthritis and type 1 diabetes.

The acute toxicity study of *Jatropha tanjorensis* in Wistar rats provided valuable insights into the safety profile of the plant extract. The absence of mortality and maintained physical stability at doses up to 6000 mg/kg indicates that *Jatropha tanjorensis* extract is relatively non-toxic at lower doses. This suggests a high margin of safety for potential therapeutic use within this dose range. At 7000 mg/kg, a significant increase in mortality rate (33.33%) indicates that toxicity begins to manifest at this dose. While the majority of mice survived, the onset of mortality at this level signals a threshold for adverse effects, highlighting the importance of dose regulation. Complete mortality at 10,000 mg/kg demonstrates that this dose is highly toxic and

lethal. This drastic increase in mortality confirms a critical toxic threshold and emphasizes that doses approaching this level are dangerous and unsafe for use. The LD50 value (the dose at which 50% of the test population is expected to die) of 7745.97 mg/kg indicates the median lethal dose. This relatively high LD50 value suggests that the extract has a broad therapeutic index and is relatively safe at lower doses. The LD50 value is crucial for determining the safety margin and guiding dosage levels for further studies and potential therapeutic applications. This finding is consistent with the report by Ebenyi et al. (2021), which observed no behavioural changes or mortality at oral doses of 2,000 and 5,000 mg/kg within the first 24 hours and during a 14-day study period following administration of an aqueous extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf. Similarly, Igbinaaduwa et al. (2011) reported no mortality or signs of behavioural changes or toxicity in mice and rats after administering methanol extract of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf at doses up to 8,000 mg/kg body weight.

ALT (Alanine aminotransferase) and AST (Aspartate aminotransferase) are enzymes that are commonly used as biomarkers for liver function (McGill, 2016; Chinnappan et al., 2023). The lack of significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in serum ALT and AST levels suggests that the extract, at the administered doses, does not cause hepatocellular damage or stress. This outcome aligns with Ezendiokwere et al.'s

Figure 28: Plate 2a: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the control group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 µm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Figure 29: Plate 2b: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 200 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 µm*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

2023 study, which examined the Acute and Subacute Toxicity Profile of Diethyl ether Extract from *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf in Male Wistar Rats. This indicates that the extract is not hepatotoxic. This implies that the extract's hepatoprotective properties may stem from its tannin content. Tannins are recognized for their antioxidant abilities, capable of scavenging free radicals and mitigating oxidative stress in cells, including those in the liver. By shielding liver cells from oxidative harm, tannins may play a role in preserving the typical levels of ALT and AST (Sobeh et al., 2017; Abu et al., 2022). While the precise mechanisms remain somewhat unclear, it's theorized that tannins might influence enzyme activity in liver cells, including ALT and AST, contributing to the maintenance of serum levels within normal ranges.

ALP (Alkaline phosphatase) is another enzyme associated with liver function (McGill, 2016; Chinnappan et al., 2023), but it can also indicate bone and other tissue-related activity (Fernandez, 2007; Haarhaus et al., 2022). The significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in ALP levels suggests that the extract might have an inhibitory effect on ALP activity. This result is consistent with the findings of Chibuogwu et al. (2021) and Ezendiokwere et al. (2023). The presence of the phytochemicals (flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and terpenoids), through their combined antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and

enzyme-modulating properties, could be responsible for the significant reduction in ALP levels observed in the study. This effect can be beneficial in managing conditions where elevated ALP levels are a concern, such as liver diseases or bone disorders (Singab et al., 2005; Sobeh et al., 2017; Abu et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2019). The dose-dependent response, with the most significant reduction at 400 mg/kg, indicates that the extract's effect is potent and potentially dose-related.

Total protein and albumin are indicators of nutritional status and liver function (Keller, 2019). An increase in these parameters suggests that the extract might have a positive effect on protein synthesis or overall nutritional status. This could indicate an anabolic effect or improved liver function in terms of protein production. This result also aligns with the findings of Ezendiokwere et al. (2023).

Bilirubin is a byproduct of the breakdown of red blood cells and is processed by the liver (Guerra Ruiz et al., 2021). Normal levels of bilirubin indicate proper liver function and red blood cell turnover. The lack of significant changes in bilirubin levels further supports the conclusion that the extract does not adversely affect liver function at the administered doses.

The significant reduction in serum cholesterol,

Figure 30: Plate 2c: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 400 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

Figure 31: Plate 2d: Photomicrograph of the sectioned kidney from the 800 mg/kg treated group displaying normal renal histomorphology. Normal glomeruli within their respective Bowman's capsules are seen, surrounded by numerous normal renal tubules in a highly vascularized connective tissue matrix. *H.E x200 magnification / Bar: 50 μ m*. Glomeruli (G); Renal tubules (arrow); Blood capillary (BC).

triglycerides, and LDL levels in the treated groups suggests that the extract has a lipid-lowering effect. This outcome aligns with the report of Akinloye et al. (2017) which examined the acute toxicity and antioxidant effects of *Jatropha tanjorensis* methanol extract in Wistar rats. This result is consistent with the hypolipidemic activity of several of the phytochemicals present in the extract, such as flavonoids and saponins. These compounds are known to have lipid-lowering properties, possibly through mechanisms involving inhibition of lipid absorption, enhanced lipid metabolism, or modulation of lipid-regulating enzymes (Juang & Liang, 2020; Hasnat et al., 2024). The observed reduction in LDL (Low-Density Lipoprotein) levels is particularly notable, as elevated LDL is a known risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. The decrease in LDL levels indicates a potential cardioprotective effect of the extract. The significant reduction in serum cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL levels with the highest dose (400 mg/kg) demonstrating the most pronounced effect suggests a dose-dependent response. This implies that higher doses of the extract may lead to more substantial improvements in lipid profiles.

HDL (High-Density Lipoprotein) is often referred to as "good cholesterol" because it helps remove other forms of cholesterol from the bloodstream (FERENCE et al., 2017). The lack of significant changes in

HDL levels suggests that while the extract effectively lowers total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL, it does not adversely affect HDL levels. This is beneficial because maintaining or increasing HDL levels is generally desirable for cardiovascular health.

The extract's capacity to lower LDL cholesterol without significantly altering HDL levels highlights its potential as a natural remedy for improving lipid profiles and enhancing cardiovascular health.

7 Conclusion

The comprehensive phytochemical and toxicological evaluation of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract conducted in this study provides valuable insights into its safety profile and potential health benefits. The phytochemical analysis revealed a rich presence of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, and steroids, which are known for their diverse pharmacological properties. The acute toxicity study in Wistar rats demonstrated that the extract is relatively non-toxic at lower doses, with an LD50 value of 7745.97 mg/kg, indicating a broad therapeutic index. The biochemical analysis of liver function markers (ALT, AST, and ALP) and lipid profile parameters (cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and HDL) suggested that the extract does not cause hepatocellular damage and has a lipid-lowering effect,

particularly at higher doses. These findings align with previous studies and support the potential use of *Jatropha tanjorensis* leaf extract as a safe and effective natural remedy for managing various health conditions. Further research is needed to elucidate the precise mechanisms of action and to explore its potential therapeutic applications in clinical settings.

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Green Synthesized Iron Nanoparticles Using *Gongronema latifolium* Leaf Extract: Characterization, Antioxidant, and Antidiabetic Activities

Ekozin, A. A.^{1*}, Isola, O. B.¹, Inetianbor, O. C.², Omondiale, S. O.¹, Omojoyegbe, R. T.³, Okanlawon, T. S.³

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

²Chemistry Department, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

³Department of Biological Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 9132750059 Email: ekozinadriel@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Green nanoparticles are derived from natural sources possessing unique properties for biomedical applications. Inhibition of key enzymes (-amylase and -glucosidase) involved in the digestion of starch and protection against free radicals and lipid peroxidation could be part of the therapeutic approach towards the management of hyperglycemia. The study was carried out to synthesize and characterize Iron Oxide nanoparticles coated with ethanolic leaf extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (Gl-FeONPs) using highly advanced techniques for its use as antioxidant and antidiabetic. The study compared the in vitro antioxidant capacities of ethanolic leaf extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (Et-Gl), iron oxide nanoparticles (FeONPs) and Gl-FeONPs by evaluating the Metal Chelating Activity (MCA), Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity (NOSA), Ferric Reducing Ability Power (FRAP) and Lipid Peroxidation (LPO). The in-vitro anti-diabetic capacities were determined against -amylase and -glucosidase. Results showed that, Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs displayed MCA (IC₅₀= 29.48 - 14.77 g/mL), NOSA (IC₅₀= 2.157 - 1.480 g/mL), FRAP (IC₅₀= 10.658 - 4.352 g/mL), LPO (14.17 - 94.38%), -amylase (IC₅₀= 2.81 - 4.83 mg/mL), and -glucosidase (IC₅₀= 2.02 - 3.52 mg/mL). Overall, Gl-FeONPs indicated the potential to prevent postprandial hyperglycemia by slowing down carbohydrate hydrolysis and oxidative stress.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, Green nanoparticle, Antioxidant, Anti-diabetic, *Gongronema latifolium*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic condition typified by a lack of insulin action, production, or both, which results in hyperglycemia (Cole Florez, 2020). Chronic hyperglycemia (high blood sugar) with problems with major macromolecule metabolism is the outcome of its lack. Diabetes mellitus can cause long-term harm, malfunction, and organ failure, particularly to the liver, kidneys, eyes, nerves, heart, pancreas, eyes (retinopathy), kidneys (nephropathy), and blood vessels (Deshpande et al., 2008). According to recent estimates, there were 455 million diabetics globally in 2017, and by 2045, that number is predicted to rise to 693 million. It was also shown that around 50% of diabetics go undiagnosed. The cost of treating diabetic patients was predicted to be USD 850 billion worldwide in the same year (Ganasegeran et al., 2020). It is

estimated that 11.2 million Nigerians, or 5.77% of the population, have diabetes (Uloko et al., 2018). Because the digestible polysaccharides do not absorb glucose quickly, causing a hyperglycemic peak, the nutrition approach successfully lowers postprandial glycemia (Srisongkram et al., 2022). α -amylase is essential for the digestion of polysaccharides. The absorption of monosaccharides (such as glucose or maltose) and abrupt high glycemic peaks, which lower insulin sensitivity, are prevented by inhibition of these two enzymes (Alqahtani et al., 2019). A family of oral hypoglycemic medications known as alpha-glucosidase inhibitors alters how carbohydrates are absorbed in the intestines, lowering blood glucose levels. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is treated with them (Alqahtani et al., 2019). Patients who are overweight or obese may benefit from lowering their blood glucose absorption through food modification (Kaur

et al., 2021). Synthetic substances such as acarbose, miglitol, and voglibose are utilized in clinical settings. However, some of these substances' side effects might include gastrointestinal (GI) abnormalities, such as bloating, abdominal discomfort, GI cramps, or diarrhea (Dirir et al., 2022). More promising than synthetic medicines (such as acarbose or voglibose) for decreasing postprandial glycemia with fewer side effects such as bloating, stomach discomfort, and diarrhea are natural items that may block α -amylase and α -glucosidase activity (Alqahtani et al., 2019; Kaur et al., 2021; Dirir et al., 2022).

Free radicals cause oxidative stress, which builds up in the body and causes reactive oxygen and nitrogen species to accumulate (Teleanu et al., 2022). This disrupts normal aging processes and causes a variety of metabolic abnormalities. These free radicals are produced either naturally during human metabolism or as a result of ultraviolet radiation and chemical pollutants in the environment. Excessive free radicals, DNA damage, and cell malignancy are all directly linked to the development of cancer, according to scientific investigations (Yang et al., 2022). A major contributing component in the development of type II diabetes mellitus has also been identified as oxidative stress. Cost-effective alternatives are urgently needed to lessen the burdens on people and society because the medical therapy for these diseases is extremely expensive (Teleanu et al., 2022). In other words, antioxidants are molecules that diminish or stop the effects of free radicals. Antioxidants are substances that shield cells from the harm produced by free radicals. Free radicals receive electrons from them, which lessens their reactivity. Many plants and animals create anti-oxidants to prevent oxidation from damaging healthy cells or making damaged cells worse (Achan et al., 2011). Plant-derived substances have been of great interest due to their versatile applications (Krishnamurti Rao, 2016).

Gongronema latifolium is a native of Esanland, Edo State, Nigeria. It is often referred to as "Utezi" in Esanland and "arokeke" in Yoruba communities in Nigeria (Okon et al., 2022). In addition to being consumed raw or as a vegetable in soup, *G. latifolium* has been used extensively in folk medicine to help maintain normal blood glucose levels (Ojo et al., 2020; Omonhinmin et al., 2022). The residents of Edo State, Nigeria's Esanland are well-known for consuming a lot of vegetables, some of

which are included in meals taken under particular circumstances, such as illness or during recovery periods (Omonhinmin et al., 2022).

Modern technology development frequently focuses on the provision of healthcare as a fundamental human right (Anjum et al., 2021). Nanotechnology stands out among all cutting-edge technologies for its success in guaranteeing high-quality medical care. Although nanotechnology has many applications across many industries, it is particularly capable of using nanoparticles to encapsulate medications (Adewuyi et al., 2018). Utilizing plant extracts to synthesize metallic nanoparticles is a promising approach since it has shown to be less expensive, safer, faster, simpler, and easier than traditional approaches (Adeyemi et al., 2022). The green synthesis of iron nanoparticles and their biomedical applications have been extensively reported (Kalpana et al., 2018; Vijayakumar et al., 2022). However, there are synthesis methods and important properties and characteristics that still need to be investigated. Therefore, in this study we synthesized iron nanoparticles using *G. latifolium* extract as a reducing agent in the redox synthesis of the nanomaterials. We characterized the nanostructures by spectroscopic and microscopic analyses and studied their in-vitro free radical scavenging activities. We also demonstrated the in vitro screening of α -amylase inhibitory activities. Moreover, the results here described give insight towards the development of novel and more effective antioxidant and antidiabetic therapies for different applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

In the current research, the leaves of *Gongronema latifolium* were selected based on the ethno-medicinal claims of the Esan tribe of the Edo people, Nigeria. The leaves of *G. latifolium* were retrieved from the forest located in Ogwa village. The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr. E.S. Osagie, Technical Officer, Plant Genetic Resources, University of Benin. Herbariums were deposited at JNTBGRI (TBGT 86816/dated November 25, 2022).

Preparation of Extracts

Gongronema latifolium was freshly collected, washed thoroughly with distilled water, and left to dry for two weeks. The leaves were homogenized by a

mechanical blender, model TT-I777. The resulting powdered leaves were macerated with ethanol and distilled water solvents. This solution was left for 72 hours to ensure proper concentration. The solution was appropriately filtered using a mesh-like structure. The plant solutes were properly disposed of while the subsequent filtered solvent underwent extraction and concentration to extract the initially present ethanol and to concentrate the plant extract using a rotary evaporator, vacuum pump, and water bath simultaneously.

Synthesis of Iron Nanoparticle Coated with Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (GI-FeONPs)

According to Ali et al. (2016), GI-FeONPs were prepared as follows: 3.33 g of Iron(III) Chloride hexahydrate and 1.5 g of Iron(II) Chloride were dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water. The solution was mixed under dry gas in an oven at 80°C for 10 minutes. Subsequently, 15 mL of plant extract was added drop-wise into the mixture under continuous stirring for 10 minutes. After 5 minutes, 60 mL of 1 M NaOH was added to the solution. The reaction further proceeded until the color of the solution, which was initially yellow, transformed to dark brown.

Characterization of Iron Nanoparticle Coated with Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *Gongronema latifolium* (GI-FeONPs)

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analysis was used to identify the functional group of FeONPs (Perkin Elmer, 147 spectrum RSI 83303). The components were mixed with KBr, shaped into pellets, and then inspected at a wavelength of 400–4,500 cm^{-1} .

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM (JEOL.JSM-6360LV.149, Japan) was used to examine surface morphology. Powdered FeONPs were encapsulated in gold by fully utilizing the sputtering method. The SEM study was employed to improve electrical conductivity and the quality of the green nanoparticle. This was conducted at 151 micrographs.

Zeta Potential Analysis

Zeta potential is a measure of the electric charge or the electric potential difference between the surfaces of a particle suspended in a liquid medium. It provides

information about the stability and behavior of the particle in a dispersion.

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

In vitro antioxidant activity of *G. latifolium*, the green nanoparticle (GI-FeONPs), and Iron oxide nanoparticles (FeONPs) was evaluated using standard procedures as mentioned below.

Metal Chelating Activity (MCA)

The MCA was determined using the spectrophotometric method as depicted by Dinis et al. (1994). The reaction mixture, which contains 0.5 mL of GI-FeONPs (50–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), 1.6 mL of distilled water, 0.05 mL of FeCl_3 (2 mM), and 0.1 mL of 1,10-phenanthroline (5 mM), was incubated at 40°C for 10 minutes, and the absorbance was measured at 562 nm. The metal chelating activity of the extracts was also measured as described above. Furthermore, a similar protocol was carried out for FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50–500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and ascorbic acid was used as the standard. The percentage metal chelating activity was determined using the formula:

$$\text{MCA (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Activity (NOSA)

The scavenging effect on nitric oxide ($\text{NO}\cdot$) radical was measured according to the method of Marcocci et al. (1994). 0.5 mL of the leaf extract was added in the test tubes to 1 mL of sodium nitroprusside solution (25 mM) and the tubes incubated at 37°C for 2 hours. An aliquot (0.5 mL) of the incubation solution was removed and diluted with 0.3 mL of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide in 5% H_3PO_4 and 0.1% naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride). The absorbance of the chromophore formed was immediately read at 570 nm against deionized water as blank with catechin (50 μg) used as standard. Results were expressed as percentage radical scavenging activity (RSA):

$$\text{NOSA (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP)

This was estimated using the method of Bensie Strain (1996). 2.5 mL of 200 mM of phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) and 2.5 mL of 1% $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ were

added to various concentrations of the extract. The mixture was incubated for 2 minutes at 50°C and then centrifuged at 1000 g for 8 minutes. 5 mL of the supernatant was then mixed with 5 mL of distilled water and 1 mL of 0.1% FeCl₃. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at a wavelength of 700 nm. Catechin was used as the standard.

Total Antioxidant Capacity (TAC)

Total antioxidant capacity of Et-GI was performed according to procedures outlined by Halliwell (1990). 0.1 mL of sample were mixed with 1 mL of the reagents solution (4 mM ammonium molybdate, 28 mM sodium phosphate, and 0.6 M sulfuric acid). The tubes were incubated for 90 minutes at 95°C. When the samples were cooled to room temperature, the absorbance of the aqueous solution was quantitatively determined at 695 nm.

Anti-Lipid Peroxidant Activity

The anti-lipid peroxidation effects of Et-GI, FeONPs, and GI-FeONPs were evaluated in vitro by the method of Suja et al. (2004). 0.5 g of rat liver tissue was sliced and homogenized with 10 mL of 150 mM KCl-Tris-HCl-buffer (pH 7.2). The reaction mixture contained 0.25 mL of liver homogenate, 0.05 mL of 0.1 mM ascorbic acid (AA), 0.1 mL of Tris-HCl-buffer (pH 7.2), and 0.05 mL of various concentrations of plant extract/serial fraction. The mixture was kept for incubation at 37°C for 1 hour. After that, 0.2 mL of 9.8% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), 0.5 mL of 0.1 N HCl, 0.9 mL of distilled water, and 2 mL of 0.6% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) were added to each of the tubes and shaken vigorously. The tubes were placed in a boiling water bath at 100°C for half an hour. The flocculent precipitate formed after cooling was removed by addition of 5 mL of n-butanol and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 523 nm. Malondialdehyde (MDA) produced was expressed as % Control.

In Vitro Anti-Diabetic Activity

Determination of α -Amylase Inhibition

The inhibition of α -amylase activity was measured using the spectrophotometric method described by Anigboro et al. (2021). The GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL) respectively, 0.5 mL of α -amylase, were incubated for 10 minutes at 37°C, then 5 μ L of 1% starch was added, incubated for 10 minutes at 50°C,

thereafter 200 μ L DNS, incubated in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes and cooled; 3 mL of distilled water was added and absorbance read at 540 nm. Additionally, the same procedure was followed while working with FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), and acarbose was used as the standard. The percentage α -amylase inhibitory activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of control (without GI-FeONPs/standard) and A_1 is the absorbance in the presence of GI-FeONPs. The IC₅₀ value was calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Determination of α -Glucosidase Inhibition

The inhibition of α -glucosidase activity was measured using the spectrophotometric method as described by Anigboro et al. (2021). The GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), 100 μ L of α -glucosidase in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.9) was incubated at 25°C for 10 minutes. 50 μ L of 5 mM p-nitrophenol and 1 mL of 1% starch solution in 0.1 M phosphate buffer was added, the mixture was incubated at 25°C for 5 minutes and read at 405 nm. Additionally, the same procedure was followed while working with GI-FeONPs (0.5 mL, 50-500 μ g/mL), and acarbose was used as the standard. The percentage α -glucosidase inhibitory activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \right) \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of control (without GI-FeONPs/standard) and A_1 is the absorbance in the presence of GI-FeONPs. The IC₅₀ value was calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Statistical Analysis

All assays were performed in triplicates and results expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Experimental data were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

1 Results and Discussions

Nanoparticles are very effective for drug transportation and delivery, particularly because they can precisely locate and carry encapsulated medicines to diseased cells (Nasimi & Haidari,

2013). The absorption and bio-distribution capacity is determined by the analysis of the chemical and physical properties of the nanoparticles, such as size, shape, and surface charge (Umrani & Paknikar, 2014; Manne et al., 2020).

FTIR analysis was carried out to determine the different functional groups present in Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs. The conspicuous wavelengths present were 3454 cm^{-1} , 2913 cm^{-1} , 2847 cm^{-1} , 2480 cm^{-1} , 1775 cm^{-1} , 1636 cm^{-1} , 1452 cm^{-1} , and 871 cm^{-1} , corresponding to functional groups O-H Stretching indicating an alcohol group, O-H and N-H Stretching indicating an alcohol and primary amine group respectively, S-H Stretching indicating a thiol group, C-H Bending indicating an alkane functional group, C=C Stretching and N-H bending indicating α, β -unsaturated ketone, C-H Bending indicating an alkane. For Gl-FeONPs, the wavelengths at 3454 cm^{-1} , 2906 cm^{-1} , 2847 cm^{-1} , 1749 cm^{-1} , 1550 cm^{-1} , and 1379 cm^{-1} correspond to O-H Stretching indicating an alcohol functional group, O-H and N-H Stretching indicating an alcohol and primary amine group respectively, C-H Bending indicating an alkane group, N-O Stretching indicating the presence of nitro compounds, and O-H Bending indicating an alcohol functional group respectively. Similar observations were reported by Bensie & Strain (1996). FTIR studies of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs were performed to characterize the chemical nature of the nanoparticles.

nanoparticle by providing information about its size, shape, and morphology. The surface morphology of the green nanoparticle (Gl-FeONPs) was examined by SEM due to its capability of detecting scattered electrons from the particle's surface. The SEM images show that the particle size, calculated to be 5.0 m (5000 nm), was dispersed at 5% by mass. The SEM pictures confirm the formation of Gl-FeONPs, showing the spherical shape of the nanoparticles. Similar observations were reported by Mirza et al. (2019) for zinc oxide nanoparticles coated with plant extracts.

Figure 2: The SEM image for Gl-FeONPs with 4500 magnification.

Zeta potential is a measure of the electric charge or the electric potential difference between the surfaces of the particle suspended in a liquid medium. It provides information about the stability and behavior of the particle in a dispersion. A Zeta-potential of $-50\text{ millivolts (mV)}$ indicates that the negative charge arises from the presence of functional groups or ions on the surface of the particles, which can be either naturally occurring or intentionally introduced through surface modification or functionalization. The magnitude of the zeta potential provides information about the stability and behavior of the particle in dispersion. Generally, larger absolute values of zeta-potential indicate greater stability, as the repulsion between particles with similar charges prevents them from aggregating or flocculating. Gl-FeONPs showed a zeta-potential of -50 mV , indicating a relatively high degree of stability for the dispersion of FeONPs. Similar observations were made by Hu et al. (2021). The Zeta potential can be used to optimize the formulations of suspensions, emulsions, protein solutions, as well as predict interactions with surfaces.

In this study, the antioxidant activity of Et-Gl,

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs. The curve shows the emission spectra of Et-Gl (blue line) and Gl-FeONPs (green line).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is a technique employed to determine the surface morphology of the

Figure 3: The ZETA Potential plot for Gl-FeONPs at pH 2-5.

FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were investigated in vitro. As excess free heavy metals have been implicated in the induction and formation of free radicals in vivo, Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were tested in a metal chelating assay in a concentration range of 50-500 mg/mL respectively. Although Et-Gl at 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ indicated no inhibition of the chelating of heavy metals, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs showed dose-dependent inhibitions of metal chelators utilizing ascorbic acid as a standard control. The in vitro metal chelating activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 4, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The IC_{50} value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 29.48 g/mL, 871.67 g/mL, and 14.77 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC_{50} was 24.445 g/mL. The metal chelating activity assay works on the principle of reduction/chelation of metals participating in redox reactions. Hence, Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs were observed to be effective chelators of ferrous ion radicals compared to ascorbic acid. Similar observations were made by Faisal et al. (2021).

The nitric oxide scavenging assay (NOSA) is based on the principle that sodium nitroprusside in aqueous solution at physiological pH spontaneously generates nitric oxide, which reacts with oxygen to yield nitrite ions that can be estimated using Griess reagent. In the present study, Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs demonstrated a dose-dependent increase in nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, fully utilizing ascorbic acid as a standard control. The in vitro nitric oxide scavenging activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 5, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The graphical trend

Metal Chelating Activity

Figure 4: A plot for metal chelating activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): $P < 0.05$.

of % inhibition against concentration was similar to that of standard ascorbic acid, indicating metal chelating activity of the nanoparticles. The IC_{50} value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 2.157 g/mL, 22.961 g/mL, and 1.480 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC_{50} was 1.838 g/mL. The half-maximal activity (IC_{50}) of Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs was lower than that of the standard respectively. However, FeONPs displayed significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher inhibition in comparison with that of ascorbic acid, which served as a standard for the assay. Similar observations were reported by Abu-Serie & Abdelfattah (2020) for iron nanoparticles, which served as good scavengers of nitric oxide radicals.

Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity

Figure 5: A plot for Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity (NOSA) of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): $P < 0.05$.

Ferric reducing ability power of biologically active compounds are electron donors that can reduce the oxidized intermediates, such as those in the lipid peroxidation processes. It is centered on the reduction of the complex of ferric iron and 2,3,5-triphenyl-1,3,4-triaza-2-azoniacyclopenta-1,4-diene chloride (TPTZ) to the ferrous form at low pH. The in vitro ferric reducing antioxidant power of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 6, with all nanoparticles compared to that of ascorbic acid. The graphical trend of % inhibition against concentration was similar to that of standard ascorbic acid, indicating metal chelating activity of the nanoparticles. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, and Gl-FeONPs were 115.91 g/mL, 332.71 g/mL, and 64.43 g/mL respectively, compared to the standard ascorbic acid whose IC₅₀ was 67.30 g/mL. Et-Gl and Gl-FeONPs displayed a significantly higher inhibition in comparison with that of ascorbic acid, which served as a standard for the assay. Similar observations were made by Rajput et al. (2013) for zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from plant extracts, which served as good ferric-reducing agents.

Figure 6: A plot for Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs, and Ascorbic acid. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ascorbic Acid): P \leq 0.05.

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is a measure of the overall antioxidant capacity of a substance or biological sample. The TAC assay measures the ability of a substance to neutralize free radicals or inhibit oxidative reactions. It provides an overall assessment of the cumulative antioxidant activity of the sample. The working principle of measuring the total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is based on the ability of antioxidants to neutralize or inhibit the harmful effects of free radicals by subjecting the ethanolic plant extract (Et-Gl) to a specific assay that assesses

its ability to counteract or scavenge free radicals. Using the garlic acid equivalent which is a standard for determining the total anti-oxidant capacity, the TAC was estimated to be 1.8 mg, indicating the plant quantitatively contained 1.8 mg of antioxidant properties. This correlates with findings by Gulcin (2020).

Anti-lipid peroxidation mechanisms aim to prevent or interrupt this chain reaction by neutralizing or scavenging the free radicals or ROS that initiate lipid peroxidation. Overall, the working principle of anti-lipid peroxidation involves the use of antioxidants and other mechanisms to neutralize free radicals, scavenge ROS, and interrupt the chain reaction of lipid peroxidation. By protecting cell membranes and lipid components, anti-lipid peroxidation strategies aim to prevent oxidative damage and maintain cellular integrity, and assess the impact of antioxidants on health and disease. The in vitro anti-lipid peroxidant activity of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs are shown in Figure 7. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were 37.298 g/mL, 96.310 g/mL and 32.829 g/mL respectively. In the present study, Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs demonstrated a dose-dependent increase in the anti-lipid peroxidation activity corresponding with Ali et al. (2020) who demonstrated that iron nanoparticles coated with *Aframomum angustifolium* were capable of inhibiting the formation of Malondialdehyde (MDA) products.

Figure 7: A plot for Anti-lipid peroxidant Activity (ALPO) of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Ibuprofen): P \leq 0.05.

Consistent management of blood glucose is one of the effective strategies for combating type II diabetes mellitus. Postprandial blood glucose level

risers due to the activity of carbohydrate hydrolyzing and degrading enzymes: pancreatic α -amylase and intestinal α -glucosidase. Inhibitors of these enzymes are currently used as oral hypoglycemic drugs for the control of hyperglycemia, especially in patients with type II diabetes mellitus. The inhibitors delay the release of monosaccharide from polysaccharides present in food (Oboh et al., 2012; Awioroko et al., 2020). Alpha-amylase is a pancreatic enzyme involved in the degradation of starch. The inhibition of Alpha-amylase activity helps in managing diabetes mellitus and in reducing postprandial blood glucose (Manne et al., 2020). The addition of α -amylase to a reaction mixture of starch and water produces maltose which serves as the substrate for the reaction, dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) served as an indicator for the product formed. Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were analyzed for alpha-amylase activity in a concentration range of 1–3 μ g/mL. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were 4.85 and 2.50 mg/mL respectively, compared to the standard acarbose whose IC₅₀ was 3.37 mg/mL. The inhibition of α -amylase by Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs showed little significant differences ($p > 0.05$) from that observed for acarbose. Similar observations were reported by Anigboro et al. (2021).

Figure 8: α -Amylase inhibitory activities of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Acarbose): ($P > 0.05$).

Alpha-glucosidase is an intestinal enzyme that breaks down monosaccharides and starch into glucose (Peng et al., 2016). The inhibition of glucosidase activity helps in managing diabetes mellitus. α -glucosidase catalyzes the conversion of the

substrate 4-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside to α -D-glucopyranoside and p-nitrophenol. Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs were analyzed for α -glucosidase activity in a concentration range of 1–3 mg/mL with no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) from that observed for acarbose. The IC₅₀ value of Et-Gl, FeONPs, Gl-FeONPs were 65.42, 55.49 and 25.25 respectively, compared to the standard acarbose whose IC₅₀ was 337.84 μ g/mL. Similar findings were reported by Anigboro et al. (2021).

Figure 9: α -Glucosidase inhibitory activities of Et-Gl, FeONPs and Gl-FeONPs. *Values are expressed as means \pm SD. Compared with control (Acarbose): ($P > 0.05$).

Conclusion

The results of this study indicated that the iron oxide nanoparticles coated with *Gongronema latifolium* (Gl-FeONPs) displayed potent *in vitro* antidiabetic potential. Additionally, their potent antioxidant activity helps combat oxidative stress, which plays a critical role in the progression of diabetes and associated complications. These findings are crucial as they provide insight into the use of green synthesized nanoparticles for the management of diabetes and its related complications. Further *in vivo* studies to ascertain the effect of metabolic reactions are suggested.

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Gene Therapy for Sickle Cell Disease: Present Insights

Lawani, M. O.^{1*}, Enerijiofi, K. E.²

¹Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

²Department of Biological Sciences, College of Basic, Applied and Health Sciences, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7513-4052>

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 9132750059 Email: lawani.mathew@aauekpoma.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is an inherited red blood cell disorder resulting from a single-point mutation. It results in complications such as acute and chronic pain, infections, stroke, kidney disease, and heart failure that reduce the quality of life not only for affected persons but also for their families. It can be treated with drugs and bone marrow transplants, but there is no known cure for it. One of the potential cures is gene therapy, which involves adding, editing or silencing and correcting genes by bioengineering techniques including CRISPR/Cas9 system; zinc finger nucleases (ZNFs); transcription activator-like effector nuclease (TALEN) technology; and base editors. The therapy procedure involves the retrieval of affected genes from patient hematopoietic stem cells, engineering them *ex vivo* and reintroduction into patients as therapeutic genes. Researchers have achieved significant progress in the use of CRISPR technology by, amongst others, repressing BCL11A gene enhancers and editing erroneous genes via base modifications as well as prime edits. This has proven effective in the reduction of adverse impacts that SCD have on patients. Nonetheless, therapeutic genes can cause insertional mutagenesis and cancer after integration into the patient. Finding a significant cure for SCD via gene therapy is in the clinical stage; methods to combat therapeutic cancer-inducing genes, as well as expertise and infrastructure provision, are highly required. Gene therapy for SCD has room for further research and development.

Keywords: SCD, Gene Therapy, CRISPR/Cas9, Mutation, Transplants

1 Introduction

1.1 Brief Overview of Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Its Impact on Affected Individuals

The first description of sickle cell disease (SCD) was given in 1910 by James Herrick, who termed the disease due to abnormally sickle-shaped red blood cells (Herrick, 1910). Sickle cell disease is an inherited blood disorder that affects the production of hemoglobin. The condition makes the red blood cells sickle-shaped, and this may result in blockage of normal flow, which may cause injury or atrophy to vital organs. SCD affects millions of the world's inhabitants, predominantly members of the African population group as well as people descending from Mediterranean and Middle Eastern countries together with Indians. It can lead to multiple complications, such as acute and chronic pain, infections, stroke, kidney disease, and heart failure, resulting in a shorter lifespan. SCD is diagnosed through a blood test and can be treated via drugs, transfusions, and stem cell replacement. Interestingly, no established treatment

is available to cure SCD, and still, many patients are restricted or deprived of getting enough access to quality treatments or research facilities (Brandow & Liem, 2022; The Foundation for Sickle Cell Disease Research; Kato et al., 2016; Yawn et al., 2014).

Imagine people are drowning in water, and inflated boats are needed to rescue them, but some of the boats have broken valves or holes in them, and in the course of rescuing the people, the boats are deflated. The shape of the boats will change, and the people will not be saved. In the same manner, red blood cells are shaped or structured for carrying oxygen; if the subunits of the hemoglobin within them are affected by an abnormal amino acid, their shape will change and the body will lack oxygen. This will in turn weaken the organs of the body, which depend on oxygen to generate ATP via the electron transport chain.

It is important to note that SCD is derived from a one-point mutation. It is explicitly described as a monogenic disorder caused by a single base-pair point mutation in the β -globin gene, replacing valine for glutamic acid in the β -globin chain (Inusa et al.,

Figure 1: A Normal Red Blood Cell and a Sickle Cell

2019). The unusual valine amino acid at position 6 in the beta-globin chain has a weak interaction with the adjacent sickle hemoglobin molecule (Harvard Medical School, 2013). The sickle shape of the red blood cells is due to valine and later results in SCD.

The presence of sickle cell disease results in the emotional drainage of the parents, and this affects interpersonal relationships between them and other family members (Burlaw et al., 1989). A critical review of 116 articles emanating from the search of four different databases focused on the impact of sickle cell disease in Nigeria, and this country was identified as having the highest global burden of sickle cell disease (Adigwe et al., 2023). A cross-sectional survey was used to look at 2,145 SCD patients from seventeen different countries throughout the world. In their statements, the patients testified that the disease imposed a significant load on them regarding their quality of life while they were suffering from it and led to an impairment of their emotional state (Osunkwo et al., 2021). The presence of a sickle cell trait has stopped lovers from having weddings because they are either sickle cell carriers or both partners carry the disease. If a cure for SCD is discovered, the quality of life for patients and carriers will significantly improve. Even though there is no known treatment for sickle cell disease, gene therapy can offer a revolutionary solution to this condition. This review aims to harness information on emerging cures for sickle cell disease via gene therapy.

2 Gene Therapy and Its Potential as a Treatment for SCD

Gene therapy refers to a genetic engineering process through mutated gene alteration, correction, or

specific target modification aimed at treatment (Paulo, 2017). Several gene therapies differ significantly and include the removal of the damaged gene and its replacement with a healthy one, the blocking or suppression of mutated genes, and the introduction of new or modified genes into the organism (FDA, 2022). Gene therapy is used in the management of some inherited diseases like hemophilia and sickle cell disease; however, it can be applied to treat acquired disorders like leukemia (NHGRI, 2022). As a future curative approach, gene therapy is questionable for its effectiveness, making it necessary to conduct sufficient research work, clinical trials, and regulate gene treatment before applying it to patients (MedlinePlus, 2022). Currently, there is no permanent solution to SCD; however, some procedures that can be offered are medicine alongside an allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplant from a healthy donor. SCD is either treated by using drugs or through transplantation; at non-serious levels, patients treat their illnesses with medication, but those with severe cases need a transplant. Nevertheless, some problems may occur because of poor matching and a shortage of blood donors (Dever et al., 2016). As a consequence, it is crucial to have a substantial cure for each type of SCD whether mild or severe. Gene therapy is a possible emerging cure for SCD. It is constituted by hematopoietic (blood-forming) stem cells (HSCs) harvesting, ex vivo modification with a vector gene carrying the normal or antisickling globin gene, and reinfusion after chemotherapy to allow engraftment of the corrected cell (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021).

Allogeneic blood or marrow transplantation is often limited by donor availability and graft-versus-host

Figure 2: Single Point Mutation Leading to the Production of Valine

Figure 3: Steps in HSC Gene Therapy

disease; gene therapy can circumvent these barriers (Kanter & Falcon, 2021). On the other hand, gene therapy has some risks, including insertional mutagenesis, which may result in leukemia or other malignancies (Jones et al., 2021). Advancements in the latest gene editing technologies like CRISPR have made up for decreasing its risks and enhancing the efficiency of gene therapy via exact, long-lasting modifications to the genome. The first CRISPR-edited gene therapy for SCD was approved by the FDA in 2023 (FDA, 2023). Gene therapy remains an experimental and expensive treatment that requires specialized centers and skilled personnel. People with SCD with extreme severity tend to show a high level of risk for gene therapies, but they still need information and counseling to be sufficiently informed about making decisions (ASH, 2023).

2.1 Types of Gene Therapy Currently in Use in SCD and Their Potential Risks and Benefits

There are four main types of gene therapy for SCD: gene addition, gene editing, inactivation or silencing of genes, and gene correction. The strengths and weaknesses of each group depend on safety, effectiveness, and feasibility. Gene therapy for SCD is still at a clinical trial level, and some researchers

have demonstrated success in fetal hemoglobin (HbF) induction with lasting effects associated with relief from transfusions, increased antisickling Hb levels, and prevention of vaso-occlusive crisis (VOC) episodes (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). On the other hand, gene therapy also introduces various barriers and challenges that need to be addressed before it can become a viable option for SCD patients, such as cost, infrastructure, side effects, and social and ethical issues. Gene therapy is not an all-in-one solution, but a targeted and sophisticated intervention that must be guided by personal considerations, inclinations, and hazardous prospects when applied to patients' health (Kanter & Falcon, 2021).

Gene addition refers to the incorporation of a healthy or bioengineered gene into a patient's hematopoietic stem cells using an internal vector, like lentivirus or adeno-associated virus. The goal of gene addition is to increase the expression of normal or antisickling globin genes such as gamma-globin or beta-globin variants (HbA2 or HbG16A). These expressions can impede the effect of sickle globin (HbS) gene expression. Among the different SCD gene therapy techniques, gene addition is the most advanced type that has been scientifically proven to be safe in several clinical trials for reducing vaso-

occlusive crises, transfusion needs, and complications (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). Gene addition therapy relies on the process of lentiviral transduction and applies autologous HSC-targeted gene therapy that binds to proper genes (Dever et al., 2016). Evidence highlights that lentiviral transduction is successful in terms of sustainability and long-term gene expression (Pirona et al., 2020).

Gene editing uses molecular tools to make modifications in the patient's genome. These changes have been beneficial using either zinc finger nucleases or transcription activator-like effector nucleases, among others. Another area of gene editing is using transcription factors to disrupt gene enhancers such as BCL11A or LRF/ZBTB7A, which normally suppress the production of HbF. Gene editing intends to rebalance HbF and HbS or eliminate sickle hemoglobin (HbS) in place of normal beta-globin (HbA). Gene editing is a recent type of gene therapy that still needs several clinical trials and long-term observations to assess its safety and efficiency (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). CRISPR/Cas9 can be used to modify the HbS gene directly. The process involves using a patient's bone marrow cells and editing them in vitro. Genome editing can also reverse the sickling of red blood cells by promoting fetal hemoglobin production (Parc & Bao, 2021).

Gene silencing inhibits the expression of specific genes, including alpha-globin or erythropoietin receptors, associated with SCD pathophysiology. Mediators for this gene silencing include siRNAs and shRNAs. HbS knockdown may revert to normal hemoglobin, abolish or reduce HbS, or modulate the erythroid response in hypoxic and inflammatory conditions. Despite many positive findings, researchers are still at the pre-clinical stage regarding gene silencing for SCD because siRNAs or shRNAs fail to get delivered to target cells and prevent off-target effects (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021). The mechanism involved in gene silencing also includes regulating the expression of a particular gene to keep its synthesis and consequent production of proteins restrained. This therapy is injected into the body, similar to gene editing, which suppresses BCL11A and leads to an increase in HbF while reducing HbS production (Kanter & Falcon, 2021). Gene silencing relies on transfer vectors, similar to gene addition, but targets messenger RNA to suppress gene products rather than cutting the specific sequence as done in

gene editing.

Gene correction uses homologous recombination or base editing to repair the sickle mutation in the beta-globin gene without introducing any foreign DNA. Gene correction can restore normal beta-globin expression and function in the patient's red blood cells. Gene correction is also in preclinical development for SCD, with technical difficulties in achieving high efficiency and specificity of gene repair (Abraham & Tisdale, 2021).

3 Advances in Gene Therapy for SCD

Frangoul et al. (2021) developed a method to treat two extreme genetic abnormalities, namely -thalassemia and sickle cell disease. The scientists utilized an intervention approach by altering specific genes using a gene editing technique based on CRISPR-Cas9 applied to cells from healthy donors. By targeting the BCL11A gene, which reduces fetal hemoglobin production, they managed to alleviate the symptoms of these diseases. After genetic correction, the cells were transplanted back into two separate patients with -thalassemia and sickle cell disease. One year later, both patients showed remarkable improvement with high levels of edited genes in the bone marrow and blood, increased fetal hemoglobin throughout their cell types, no longer needing blood transfusions, and a reduction in painful episodes of sickle cell disease. This implies that the gene editing method using CRISPR-Cas9, targeting the BCL11A gene enhancer, proved effective in treating these genetic disorders, thus offering an alternative avenue for therapeutic intervention.

Zarghamian et al. (2023) focused on using modern DNA technology platforms, including CRISPR-Cas nucleases and base editors, to correct the defective gene resulting in SCD. These tools are designed to restore the production or functionality of fetal hemoglobin (HbF) that can compensate for the mutated hemoglobin (HbS). They discussed various approaches, either by rectifying specific genes responsible for inhibiting HbF formation or by correcting the mutant directly in the hemoglobin gene packaging. They noted that in animal model studies and early-phase human clinical trials, these genetic editing techniques have shown preliminary promise for efficacy and safety.

Levesque and Bauer (2023) commented on a new treatment for sickle cell disease (SCD) and

other blood conditions through the prime editing procedure. CRISPR, and particularly prime editing, is a viable treatment option for the genetic mutation in hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs). Prime editing is a more advanced technique that allows for high-accuracy targeting without causing breaks in the double-stranded structure of the DNA, considered much safer. The conventional prime editing machinery contains a molecular entity called PE2, which is made of Cas9 nickase (an enzyme producing cuts on the DNA) and reverse transcriptase fused. This tool is aided by special RNA molecules targeting the site of interest in the HBB gene. Specific changes are made by the prime editor without requiring a DNA template. To enhance prime editing effectiveness, they incorporated another RNA component (sgRNA) to generate a nuclease-induced DNA break in a single-stranded form. This helps the cell's repair machinery incorporate the desired genetic correction more effectively, although it introduces small genetic changes (indels) at the target site. The advantages of prime editing over other methods, such as base editing, include its ability to target non-dividing stem cells more efficiently and its flexibility in making precise changes without some of the limitations seen in other gene-editing techniques.

Casgevy and Lyfgenia are groundbreaking gene therapies recommended by the FDA for adults with SCD aged 12 and older. Casgevy works by CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing, while Lyfgenia uses lentiviral vectors and modifies the blood stem cells of patients with sickle cell disease to produce healthier hemoglobin that minimizes complications caused by the condition. These are one-time treatments that require pre-transplant chemotherapy and have been proven efficient in clinical trials. Both therapies obtained multiple FDA designations for fast-track development, marking a significant advancement in gene therapy for SCD (FDA, 2023).

4 Challenges and Considerations of Gene Therapy for SCD

Developmental gene therapy, with its goal of curing SCDs, is a complex and expensive application requiring experts. It involves appropriate infrastructure and rigorous clinical trials before it can be safely implemented to enhance human health (MedlinePlus, 2022). Gene therapy also has side or off-target effects, such as insertional mutagenesis,

which can cause cancerous growth, potentially causing more harm than good in improving the health condition of a patient with SCD.

To mitigate the potential for hematologic malignancies (blood cancer) in Casgevy and Lyfgenia gene therapies, a black box warning is included in the labels, particularly for Lyfgenia, and patients will undergo lifelong monitoring. Long-term studies will assess the safety and effectiveness of both treatments (FDA, 2023). Baum et al. (2004) identified several cases of leukemia that were supposedly developed from an attempt to use retroviral transfer as part of clinical gene therapy. This method involved using retroviruses to insert therapeutic genes into blood cells. The issue of blood cancer appeared after the therapeutic genes accidentally activated a regular cell's proto-oncogene, which is an oncogene capable of producing tumors. Hackett et al. (2023) studied the use of the Sleeping Beauty (SB) transposon/transposase system in clinics. They observed that this bioengineering method assists in inserting Chimeric Antigen Receptors (CAR) into T cells. CARs act as navigation guides for T cells to target specific threats, such as cancer. Researchers may adopt this system to test the activity of therapeutic genes against cancer after the introduction of these genes into the patient.

Another possible way to reduce the effect of insertional mutagenesis is to change the type of vector used to insert the therapeutic gene(s). Lentiviral vectors can affect both stem and permanent cells and provide lasting stable gene expressions, but their transfer is not site-specific, which may lead to insertional mutations. The use of adeno-associated viruses is site-specific and safe, making it a preferable option for gene therapy (Zheng et al., 2018). The major drawbacks to developing and employing various types of gene therapies for SCD are not technical but financial. The costs are high for reagents like clinical-grade lentiviral and adeno-associated vectors, gene editing reagents, cell processing materials, personnel costs, and drug research and development costs. If the costs for transfer vectors production, cell processing, and other financially demanding materials improve, the cost of administering gene therapy to patients will decrease (Kohn et al., 2023).

Other difficult questions stemming from the treatment of SCD through gene therapy include

the safety and efficacy of transgenic technologies, the consent process involving informed decisions for patients on this specific level of medical care provision, access and affordability of gene therapy by different socioeconomic groups in society, enhancement or modification of non-disease state traits, and the implications of germline gene editing for future generations. These concerns must be addressed with due deliberation and public participation to ensure that biotechnology, which involves gene therapy, is used appropriately and in a manner that respects both individuals and communities affected by SCD (Kanter & Falcon, 2021; Giacca, 2010; Spink & Geddes, 2004).

5 Conclusion

Gene therapy for sickle cell disease is still in its clinical stage. It has the potential to provide a lasting cure for SCD. It also has the advantage of overcoming the limitations of allogeneic blood transplantation, donor availability, and mismatching challenges. However, it comes with some off-target effects, such as insertional mutations, which may eventually develop into cancer. To mitigate the negative effects of this technique, current gene editing techniques such as CRISPR should be employed. There is also a need for expertise and adequate infrastructure to carry out more research and development in this area.

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Determination of Levels of Heavy Metal in Sub-Soil Around Incinerator in University of Benin Health Centre

Emuokhonun, G. A.¹, Unuigbe, C. A.², Okodugha, V. O.³, Madu, P. C.⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author Tel: +234 7061138733 Email: godwinemuokhonun@aauekpoma.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Incineration of medical waste (MW) is an important alternative way for disposal of this type of hazardous waste. Samples of soil around adopted incinerator and soil within the health center were collected from University of Benin Health Center and soil samples from Capitol (before UNIBEN Chancellor residence) in the same University of Benin was also collected which served as the control site. These studies were carried out in Benin City, Edo state of Nigeria from January 2017 to December 2017. Samples were analyzed for Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn. Samples were collected between the hours of 4pm to 7pm on Fridays of every week for one year. The mean concentrations of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) were determined in the samples. Atomic absorption spectrophotometry was used for heavy metal analysis after digestion using standard methods. The results obtained are: 0.467 ± 0.267 mg/kg, 0.0331 ± 0.049 mg/kg, 0.003 ± 0.005 mg/kg, 0.7251 ± 0.316 mg/kg, 12.4761 ± 0.315 mg/kg, 0.922 ± 0.073 mg/kg for (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe and Mn) respectively for the control site, 0.800 ± 0.374 mg/kg, 0.133 ± 0.098 mg/kg, 0.133 ± 0.098 mg/kg, 1.6191 ± 0.737 mg/kg, 23.467 ± 0.861 mg/kg, 2.465 ± 0.295 mg/kg (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) respectively for the health center and 1.135 ± 0.281 mg/kg, 0.242 ± 0.162 mg/kg, 0.023 ± 0.036 mg/kg, 2.118 ± 0.881 mg/kg, 26.258 ± 1.200 mg/kg, 2.465 ± 0.295 mg/kg (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, Fe, and Mn) respectively for the incinerator site. Data obtained were analyzed using (ANOVA). A probability $\alpha = 0.05$ was considered as significant. P-values at (probability $\alpha = 0.05$) of (Zn - $4.2E-09$), (Pb = 0.007809), (Cd - 0.21624), (Cr = $1.05E-07$), (Fe - $1.13E-23$) and (Mn = $1.44E-15$) except for Pb and Cd, others listed were all less than 0.001, this indicates that the various site/location has a significant effect on the mean concentrations of the various heavy metals. While for Pb and Cd, the various site/location had no effects on their mean concentrations. The results from the site/locations were higher than the control site, indicating a clear case of pollution. Comparison of heavy metal concentration in soil with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that they are all below the set limits. The soils at the adopted medical incinerator had higher concentrations of heavy metals than the soils around the health center. Medical waste, when not properly disposed of, poses a serious threat to public health and should be disposed of appropriately.

Keywords: Incineration, Medical Waste, Heavy Metal, Concentration

1 Introduction

Municipal solid waste management is an area of research that has evolved significantly in developed countries over the years unlike what is obtainable in developing countries. Among the constituents of municipal wastes are medical wastes. Standard medical waste management protocol involves incineration. While this has the advantage of killing pathogens in the waste stream and reducing waste volume and reactivity, incineration has been found to impact on the environment through the release of hazardous combustion products, such as heavy

metals, dioxins and PAHs which have environmental and public health implication. This is of great public concern (Thakur *et al.*, 2023; Tait *et al.*, 2020.). Medical waste incineration involves the burning of waste generated by hospital veterinary facilities and medical research facilities which include infectious medical wastes as well as non-infectious general housekeeping waste.

However there is usually contamination of the surrounding environment with the various release from incineration and uncontrolled disposal of ash is a common practice in the country. This leads to

pollution in our environment, as a result of the various components contained in them (Kanhari *et al.*, 2020).

Incinerated hospital waste has been found to contain more heavy metals like chromium, cadmium, lead, magnesium, zinc and other metals (Ghobakhloo *et al.*, 2024). Exposure can pose public health problem such as acute respiratory syndromes, gastrointestinal abnormalities and various cancers (Winiarska *et al.*, 2024)

Heavy metals are generally defined as metals with relatively high densities ($>5\text{g/cm}^3$) atomic weights, or atomic numbers (Iroegbulem *et al.*, 2023; Iyama *et al.*, 2023). The term "Heavy metals" is used to describe more than a dozen elements that are metals or metalloids. Though they are natural constituents of the earth's crust, there are also anthropogenic sources, in small amounts, they enter the human body via food, drinking water and air.

The most common heavy metals found at contaminated sites in order of abundance are Pb, Cr, As, Zn, Cd, Cu and Hg. Medical waste is considered as a source of contamination of land and water. If not rendered harmless before it is buried in land or disposed in water (Adepoju *et al.*, 2024). The harmful chemicals from biomedical waste may pollute air, water and land that in turn may cause health problems to the residents (Shabani *et al.*, 2024).

Incinerated hospital waste has been found to contain more heavy metals like Chromium, Cadmium, lead, Mercury, Zinc and other metals (Ghobakhloo *et al.*, 2024). Acute exposures to high levels cause nausea, vomiting, gastrointestinal abnormalities and dermatitis. Chronic exposures to heavy metals cause cumulative toxic effects, which affect various systems in the body depending on the heavy metal involved (Parui *et al.*, 2024)

Soils are the major sink for heavy metals released into the environment by so many anthropogenic activities and most metals do not undergo microbial or chemical degradation and their total concentration in soils persist for a long time after their introduction (Corvalán *et al.*, 2024). Heavy metals contamination of soil may pose risks and hazards to humans and the ecosystem through direct ingestion or contact with contaminated soil, the food chain (soil-plant-human or soil-plant-animal-human), drinking of contaminated groundwater e.t.c. (Eigbike *et al.*, 2024)

Lead is causing concern in particular due to the

possible impacts on children. Lead influences the nervous system by slowing down neural response (Huang *et al.*, 2024). This influences learning abilities and behaviour. Children are exposed to lead right from their birth, as children in the embryonic stage receive lead from their mothers through the blood (Chbihi *et al.*, 2024). Children exposed to lead via dust and soil contaminated by deposition from air and other sources. In the environment, lead is known to be toxic to plants, animals and microorganisms. Effects are generally limited to specially contaminated areas (Debroy *et al.*, 2024).

Particularly in the renal cortex of the kidneys, cadmium buildup causes renal dysfunction, including poor protein, glucose, and amino acid absorption. Renal tubular injury, or kidney damage, is most likely the major health consequence. (Bautista *et al.*, 2024).

Renal stone development and hypercalciuria are other symptoms of the disruption in calcium metabolism. Cadmium is categorized as class 1 by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). (Milanković *et al.*, 2024).

In general, cadmium is more accessible, more mobile in soil, and has a tendency to bioaccumulate. Animal and plant life does not require cadmium. The overall population who does not smoke is primarily exposed to cadmium through diet. Other pathways make up a very minor portion of the total intake. The human body accumulates cadmium, particularly in the kidneys. (Adamo *et al.*, 2024; Nungula *et al.*, 2024; and Satarug, 2024)

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from Pyrex (Nigeria). They included; nitric acid, hydrochloric acid,

2.1 THE STUDY AREA

University of Benin is situated within the Ovia North-East local Government area of Benin City, Edo state Of Nigeria. It lies between the geographical coordinates of longitude 536' and 0.53" E and of latitude 6°20' and 1.32" N.

2.2 SAMPLING LOCATION

Sampling sites used for this study is located within the premises of the University of Benin Health Center

facility. An incinerator is made out of the Center's combustion pit. It is approximately 8 feet deep and well protected from ground contamination with concrete walls. It also has a metallic cover to prevent rodents from assessing the wastes in it as well as limit air contamination during wastes combustion. Due to constant burning over the years, the cover has corroded significantly leaving observable opening. Hazardous hospital wastes are usually combusted in this local incinerator during the dry seasons of the year.

2.3 SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Soil samples were collected weekly from around adopted incinerator, soil within the University of Benin Health Center and soil samples from Capitol (before UNIBEN Chancellor residence) in the same University of Benin which served as the control site. Sampling was done from January to December 2017. Composite surface soil samples were collected for the entire sampling duration.

Collected soil samples were wrapped in polyethylene bags and placed in a refrigerator.

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a probability 0.05 was considered as significant.

2.4 SAMPLING PREPARATION

All foreign objects like roots and gravel sized materials were picked and separated from the dried samples. 10g of the samples were weighed into porcelain crucibles using chemical balance and then oven dried at a temperature of 105 °C and 1g was then weighed into a labeled 100ml conical flask (Qiu *et al.*, 2018).

2.5 Cleaning of glassware

All apparatus were washed with detergents then rinsed with distilled water. The glassware was then dried in a hot oven at 105^oC.

2.6 Soil digestion

Well mixed samples of 1g each were weighed using a Scientech Zeta series electronic balance. The samples were put into 250 ml glass beaker and digested with 24 ml of aqua regia and then evaporated to near dryness. The soil samples were then dissolved in 30ml of distilled water, filtered through a 0.45 μm

membrane paper and then made up to 100 ml with distilled water prior to AAS analysis (Begum *et al.*, 2009). Duplicate samples were analyzed

The resulting solution was stored in a pre-cleaned polyethylene bottle until time for analysis. All the soil samples were analyzed for Zn, Pb, Cd, Cr, and Mn using AAS, using appropriate lamps and resonance wavelength of the metals, at Department of Chemistry Research Laboratory, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The concentrations of the various heavy metals studied for the duration of the study are presented in Tables 1.1-1.5, and figures 1.1-1.2 below

Results obtained indicate a concentration range of 1.217±0.264 mg/kg to 0.483±0.248 mg/kg for Zn for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 0.200±0.276 mg/kg to 0.083±0.041 mg/kg for Pb for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 0.037±0.049mg/kg to 0.002±0.004mg/kg for Cd for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 2.322±1.140mg/kg to 0.705±0.385mg/kg for Cr for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of March, 21.767±7.710mg/kg to 20.050±6.129mg/kg for Fe for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of November, 2.582±1.314mg/kg to 1.810±0.713mg/kg for Fe for the duration of the sampling with the highest concentration obtained in the month of November, as seen from table 1.2.

Results from Table 1.1 show that Fe had the highest mean concentration (across the months) of 12.476±0.315 mg/kg and Cd had the lowest, 0.003±0.005 mg/kg among the heavy metals found in soils around the Control. The descending order of metal content was Fe<Mn<Cr<Zn<Pb<Cd. Similar trends were observed for the results for Health Centre and incinerator sites in Table 1.1 where the mean concentrations of Fe (across the months) were 23.467±0.861 mg/kg and 26.258±1.200 mg/kg respectively and Cd had the lowest, 0.003±0.005 mg/kg among the heavy metals found in soil. The descending order of metal

Figure 1: A bar chart showing heavy metal concentration across the three sites

Table 1: Summary of Mean Concentration of Heavy Metals in Soils across the Sites

Parameters	Control	Health Center	Incinerator	WHO Values	p-values
Zn (mg/kg)	0.467±0.267	0.800±0.374	1.135±0.281	300.000	4.2E-09
Pb (mg/kg)	0.033±0.049	0.133±0.098	0.242±0.162	100.000	0.007809
Cd (mg/kg)	0.003±0.005	0.133±0.098	0.023±0.036	3.000	0.21624
Cr (mg/kg)	0.725±0.316	1.619±0.737	2.118±0.881	100.000	1.05E-07
Fe (mg/kg)	12.476±0.315	23.467±0.861	26.258±1.200	-	1.13E-23
Mn (mg/kg)	0.922±0.073	2.465±0.295	2.465±0.295	1000.000	1.44E-15

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Control site

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	-0.046	1				
Cd	-0.046	0.625*	1			
Cr	0.169	-0.706*	-0.694*	1		
Fe	0.413	-0.236	-0.119	0.185	1	
Mn	0.031	-0.546	-0.521	0.454	0.407	1

Table 3: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Health Center

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	0.049	1				
Cd	0.049	-0.437	1			
Cr	0.261	-0.602*	0.071	1		
Fe	0.333	0.379	-0.057	0.266	1	
Mn	-0.472	0.317	-0.050	0.074	0.247	1

Table 4: Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Incinerator

	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	Fe	Mn
Zn	1					
Pb	0.679*	1				
Cd	0.466	0.873**	1			
Cr	0.638*	0.895**	0.733**	1		
Fe	0.111	0.000	-0.128	0.179	1	
Mn	0.186	0.020	0.036	0.100	0.782**	1

content was Fe > Mn > Cr > Zn > Pb > Cd. The concentration of heavy metals at the three sites shows a relative decrease with distance from the source (Incinerator > Health Center > Control). This may be attributed to contamination of soil within the immediate vicinity of the incinerator by ash which could be aided by wind

as the adopted incinerator has an observable opening due to corrosion as a result of continuous burning. The Incinerator recorded high mean concentrations of heavy metal contents in the three sites across the months.

From Table 1.2, the result shows the mean concentrations of heavy metals in the soils across the month. In the month of March, it was observed that the mean concentration of Zn, Pb, Cd, and Cr recorded higher concentrations (1.217±0.264 mg/kg, 0.200±0.276 mg/kg, 0.037±0.049 mg/kg and 2.322±1.140 mg/kg) respectively as compared to other months studied while Fe and Mn recorded higher mean concentrations (21.767±7.710 mg/kg, 2.582±1.314 mg/kg) respectively with Fe having the highest mean concentration (21.767±7.710 mg/kg) among all the metals studied. Zn had the lowest mean concentration (0.483±0.248 mg/kg) in the month of October, Pb had the lowest mean concentration (0.083±0.075, 0.083±0.041 mg/kg) in the month of September and October having approximately the same value. Cd had the lowest mean concentration (0.002±0.004 mg/kg) in the month of October, Cr had the lowest mean concentration (0.705±0.385 mg/kg) in the month of April, Fe had the lowest mean concentration (20.050±6.129 mg/kg) in the month of May and Mn had the lowest mean concentrations (1.810±0.713 mg/kg) in the month of September. All the metal concentrations in soil were below the WHO maximum allowed limits (Table 1.1-1.2). The concentrations of heavy metals in these soils were low compared to that of polluted soils as reported in the research work done by Yahaya et al. (2009) and Timothy and Olajumoke (2013). The concentration of heavy metals at the three sites shows a relative decrease with distance from the source (Incinerator > Health Centre > Control). This may be attributed to contamination of soil within the immediate vicinity of the incinerator by ash which could be aided

Figure 2: A bar chart showing heavy metal concentrations across the months

by the wind as the adopted incinerator has an observable opening due to corrosion as a result of continuous burning. The Incinerator recorded high concentrations of heavy metals studied as compared to the Health Centre and the control site which in turn had the least concentrations of heavy metals studied.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). A probability ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. From Table 1.1, P-values at (probability ≤ 0.05) of (Zn = 4.2E-09), (Pb = 0.007809), (Cd = 0.21624), (Cr = 1.05E-07), (Fe = 1.13E-23) and (Mn = 1.44E-15) except for Pb and Cd, others listed were all less than 0.001. This indicates that the various sites/location have significant effect on the mean concentrations of the various heavy metals. While for Pb and Cd, the various site/location had no effects on their mean concentrations. From Table 1.2, P-values at (probability ≤ 0.05) of (Zn = 4.89E-09), (Pb = 0.303), (Cd = 0.040), (Cr = 7.54E-08), (Fe = 0.010) and (Mn = 0.00027) were all less than 0.005. This indicates that the months have significant effect on the concentration of the various metal concentrations respectively.

From Table 1.3, results of the Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the control site, *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Significant positive correlations were observed between Cd and Pb, as Cd concentrations increase, concentrations of Pb also increase while significant negative correlations were observed between Cr and Pb, Cr and Cd, as concentrations of Cr increase, concentrations of Pb and Cd decrease. This indicates that they were from the same source of contamination.

The results from Table 1.4, Correlation matrix for heavy metals at the Health Center *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Significant negative correlation was observed for Cr and Pb, as the concentrations of Cr increase, concentrations of Pb decrease.

From Table 1.5, the results of the Correlation Matrix for heavy metals at the Incinerator *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Significant positive correlation was observed between Pb and Zn, Cd and Pb, Cr and Pb, Cr and Cd, Mn and Fe. Significant positive correlation indicates that as one increases the other increases. Significant negative correlation was observed Fe and Cd, negative

correlation indicate that as one increases the other decreases.

Conclusion: The results from the sites/locations were higher than control site, indicating a clear case of pollution. Comparison of heavy metal concentration in soil with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that they are all below the set limits. The soils at the adopted medical incinerator had higher concentrations of heavy metals than the soils around the Health Centre. Medical waste when not properly disposed poses serious threat to public health and should be disposed of appropriately.

RECOMMENDATION

Comparing current study with WHO maximum allowed limits showed that the heavy metals concentrations were below. Appropriate care should be taken to avoid further increase in the concentrations as bottom ash could increase the concentrations. This could be done by ensuring the proper sealing of the adopted incinerator.

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Appendix

Various concentrations of Zn

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.00	0.70	0.40	0.20	0.30	0.20
	0.80	0.60	0.60	0.30	0.30	0.20
Health center	1.30	1.20	1.00	0.50	0.40	0.60
	1.30	1.10	0.90	0.60	0.30	0.40
Incinerator (around)	1.50	1.40	1.30	0.70	0.80	1.20
	1.40	1.22	1.20	0.80	0.80	1.30

Various concentrations of Pb

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00
	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10
Health center	0.00	0.30	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20
	0.10	0.30	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.20
Incinerator (around)	0.50	0.20	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.20
	0.60	0.10	0.30	0.20	0.10	0.30

Various concentrations of Cd

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Health center	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Incinerator (around)	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01
	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00

Various concentrations of Cr

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.01	0.32	1.00	1.00	0.30	0.72
1.00	0.37	1.01	0.97	0.30	0.70	
Health center	2.40	0.61	2.37	1.30	0.97	2.11
2.42	0.57	2.40	1.31	0.97	2.00	
Incinerator (around)	3.54	1.20	2.50	1.57	1.31	2.58
3.56	1.16	2.53	1.59	1.29	2.59	

Various concentrations of Fe

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	12.80	12.40	12.20	12.70	12.90	12.20
13.01	12.20	12.40	12.50	12.40	12.00	
Health center	24.20	23.70	22.60	23.30	22.40	24.40
24.50	23.80	22.50	23.00	22.50	24.70	
Incinerator (around)	26.10	25.80	25.20	25.50	26.60	28.70
25.80	25.60	25.40	25.30	26.50	28.60	

Various concentrations of Mn

Months	March	April	May	Sept	Oct	Nov
Control	1.02	0.77	0.91	0.91	0.95	0.96
1.00	0.80	0.93	0.90	0.96	0.95	
Health center	2.24	2.41	2.39	2.10	2.55	2.97
2.27	2.38	2.43	2.13	2.72	2.99	
Incinerator (around)	3.24	3.12	3.00	2.42	3.75	3.82
3.25	3.08	2.59	2.40	3.75	3.80	

ANOVA

Zn

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	2.696056	5	0.539211	25.71209	4.2E-05
2.602987					
Months	2.656056	5	0.531211	25.33061	4.89E-05
2.602987					
Error	0.524278	25	0.020971		
Total	5.876389	35			

Pb

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	0.268056	5	0.053611	4.058032	0.0073
2.602987					
Months	0.084722	5	0.016944	1.28259	0.3021
2.602987					
Error	0.330278	25	0.013211		
Total	0.683056	35			

Cd

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	0.002981	5	0.000596	1.53067	0.2161
2.602987					
Months	0.005381	5	0.001076	2.763195	0.0401
2.602987					
Error	0.009736	25	0.000389		
Total	0.018097	35			

Fe

SoV	SS	df	MS	F	P-val
F crit					
Locations	1274.29	5	254.8581	453.1056	1.13E-05
2.602987					
Months	10.95335	5	2.190669	3.894735	0.0091
2.602987					
Error	14.06174	25	0.562469		
Total	1299.305	35			

Mn

SoV F crit	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Locations 2.602987	32.11669	5	6.423338	97.45652	1.44E-15
Months 2.602987	2.372556	5	0.474511	7.199404	0.00027
Error	1.647744	25	0.06591		
Total	36.13699	35			

Cr

SoV F crit	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Locations 2.602987	11.96103	5	2.392205	18.57903	1.05E-07
Months 2.602987	12.38289	5	2.476578	19.23431	7.54E-08
Error	3.218958	25	0.128758		
Total	27.56288	35			